

**SURFACE ELECTROMYOGRAPHY
FOR THE ASSESSMENT OF
NEUROMUSCULAR DISORDERS**

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this study was to investigate the usefulness of Surface Electromyography (SEMG), in the clinical laboratory. Towards this goal, recordings from 94 normal subjects (NOR) and 20 neuromuscular subjects (11 myopathy (MYO) and 9 neuropathy (NEURO)) were recorded at 10, 30, 50, 70 and 100% of maximum voluntary contraction. These signals were analysed in the time, frequency and bi-frequency domains.

The time-domain parameters, turns and zero crossings per second, increased with force level (FL), for all three groups. Frequency-domain, median and mean frequencies, decreased with FL for the NOR group. Frequency at maximum power was unaffected with FL, but differences were found between all groups of subjects. Maximum and total power increased with FL for all groups, with MYO subjects having significantly higher values for the latter parameter. Bi-frequency parameter, bispectrum peak amplitude increased with FL only for the NOR group and significant differences were found between all three groups. Significant differences between the Gaussianity of the NEURO group and the other two groups were found. The location and slope of the bispectrum peak amplitude was unaffected with FL, however significant differences between the NEURO group and the other two groups were found. Repeatability and reliability measurements on a selected group of subjects gave very good results. Correlation analysis on all possible parameter pairs was performed for normal values. Excellent and good results are presented and compared with the corresponding pairs for patient data, where differences for certain parameters were found. It was shown that all parameters investigated were not affected by age or gender.

Cluster analysis using the KNN algorithm was used to perform two (a. NORMAL/ABNORMAL (MYO and NEURO) and b. MYO/NEURO), and three class (NOR/MYO/NEURO) classification models. The percentage of correct classifications score for NORMAL/ABNORMAL and MYO/NEURO models were

94.4% and 70% respectively. The percentage of correct classifications score for the three class models varied from 59.3% when an equal number of subjects (9 NOR/9 MYO/9 NEURO) was used to 82.9% when 91 NOR/11 MYO/9 NEURO subjects were used.

Self Organising Feature Maps give visually the mapping of two (a. NORMAL/ABNORMAL and b. MYO/NEURO) and three (NOR/MYO/NEURO) class models, with the former group presenting a better discrimination.

Based on the findings of this study, it is concluded that the SEMG system investigated can be used successfully and effectively as an additional tool by the neurophysiologist for the assessment and monitoring of muscle function. It is proposed, that the system can be used “blindly” without sharing any prior information or knowledge about the possible classification of the subject, by the referring neurophysiologist.

*In the Memory of my daughter Irene,
and to those who inspired and encouraged me
everyday.*

*My wife Nasso, my son Andreas,
my parents Andreas and Kati and
my brother Kyriacos.*

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SYMBOLS AND ABBREVIATIONS

A/D	Analog to Digital Converter
Ag	Silver
Ag/AgCl	Silver-Silver Chloride
ALS	Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis
AN	Anconeus
ANN	Artificial Neural Networks
ANOVA	Analysis of Variance
ASCII	American Standard Code for Information Interchange
ASYM	Skewness
AVR	Average Rectified Values
BB	Biceps Brachii
Bfx	Bispectrum peak amplitude in the x-direction
Bfxslope	Bispectrum peak slope in the x-direction
Bfy	Bispectrum peak amplitude in the y-direction
Bfyslope	Bispectrum peak slope in the y-direction
Bmax	Maximum amplitude of bispectrum
BPN	Back-propagation network
BSS	British Safety Standards
CC	Correct Classification
CI	Confidence Interval
CING	Cyprus Institute of Neurology and Genetics
Cl ⁻	Chloride
CNS	Central Nervous System
CV	Coefficient of variation
Ed _{xy}	Euclidean distance
EEG	Electroencephalography
EMG	Electromyography
EP	Evoked Potentials

F	Female
FF	Finger Flexors
FFT	Fast Fourier Transform
FL	Force level
FN	False Negative
FP	False Positive
FT	Fourier Transform
HFB	Higher frequency band
HL	Healthy subjects
HOS	Higher Order Spectrum
HPR	Half Power Range
IBPN	Improved Back Propagation Network
ICC	Interclass Correlation Coefficient
IEC	International electro technical committee
IEMG	Integrated EMG
IFT	Inverse Fourier Transform
IMF	Initial Median frequency
IVC	Isometric Voluntary Contraction
K ⁺	Potassium ions
KNN	k-Nearest Neighbour
LE	Linear Envelope
LFB	Lower frequency band
LVQ	Learning Vector Quantification Network
M	Male
MED	Median Frequency
MFCV	Muscle Fibre Conduction Velocity
MND	Motor Neuron Disease
MNF	Mean Spectral Frequency
MPF	Mean Power Frequency
MRC	Medical Research Council
MU	Motor Unit
MUAP	Motor Unit Action Potential
MVC	Maximum voluntary contraction
MYO	Myopathy subjects

n	Sample size
Na ⁺	Sodium ions
NEURO	Neuropathy subjects
NN	Neural Network
NOR	Normal subjects
NS	Non Significant
P _{5%}	Five percent power range
P _{10%}	Ten percent power range
P _{25%}	Twenty five percent power range
P _{75%}	Seventy five percent power range
P _{90%}	Ninety percent power range
P _{95%}	Ninety five percent power Range
PC	Personal Computer
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
Pfmean	Mean power frequency
Pfmed	Median power frequency
Pfx	Maximum power frequency
PLS	Primary Lateral Sclerosis
Pmax	Maximum power
Pmed, P _{1/2}	Half power range
PPK	Peak Power Frequency
PR	Precision
PS	Power Spectrum
PSD	Power Spectrum Density
Ptotal	Total power
Q	Decline Factor (Relates amplitude to distance)
RBN	Radial Basic Network
RE	Recall
RF	Rectus Femoris
RMS	Root Mean Square
S	Significant
SD	Standard Deviation
SE	Sensitivity
SEM	Standard Error of the Mean

SEMG	Surface electromyography
SENIAM	Surface EMG for Non-Invasive Assessment of Muscles
sg	Test for gaussianity
SIQR	Semi-Inter-quartile Range
sl	Test for Linearity
SMA	Spinal Muscular Atrophy
SOFM	Self Organising Feature Maps
SP	Specificity
t/s	Turns per second
TA	Tibialis Anterior
TB	Tibialis
TN	True Negative
TOC	Third Order Cumulant
TP	True Positive
VL	Vastus lateralis
VM	Vastus medialis
ZC	Zero Crossings
zc/s	Zero crossings per second
Σx	sum of samples
σ	Variance
→	Shifted
↑	Increased
↓	Decreased
↔	remained constant

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Chapter 1
Introduction

Chapter 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Introduction

Early detection and diagnosis are generally accepted today as being essential tools in managing any of the forty or so known neuromuscular disorders.

Clinical examination and laboratory tests help towards managing and even preventing at some instances these neuromuscular disorders through prenatal diagnosis and genetic counselling. Information obtained may lead to the understanding of the nature and hopefully the treatment of these diseases. More specifically laboratory investigations include neurophysiological tests, nerve and muscle biopsies and biochemical analysis and more recently DNA analysis for the localization and identification of genes. Neurophysiological tests are carried out using needle electrodes. And apart from the fact that patients are subjected to considerable pain and discomfort, as well as the risk of infection, constant expert supervision is necessary, which renders the whole process quite lengthy. In paediatric examinations and tests in particular, there are even more difficulties in using needle electrodes, and long term monitoring is quite difficult, Merletti et al 1989. Because of the reasons mentioned, several researchers have attempted to examine the diagnostic abilities of surface rather than needle electrodes for various neuromuscular disorders, and several references were looked into during this research.

Recent advances in signal processing techniques have extended the quality and quantity of information, which may be extracted from signals of surface electrodes, and this research aims at establishing whether surface electromyography techniques can indeed provide suitable and useful diagnostic results and information.

A surface detected signal is preferred only for obtaining “global” information about the time and/or intensity of superficial muscle activation, Merletti et al (1989). Features extracted from the recorded electrical activity of the muscles known as Electromyography (EMG), aim towards detecting any abnormalities in the motor

unit (MU), the smallest functional unit of the muscle. The part of the recorded EMG indicating the activity of a single MU is termed the Motor Unit Action Potential (MUAP). Such an activity is usually recorded, as already mentioned, with needle electrodes, enabling the examination of the shape of the MUAP (amplitude, duration, number of phases and turns) and hence providing a useful diagnosis of the neuromuscular disorder, Christodoulou et al (1999). From as early as 1963, O'Connell and Gardner examined the usefulness of surface EMG in clinical applications and examined the abilities and limitations of such a recording in kinesiological studies. An early attempt for identifying MUAPs from an examination recorded with surface electrodes was performed in 1964 by Harris, Rosov, Cooper and Lysaught who used rubber suction cups. In 1966, Grossman and Weiner warned physiologists against accepting surface electromyography as a diagnostic tool, due to the phenomenon of cross talk, signal attenuation and filtering.

Today though, advances in signal processing methods and technological advances in surface electrodes, have made it possible to extract more and more information from the complex electromyography signal in contrast to the initial belief. Even so analysis of signals recorded with surface electrodes has numerous drawbacks. Furthermore many discrepancies exist between findings of various research groups. This could be attributed to:

- (i) The limited and different number of subjects examined in most of the cases (4-94), Hagberg et al (1982).
- (ii) The difference in recording time (1 to 45 seconds), since fatigue may influence results at longer recording times; Gerdle et al (1990), Krivickas et al (1998).
- (iii) The method of statistical analysis used.
- (iv) The force level exhibited; Hagberg et al (1982), Gerdle et al (1990), Rainoldi et al (1999), Farina et al (2002).
- (v) The positioning of electrodes.
- (vi) Even more generally, to the variations in the experimental conditions, Krivickas et al, (1998).

This has urged the American Association of Electrodiagnostic Medicine to publish a statement, Haig et al (1999), stating clearly that: "At present there are no clinical

indications for the use of Surface EMG (SEMG), in the diagnosis and treatment of disorders of muscle and nerves. However, it may prove clinically useful in the future for the non-invasive monitoring of the progression of a nerve or muscle disorder. Furthermore, it may become a complementary test in the primary diagnosis of such disorders”.

1.2 Original Aspects of this Work

The original aspects of this work are:

- (i) The design of a simple, non-invasive, user-friendly recording set-up, which could be used with slight modifications on most muscles of the four extremities. It has been used on normal subjects, children and subjects suffering with neuromuscular disorders alike, with the same degree of ease and accuracy. From the experience gained through this study, non-medical personnel (biomedical engineers, technicians etc) may perform the recording procedure in approximately 20 minutes.
- (ii) The development of a large data bank of recordings, containing data taken from 94 normal and 20 subjects suffering with neuromuscular disorders.
- (iii) The analysis of that data and the calculation of fourteen parameters, (two from the time-domain, five from the frequency-domain and seven from the bi-frequency domain).
- (iv) The influence of increased voluntary contraction (IVC) on those parameters was examined, and normal and pathological values were computed.
- (v) Reliability measurements were performed.
- (vi) Repeatability measurements were performed.
- (vii) Age and gender dependence was examined for normal subjects.
- (viii) Correlation analysis between parameters examined was performed.
- (ix) Cluster analysis was performed for feature classification and Self Organising Feature Maps for visualisation. Two SEMG classifier systems were developed. One for classifying a subject as NORMAL or ABNORMAL and then to distinguish between MYO and NEURO patients. The second classification system was a three class classification model to classify a subject as NOR, MYO or NEURO. A normal subject

is defined as a subject with no neuromuscular disorder symptoms. On the contrary an abnormal subject is defined for this study as a subject suffering with diseases that involve the weakness or wasting of the body muscles.

It should be emphasised that to the best of my knowledge no other studies have published normal and abnormal values computing bi-frequency techniques on SEMG recordings. Using only frequency techniques may lead to erroneous results if the signal recorded is assumed to be Gaussian distributed. If however bi-frequency techniques are used, the results are less distribution dependant.

1.3 Guide to thesis Contents

In Chapter 2, the Motor Unit and the Motor Unit Action Potential are introduced, followed by a short description on the development of surface EMG electrodes, the material used and their construction. The SEMG signal with its various components is then described followed by an introduction into the neuromuscular disorders and their effect on the SEMG signal.

Chapter 3 presents the early developments in electromyography and the advances made in quantitative EMG. Time, frequency and bi-frequency analysis are introduced, followed by tables listing previous studies on SEMG analysis (and only a few on needle EMG), together with a brief description for each study.

Chapter 4 describes the methodology, including the recording set-up and procedure as well as the acquisition methods. A detailed explanation of the statistical analysis was performed to investigate:

- (i) The influence of IVC on the three groups of subjects.
- (ii) Differences between normal and pathological subjects.
- (iii) Reliability measurements.
- (iv) Repeatability of measurements.
- (v) Increasing-decreasing IVC dependence.
- (vi) Age and gender dependence.

Furthermore correlation analysis, Cluster Analysis and Self-Organising Feature Maps are also explained in Chapter 4.

Chapter 5 tabulates results obtained using the statistical analysis as explained in Chapter 4. In particular, the influence of force level is examined on normal and abnormal values, which are then compared between them. Reliability and repeatability measurements are presented, as well as age and gender analysis, and correlation analysis between parameter pairs. Cluster analysis and SOFM mapping results are finally given.

Discussion of findings of this work are reported in Chapter 6, together with a discussion regarding protocols followed, of the statistical analysis performed, possible sources of errors are listed, and a comparison with other studies is attempted whenever possible. Based on the results obtained in this study, a short description of a proposed diagnostic system is given.

The last Chapter, Chapter 7, gives the conclusions of this work and makes suggestions for further research.

Five Appendices provide additional information. Appendix 1 is a copy of the short description of the experiment, given to each participant. This was approved by the ethical committee of the Cyprus Institute of Neurology and Genetics. Appendix 2 the form filled in during recording and Appendix 3 provides the technical specifications of the data acquisition hardware used. Appendix 4 includes various papers published in Conference proceedings and a paper submitted for publication. Appendix 5 shows plots from the three domains, at maximum voluntary contraction for the three subjects, one normal, one myopathy and one neuropathy patient. Finally a CD is included with raw data recorded during the five force levels, from a subject of each group. Values obtained during recordings are attached as Excel files on the CD.

Chapter 2
Principles of SEMG

Chapter 2

PRINCIPLES OF SEMG

A brief introduction into the human motor unit anatomy is presented in this chapter. The main types of surface electrodes and their recording characteristics are discussed, as well as their effect on the recorded signal. An overview of the main groups of neuromuscular disorders are presented and their influence on the recorded SEMG signal.

2.1 The Motor Unit

The nervous system consisting of the brain, spinal cord and nerves makes up the Central Nervous System (CNS). The nerves are made up from cells commonly known as neurons. In general the purpose of a neuron is to generate and / or propagate electrical excitation in the form of an action potential. From a functional point of view there are three classes of neurons:

- (i) Afferent neurons, which communicate information from the periphery part of the body to the CNS.
- (ii) Efferent neurons, which communicate information from the CNS to various organs such as the muscles and glands.
- (iii) Interneurons, which make connections between afferent and efferent neurons, constituting 99% of the neurons in the body.

Although there are different types of neurons, they all consist of a cell body or soma, which contains the nucleus and most of the chemicals required for the cell metabolic and synthetic machinery, dendrites, an axon, and axon or nerve terminals. Dendrites are thread-like parts originating from the cell body and can vary in length. Their purpose is to pass information into the cell and allow interactions with other neighbouring cells. The axon may be considered as the longest thread, (may be up to a metre long, with a diameter of 15 μ m), whose aim is to conduct impulses away from the cell body and may pass information to a muscle at a considerable distance. When the axon reaches a muscle, it branches out and innervates a number of muscle fibres through the end plates. The number of muscle fibres, served by the same axon, varies according to the purpose of each muscle. For example the muscles controlling fine movements and adjustments such as the movements of the eye

have the smallest number of muscle fibres (5-10), whereas the gastrocnemius muscle consists of about 1600 fibres. The neuron and all the muscle fibres supplied by the same anterior horn cell constitute the Motor Unit (MU), Fig. 2.1, which is considered as the smallest unit that may be activated by a voluntary contraction causing all combining muscle fibres to act simultaneously. Figure 2.1 also demonstrates the electrical activity within the MU territory, as this is picked-up by a needle electrode, Fig. 2.1B. This electrical activity, Fig. 2.1C, is summed up to produce the Motor Unit Action Potential (MUAP), Fig. 2.1D, which is described in detail immediately afterwards in this chapter.

Muscle fibres found in human muscle, may be divided in three groups, fibres I, IIa and IIb, Dubowitz et al (1973). The grouping is done according to the degree of fatigue resistance, which the fibres present. For example type I fibres are fatigue resistant, meaning that they can perform an exercise for a long time, but they are capable of less force. They are known to have a slow twitch-contraction time. Type IIa fibres are also fatigue resistant but have a fast twitch-contraction time and are recruited immediately after type I fibres. Finally type IIb fibres, fatigue rapidly and have a fast twitch-contraction time, but are capable of higher force levels.

2.1.1 Motor Unit Action Potential

It was stated earlier that the purpose of the neuron is to generate and / or propagate electrical excitation in the form of an action potential. This action potential is developed through an electrochemical process, meaning that the chemicals within the cell body result in an electrical signal. When a neuron is not sending a signal it is said to be *at rest*. At rest the inside of the neuron has a negative charge relative to the outside of the neuron. Potassium ions (K^+), having a positive charge together with sodium ions (Na^+), are the most important ions found in the nervous system, and may cross the neuron membrane easily. In contrast to Potassium ions, still at rest, other ions like Chloride (Cl^-), which are negatively charged, are also attempting with a certain degree of difficulty to cross the neuron membrane. These and more ion movements occur, resulting in a difference in the voltage between the inside and the outside of the neuron equal to $-70mV$. This is termed the *resting potential* indicating the electrical difference between the inside and the outside of the neuron at rest.

Figure 2.1 Schematic illustration of a MUAP recorded with a needle electrode. A. Longitudinal. B. Cross sectional view of the motor unit with the recording electrode and the contributing to the MUAP fibres. C. Single fibre action potentials as they arrive at the recording surface. D. MUAP calculated by the sum of action potentials in C. (Redrawn from Pattichis (1992), p.41).

If however, a sudden pulse like change in the membrane potential occurs (lasting approximately half a millisecond) then a nerve impulse is generated. This enables information signals to be transmitted from one part of the nervous system to another. This sudden pulse is termed *action potential* and may occur by any factor that suddenly increases the permeability of the membrane to sodium ions. An electrical stimulation, a mechanical compression of the fibre, application of chemicals to the membrane, or almost any other event disturbing the resting state of the membrane is capable to produce such a pulse, Guyton 1981. Two are the main stages of such an action potential, the membrane depolarisation and the membrane repolarisation shown in Fig. 2.2. The membrane at rest is illustrated in Fig. 2.2A, with a negative charge inside the fibre membrane and a positive charge outside the fibre membrane. If any of the reasons mentioned earlier however occur, the permeability of the membrane to sodium ions will suddenly increase. This will cause

many of the sodium ions being outside the fibre in large populations, to rush inside and produce a positive charge inside the fibre and hence the normal resting potential of -70mV disappears (Fig. 2.2B). The sudden change from negative to positive charge inside the fibre is termed *depolarisation*. The positive potential developed momentarily inside the fibre is called *reversal potential*. Immediately after depolarisation, the pores of the membrane become more permeable than normal to potassium ions, but almost impermeable to sodium ions. Hence no more sodium ions are moved to the inside, and on the same time potassium ions move to the outside because of their high concentration inside the fibre. However, because of the positive charge of the potassium ions, the excess positive charge inside the fibre, is transferred once again outside the fibre and hence the normal resting potential is established. This is termed *repolarisation* and illustrated in Fig. 2.2C.

Figure 2.2 Sequential events during the action potential, showing: A. The normal resting potential. B. development of a reversal potential during depolarisation. C. re-establishment of the normal resting potential during repolarisation. (Redrawn from Guyton (1981), p.109).

As mentioned earlier by placing a recording electrode, inside the MU territory, a potential may be recorded known as *electromyography* (EMG), provided that the current generated by the depolarising muscle fibre or axon, flows through the recording electrode into a signal amplifier and returns to the patient through a ground lead. During an EMG recording, the

activities of many motor units may be recorded due to overlapping. Buchthal and Rosenfalck (1973) have proved that the intermingling of several motor units can be interpreted by the fact that each motor unit is not represented by a single action potential but by a multitude of action potentials which can be picked up separately at different sites within the motor unit. The maximum amplitude of the potentials recorded is proportional to the fibre density. In other words the amplitude will be greater in a muscle with more muscle fibres than another muscle with less fibres. The exact relation between the maximum amplitude and fibre concentration is however unknown. In Table 2.1 the number of motor units and average number of muscle fibres per motor unit in some human muscles is listed.

Table 2.1 Number of motor units and average number of muscle fibres per motor unit in human muscle (Buchthal et al (1980)).

Muscle	No. of Motor Axons	No. of muscle fibres per muscle x 1000	Average No. of muscle fibres per motor unit.
Biceps brachii	774	580	750
Brachioradialis	330	130	390
Interosseus dorsalis 1	119	40.5	340
Lumbricalis 1	98	10.3	110
Opponens pollicis	133	79	595
Masseter	1020	1000	980
Temporalis	1150	1500	1300
Gastrocnemius medius	580	1000	1720
Tibialis anterior	445	270	610

2.2 SEMG Electrodes

The recording electrode is one of the most important parts in set-up design. The quality of the signal obtained is greatly influenced by the type of electrodes used, their material and construction, their electrical characteristics and their geometry. Duchenee et al (1993) divides the recording electrodes in two main categories: (i) dry electrodes, which are in direct contact with the skin and (ii) floating electrodes, which use an electrolytic paste as an

interface between the skin and the metallic part of the electrode. Dry electrodes being more convenient have seen many improvements through out the years, although the basic idea does not differ significantly from the electrode developed by d'Arsonval more than 100 years ago. His electrode consisted of a silver electrode where a thin silver chloride layer has been laid down and put in contact with the skin by means of an electrolytic paste.

One important improvement though in the design of surface recording electrodes, was the development of the so-called *active electrodes*, Merletti et al (1989). The main difference between active electrodes and a single dry or a single floating electrode is that an active electrode includes at least two detection surfaces and an impedance buffer or amplifier included in the device (electrode block), that is mounted directly on the electrodes. Active electrodes present lower noise, less movement artefacts, resulting in a better quality of detection, and lower power line interference. An active electrode is usually connected in a bipolar (differential) configuration either with one or two amplifiers, see Fig. 2.3

Figure 2.3 Single Differential amplifier

The average action potential propagation through muscle fibres and hence the muscle fibre conduction velocity may be estimated via a configuration shown in Fig. 2.4A with the corresponding recorded signal in Fig. 2.4B (A, B, C of the waveform being delayed signals and D non-delayed). However this configuration as shown by Broman et al. (1985a), may lead to false high values of conduction velocity due to the simultaneous presence of differential signals on the two electrode sets, probably due to cross talk, Fig. 2.4B. A simple solution is the double differential detection technique given in Fig. 2.4C, with the

corresponding recording signal illustrated in Fig. 2.4D (output from the first stages showing delayed and non-delayed signals) and Fig. 2.4E (output from the second stages showing cancellation of non-delayed signals).

Figure 2.4 Single and double differential techniques with corresponding waveforms. A. Detection with two differential amplifiers. B. Examples of delayed signals (A, B C). C. Double differential detection system. D. Outputs from the first stages showing delayed and non-delayed signals. E. Outputs from the second stages showing cancellation of non-delayed signals. (Redrawn from Merletti et al. (1989), p.117.).

Other techniques involved an array of electrodes, allowing a two-dimensional location of motor end plates, as well as the recording of MUAPs waveform properties.

As mentioned earlier the electrode is most important for the quality of the recorded signal and the following aspects need to be taken into consideration:

- (i) Electrode material and construction.
- (ii) Electrode size and shape.
- (iii) Interelectrode distance.
- (iv) Electrode input impedance.

Electrode material and construction. Many materials have been tested, however the preferred material by most researches is Silver-Silver Chloride (Ag/AgCl) and Silver (Ag). The material should be such as to allow a good contact between the electrode and skin, and low electrode-skin impedance. If an electrode block is used the electrode distance should be fixed and the plastic material used to hold the electrodes be of lightweight material. Electrode cables should be easily secured, to avoid the potential risk of movement artefacts.

Electrode size and shape. Hermens et al (2000), has found that although many sizes of detection surfaces have been used in the past, the preferred size is 10 mm of circular shape. Circular and bar electrodes do not differ much in performance characteristics, provided the pick-up area is nearly the same, Hermens et al (2000). However bar electrodes intersect more muscle fibres provided that $l \geq 0.785 w$, where l is the length and w the width of the electrode, De Luca (1995).

Interelectrode distance. Hermens et al (1999), suggests that when bipolar electrodes are being applied, on relatively small muscles, the inter electrode distance (which should be fixed), should not exceed $\frac{1}{4}$ of the muscle fibre length. It should be remembered that the interelectrode distance affects the bandwidth and amplitude of the recorded signal. A large interelectrode distance shifts the distance towards lower frequencies and may increase the amplitude. The most commonly used interelectrode distance is 10 mm. If larger distances are used this also implies larger electrodes, which may not be able to be used on relatively small muscles. In such a case the issue of crosstalk becomes quite important.

Electrode impedance. The electrode impedance plays an important role in the attenuation of the recorded signal. This impedance consists of the intrinsic impedance of the electrodes and the electrode skin impedance and must be less than the signal amplifier impedance in order to reduce the voltage drop across the electrode. It has been found that a ratio of amplifier to electrodes impedance of 100:1 is sufficient to neglect this voltage drop. This ratio should be maintained across the range of frequencies contained in the signal, keeping in mind that both impedances decrease as frequency increases. In modern amplifiers the amplifier input impedance ranges between 200-1000 M Ω and is in parallel with a capacitor of about 5-10 pf. The capacitor will cause the impedance to decrease at high frequencies.

2.3 The SEMG signal

The structural organization of the motor unit described earlier in this chapter, determines MUAP shape. Stalberg et al (1986), proposed that MUAP parameters reflect motor unit architecture, affected by neuromuscular diseases. Buchthal et al (1955) showed that the MUAP duration, the amplitude and the number of turns, might prove useful for the diagnosis of neuromuscular disorders. Today, with the advances made in computer hardware and signal processing techniques, more parameters may prove useful for the diagnosis of neuromuscular disorders even with the use of surface electrodes. When analysing the shape of a single MUAP alone as shown in Fig. 2.5, the following parameters may be analysed:

- (i) Duration.
- (ii) Amplitude.
- (iii) Spike duration.
- (iv) Number of phases.
- (v) Area.
- (vi) Spike area.
- (vii) Number of turns.

Figure 2.5 The different components of a MUAP.

Duration is the time interval from the initial take off of the potential till the return to the baseline. Its value in normal recordings is determined by the anatomical scattering of the endplate zone, Buchthal (1957). This was contributed to the various distances along which the muscle fibre action potential had to travel from the individual endplates before reaching the recording surface of the electrode. Later on, however, it was shown by Nandedkar et al (1988), that the numbers of fibres in a motor unit contribute much more to the duration than the spread of the endplate zone. Furthermore the same group highlighted the point that for the same MU, different durations of MUAP may be recorded, depending on the exact positioning of the electrode, and hence MUAP durations vary significantly in normal values.

The **amplitude** is measured from the minimum peak to the maximum peak. It is greatly influenced by the distance between the recording electrode and the active muscle fibres closest to it. Even the slightest difference in distance, has been shown from experiments performed with needle electrodes (0.5 –1.0 mm), (Buchthal 1957), a tremendous fall in amplitude. It is hence obvious that when recording with surface electrodes, only the closest fibres to the electrode contribute to the amplitude recorded, which reflects the density of

muscle fibres in the MU, the diameter of individual fibres and the temporal synchrony of the action potentials of different fibres.

The **spike duration** is measured from the first to the last positive peak (Fig. 2.5) of the MUAP, including satellite if present. This parameter, being more sensitive than the duration, is often used more in quantitative analysis. However it has been shown by Nandedkar et al (1988), that the spike duration of the MUAP depends mainly on the number and size of muscle fibres that are up to 420 μm from the active recording surface, which is usually an area containing 1 to 6 muscle fibres in a normal biceps brachii muscle. It is hence obvious that this parameter has a great importance in needle electrode recording only.

The **number of phases** is the number of baseline crossings exceeding a certain threshold. The configuration of the MUAP in healthy muscle is smooth and diphasic or triphasic. If a MUAP contains more than three phases it is classified as polyphasic, which is the case in approximately 12% of normal subject recordings. This could be the result of temporal dispersion in the conduction of impulses along the nerve or muscle fibres of the MU.

The **area** is computed by the sum of the rectified MUAP over the duration. The number and size of the muscle fibres closest to the recording electrode once again contribute the most to the area of the MUAP.

The **spike area** is computed by the sum of the MUAP over the spike duration. It reflects the number and the diameter of muscle fibres, as well as the temporal dispersion of action potentials of muscle fibres closest to the electrode.

The **number of turns** is the number of slope reversals separated from the previous one and the following one by amplitude predetermined threshold in the area 20 to 50 μV . The number of turns reflects properties of the motor unit that are similar to the number of phases, but may be more sensitive in certain muscles, as Falck has shown in 1983. He has shown that the number of turns increase with age in the tibialis anterior but not the number of phases.

2.4 Neuromuscular disorders and their effect on the SEMG signal

Neuromuscular disorders embrace a broad category of disorders covering conditions that cause weakness and wasting of the skeletal muscles. They affect components of a motor unit (motor neuron cells of the spinal cord, nerves, neuromuscular junctions, and muscle fibres). Neuromuscular disorders are accompanied either by (i) individual muscle fibre anatomy variations or (ii) changes in the architecture of the Motor Unit territory. The diagnosis of such diseases often presents great difficulties and often requires a multi-disciplinary approach including clinical examination, electromyographic evaluation and muscle biopsy.

Generally neuromuscular disorders are divided in myopathies and neuropathies.

Myopathies. Diseases in which the skeletal muscle is primarily involved. Myopathies may be caused by a variety of factors, including inherited genetic defects (e.g., the muscular dystrophies), endocrine, inflammatory (e.g., polymyositis), or metabolic abnormalities. Almost all of the various myopathies lead to a weakening and atrophy of the skeletal muscles, especially the proximal muscles, such as those in the thigh and shoulder. Muscles further from the centre of the body, the distal muscles, such as those in our hands and feet, are generally less affected by the debilitating consequences of myopathy. Some myopathies, like the muscular dystrophies, develop at a very early age, whereas others develop later in life. Some of them progressively worsen over time and do not respond well to treatment, while others seem to be treatable and often remain stable over long periods of time. Many times a myopathy is simply *labelled non-specific muscle myopathy* because present day knowledge does not allow accurate categorisation. Treatment for myopathy is generally limited. Unfortunately, there is no cure available as yet for muscular dystrophy. Current available treatment focuses on the symptoms. Drugs and physical therapy are both used to alleviate muscular discomfort. Researchers are seeking gene therapy treatments for some of the disorders. Five well known types of muscular dystrophy are listed and briefly explained below:

- (i) Duchenne muscular dystrophy. An inherited disorder, characterised by rapidly progressive muscle weakness of the legs and pelvis initially, and of the whole body at a later stage. This weakness causes skeletal deformities of the spine and other areas and is likely to cause even breathing difficulties. Symptoms usually appear in males before the age of 6 although they may appear at early infancy. Usually by the age of 10, walking is impossible without the proper aids and a few years later most patients are confined to a wheelchair.
- (ii) Becker's myopathy. Same as Duchenne but with a more benign phenotype.
- (iii) Fascioscapulohumeral muscular dystrophy. Progressive muscle weakness and loss of muscle tissue affecting the face, shoulder and upper body. Symptoms appear usually in the second decade although it may appear at a later stage. Progression of the disease is mild and slow.
- (iv) Limb girdle. An inherited group of at least 10 different muscular dystrophies, affecting the muscles of the shoulder, and pelvic girdles. It usually starts with difficulties standing up from a sitting position, or climbing stairs at childhood. Prognosis is variable.
- (v) Myotonic muscular dystrophy. This is the most common form of myopathy affecting adults. Common features of this disease are a slowly progressive weakness and wasting of the masseter but a more pronounced weakness of distal muscles rather than proximal muscles. A delayed muscle relaxation following stimulation or voluntary contraction is also a symptom of this disease, Johnson (1980).

EMG changes in Myopathies. As in peripheral neuropathies, EMG recordings from diseased muscle, may present increased or decreased MUAP amplitude and/or duration. An increase in amplitude is observed with hypertrophy and /or regeneration of muscle fibres, whereas a decrease in amplitude is observed with atrophy and /or with a reduction in the number of muscle fibres. The muscle fibre hypertrophy causing the amplitude to increase may also cause the duration of the MUAP to increase. With muscle fibre enlargement the duration of the MUAP is once again seen to increase. On the other hand a loss of muscle fibres and /or muscle fibre atrophy causes the MUAP duration to decrease. Muscle fibre enlargement, together with regeneration and splitting of muscle fibres causes also an

increase in the number of phases, a phenomenon observed in neuropathy subjects as well. An increase in the number of phases may be seen in myopathy (polyphasia) but also due to the drop out of individual muscle fibres from the motor unit.

Neuropathies. These are the diseases causing primarily damage to the nerves. Although the causes are diverse, they produce common symptoms including weakness, numbness, paresthesia (abnormal sensations such as burning, tickling, pricking or tingling) and pain in the arms or legs. They tend to be most severe in distal portions of extremities, especially in lower legs and feet. Although a large number of cases are of unknown cause, EMG can still help not only for making a diagnosis, but also to make an accurate prognosis and determination of the appropriate treatment, Johnson (1980).

EMG changes in peripheral Neuropathies. In mild peripheral neuropathies, only minor if any abnormalities may be seen from a needle EMG examination, even less abnormalities may be detected from SEMG recordings, Johnson (1980). Changes that may occur are amplitude increase or decrease, depending on whether there is re-innervation of more muscle fibres resulting in larger motor units or reduced number of innervated muscle fibres per muscle unit as a result of the disease process. The duration of the Motor Unit Action Potential, may also present the same contradicting results, depending on whether there is a re-innervation of more muscle fibres and a dispersion of the endplate zone, which may cause the duration to increase. A fractionation of the re-innervated muscle fibres, however which may also occur, will cause the duration of a MUAP to decrease. One change, which may be detected, though, caused by the increased width of the endplate zone and the muscle fibre splitting is an increase in the number of phases. It is hence obvious that the MU shape is quite unstable in these kind of diseases caused mainly by the re-innervation of muscle fibres. One characteristic of the MUAP though which should be aimed for, is an observation of an increase or not in the number of phases recorded.

Chapter 3

Signal processing of SEMG

Chapter 3

SIGNAL PROCESSING OF SEMG

3.1 Introduction

Early developments in electromyography

Piper in Germany carried out the first extensive study on electromyography in 1912. He was able to record the human voluntary muscle activity utilizing the Einthoven's string galvanometer. Shortly afterwards in 1928, Proebster described spontaneous irregular action potentials in the denervated muscle of a boy with a traumatic plexus birth lesion and in another patient with long-standing poliomyelitis. This was considered as a milestone in clinical electromyography and Proebster had earned the credit for establishing this field. In 1929, Andrian and Bronk, devised the concentric needle electrode and were able to study the MUAP. They even went one step further and amplified the recorded signal and used the result to drive a loudspeaker a technique still used today. In this way they were able to better interpret the EMG signal. They proved that in completely relaxed normal muscle, there was no spontaneous electrical activity. Also they noted the firing rates and values of action potentials during voluntary contraction. The use of differential amplification employed by Matthews in 1934, allowed the recording of small amplitude motor units.

A few years later, in 1940, the cathode ray oscilloscope introduced in 1924 by Gasser and Erlangen replaced totally the galvanometer and hence helped the Neurophysiologist to study the undistorted shape of muscle activity. In the years that followed, the development of sensitive electronic equipment and the invention of new techniques in studying the muscle, contributed significantly to the assessment of neuromuscular disorders.

Advances in quantitative EMG

Buchthal made the first considerable advance in 1955, in studying MUAP parameters. However four years earlier, Richardson, had shown that the power spectrum of the EMG activity is shifted towards the higher frequency area in patients suffering with myopathy, compared with normal subjects.

Willison (1964), performed extensive research to differentiate neuropathies and myopathies by analysing turns and amplitude of motor units during a constant force level. A few years later the number of zero crossings were used as a measure of quantitative EMG. Larson (1975), used a simple form of spectrum analyser to differentiate myopathies from neuropathies. More and more researchers have since then applied quantitative EMG analysis with one or more parameters, in an effort to discriminate between myopathies, neuropathies and normal subjects.

Many researches divide EMG or SEMG parameters in two main groups, depending on whether they were derived from a single signal or from an interaction between two or more signals, Duchene et al (1993). If the analysis is performed on a single signal, it may be divided, into temporal or time domain analysis and spectral or frequency domain analysis. If muscle fibre conduction velocity (MFCV) is required, then the analysis should be performed by examining the interaction between two or more signals.

With the developments in signal processing and hardware equipment more and more groups complement each other in an effort to discriminate between normal and abnormal subjects.

Unfortunately the improvements in quantitative EMG recorded with surface electrodes, have not followed the corresponding achievements of needle EMG recording.

The first known study using surface electrodes to perform a diagnostic study was attempted by Brazier in 1946. Although his group did detect fasciculation in persons with symptoms of cervical radiculopathy, being the objective of the study, no conclusive results were drawn since no controls were used and no comparison with needle electrodes was made. From 1946 no systematic studies were performed until 1964, when Haris, Rosov, Cooper and Lysaught made an attempt to use surface electrodes in electromyography once again, to draw diagnostic results. Although two years later in 1966, Grossman and Weiner warned researchers that surface electromyography could give erroneous results, the attempts still went on. Today, nearly six decades since Brazier's attempt, and with all the advances made in signal

processing and hardware equipment, results obtained still lag significantly those extracted from needle electrodes. Furthermore many discrepancies exist between findings of various research groups involved in SEMG for the reasons stated in Chapter 1.

3.2 Time domain analysis

Temporal or time domain analysis is a method to describe the signal by means of its value on the time axis. The most common parameters of the time domain analysis are:

- Number of turns (t/s): These are defined as the number of slope reversals separated from the previous and the following turn by a certain amplitude threshold.
- Number of zero crossings per second (zc/s): Defined as the number of sign reversals exceeding a certain threshold.

3.3 Frequency domain analysis

Another way to represent the signal is that of the spectral or frequency domain. The last twenty years have witnessed an expansion of new power spectrum estimation techniques, which all rely on the same principle. Spectral analysis may simply be described as a decomposition of the signal into sinusoidal components of different frequencies. The amplitude of the components as a function of the frequency constitutes the spectrum of the signal. The Fourier Transform (FT) performs transforming the signal from the time domain into the frequency domain.

$$S(\omega) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} s(t)e^{-j\omega t} dt = F\{s(t)\} \quad (3.1)$$

where $\omega=2\pi f$ is the angular frequency, and $F\{*\}$ is the Fourier operator.

The inverse Fourier Transform (IFT) is the operator that transforms the signal back to its original time domain from the frequency domain.

$$s(t) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} S(\omega)e^{j\omega t} d\omega = F^{-1}\{S(\omega)\} \quad (3.2)$$

Since the frequency domain representation $S(\omega)$ is complex, then

$$S(\omega) = |S(\omega)|e^{j\theta(\omega)} \quad (3.3)$$

Where $|S(\omega)|$, is the amplitude spectrum representing the absolute value of the complex function, and $\theta(\omega)$, is the phase spectrum representing the phase of the complex function. The square of the absolute value, $|S(\omega)|^2$, is called the power spectrum (PS). The power spectrum of a signal describes the distribution of the signal's power on the frequency axis.

3.4 Bi-frequency domain analysis

Although analysis of physiological signals using PS techniques has been a well-accepted method for the last few decades, certain parameters may not be reliably estimated with this method. Power spectrum analysis would have been sufficient if the signal had a Gaussian distribution of a known mean. However most practical cases are not represented by a Gaussian distribution process.

This is the reasoning why bispectrum (bi-frequency) analysis is useful, a particular form of Higher Order Statistics (HOS). Bispectrum analysis also offers many advantages versus PS analysis.

It may: (i) detect and characterise existing non linearities of the signal, (ii) estimate the phase, and (iii) extract information due to deviations from normality (Nikias 1987).

For a zero-mean, stationary process $\{s(t)\}$, the third-order cumulant (TOC) is defined as the expected value of the triple product

$$R(m, n) = E\{s(t)s(t + m)s(t + n)\}, \quad (3.4)$$

and the bispectrum is defined as the Fourier transform of the TOC sequence (Hinich 1982):

$$B(\omega_1, \omega_2) = \sum_{m=-\infty}^{m=\infty} \sum_{n=-\infty}^{n=\infty} R(m, n) e^{-j(\omega_1 m + \omega_2 n)}. \quad (3.5)$$

In addition, the sum of magnitudes of the estimated bispectrum is computed by

$$D = \sum_{(\omega_1, \omega_2)} |B(\omega_1, \omega_2)|. \quad (3.6)$$

To quantify the non-Gaussianity of a random process, the normalised bispectrum, or bicoherence is estimated as follows

$$B_n(\omega_1, \omega_2) = \frac{B(\omega_1, \omega_2)}{\sqrt{P(\omega_1)P(\omega_2)P(\omega_1 + \omega_2)}}, \quad (3.7)$$

where $P(\cdot)$ is the power spectrum. The test of Gaussianity is based on the mean bicoherence power defined as follows

$$S_g = \sum |B_n(\omega_1, \omega_2)|, \quad (3.8)$$

with the summation performed over the non-redundant region.

A typical bispectrum plot is shown in Figure 3.1 below indicating that the region around the 50 Hz area occupies most of the energy of the signal.

3.5 Previous studies on SEMG analysis

As mentioned earlier in this Chapter, since Proebster managed to describe irregular action potentials in two separate cases in 1928, and since the first known effort to perform a diagnostic EMG study using surface electrodes in 1946 by Brazier, many research groups have attempted to draw conclusive results using needle and even surface electrodes. Many different muscles were examined and various parameters were calculated.

Tables 3.1-3.4 present in chronological order research groups examining; EMG on Biceps Brachii (BB), muscles on normal subjects (Table 3.1), on abnormal subjects (Table 3.2), on other muscles other than the BB on normal subjects (Tables 3.3), and classification methods between normal and abnormal subjects (Table 3.4). These tabulate the research groups, the year of paper publication, the number of subjects with their age span, parameters analysed, force exhibited during the experiment, recording and resting time and some conclusive results.

Following the tables, a brief description of the findings of each research group are given.

Table 3.1 A listing of SEMG studies performed on the biceps brachii muscle on normal subjects in chronological order.

RESEARCH GROUP	YEAR	PARAMETERS EXTRACTED	No. OF SUBJECTS (AGE)	COMMENTS [recording time/resting time]
Hagberg et al	1982	Pfmean	4 (21-24)	Pfmean independent of FL > 25% MVC [5-80% MVC, 3-5 sec/1 minute]
Gander et al	1985	Pfmed, Pfx, PS	6 (20-40)	PS → HFB with ↑ of FL; Pfmed, & Pfx ↑ with FL (< 35 Nm); Pfmed & Pfx ↓ at high FL (> 35 Nm) [8 sec/2-several minutes]
Inbar et al	1986	Pfmed, zc	NP	Pfmed independent of FL; zc independent of FL; zc correlated with Pfmed [30,50,70, 90% MVC 6 sec/NP]
Moritani et al	1987	Pfmean	12 (26.3±2.5)	Pfmean ↑ with FL up to 80% of MVC [5 sec/2 minutes]
Shankar et al	1989	Pfmed, Ptotal	10 (25-28)	Pfmed affected by torque applied [4.9 Nm monitored at 8 positions 10 seconds/5-10 minutes]
Daanen et al	1990	Pfmean	5 (19-30)	Pfmean ↔ during 5 day recording for same subjects; Interindividual differences in Pfmean large [40% MVC, 5 seconds/5 minutes]
Gerdle et al	1990	Pfmean	9 (30-40)	Pfmean ↑ up to 60% MVC; Pfmean independent of interelectrode distance [20-100% MVC, 1-2 seconds/several minutes]
Bilodeau et al	1992	Pfmed, Pfmean	29 (22-37)	Pfmed and Pfmean do not follow the same pattern between genders. Increase more with FL for men. SE for Pfmed=5.7% for men and 3.6% for women; SE for Pfmean=6.5% for men and 3.2 for women [10-80% MVC, 5 seconds/2minutes]

RESEARCH GROUP	YEAR	PARAMETERS EXTRACTED	No. OF SUBJECTS (AGE)	COMMENTS [recording time/resting time]
Linsen et al	1993	P ₁₀ , P ₉₀ , P _{med}	26 (32 ±9.7)	PS parameters vary interindividually; Repeatability showed no significant differences; No effect of age, for parameters examined; Gender is only related to maximal force (higher in males) [80% MVC, 30 contractions per minute]
Li et al	1996	P _{total} , P _{fmean}	12 (22-25)	P _{fmean} and PS are affected by electrode location; P _{fmean} ↓ with distance from end plate P _{total} ↑ with FL; [20-60% MVC, brief contractions/NP]
Krivickas et al	1998	P _{fmed}	31 (22-37)	P _{fmed} greater in male than female; Slope not affected by gender [50% MVC, 45 seconds/15 minutes]
Rainoldi et al	1999	P _{fmean}	10 (23-43)	P _{fmean} ↓ with FL 30 to 70% MVC; [30 seconds/5 minutes] Repeatability: (i) SE=2-3% for P _{fmed} , (ii) statistically significant differences observed in 1/4-2/3 of the experimental sessions
Farina et al	2002	P _{fmean} , P _{fmed}	10 (22-35)	No relationship may be drawn between spectral parameters and force level
FL (force level)		Nm (Newton metres)	P _{fmed} (median frequency)	P _{total} (Total power)
HFB (higher frequency band)		P ₁₀ (Ten percent power range)	P _{fx} (frequency at maximum power)	SE (Standard error)
MVC (maximum voluntary contraction)		P ₉₀ (Ninety percent power range)	P _{med} (Fifty percent power range)	t/s (turns per second)
NP (Not provided)		P _{fmean} (mean power frequency)	PS (Power Spectrum)	zc (zero crossings) → (shifts), ↑ (increase), ↓ (decrease), ⇕, ↔ (constant)

Table 3.2 A listing of EMG studies performed on the biceps brachii muscle of subjects suffering from neuropathy or myopathy in chronological order.

RESEARCH GROUP	YEAR	PARAMETERS EXTRACTED	NO OF SUBJECTS (AGE)	COMMENTS [recording time/resting time]
Chaffin	1968	PS	12 NOR 6 MYO 9 NEURO	PS → LFB for NOR PS → HFB for MYO or NEURO [5 & 30% MVC, 15 seconds/NP]
Muro	1982	Pfmean, Pfx	5 NOR (24-41) 5 MYO (22-38) 5 NEURO (20-33)	Pfmean results HG, MG → HFB, with ↑FL NG → LFB, with ↑FL Pfx results No significant change observed [0.25-3 kg, 10 seconds/30 minutes]
Fuglsang et al*	1984	zc	10 NOR (from another study) 17 MYO (21-69) 14 NEURO (24-76)	zc ↑ up to mid FL for NOR zc ↑ up to mid FL for 1/7 MYO zc ↑ considerably from weak to moderate FL for 6/17 MYO zc ↑ with FL except 30% MVC where 70% of NEURO showed a ↓ in ZC [0-MVC, 10 seconds/NP, <i>concentric needle electrode</i>]
Pattichis et al*	1994	t/s, Pfx, Ptotal, sg, sl	1 NOR 1 MYO 1 MND	t/s ↑ with FL for NOR & MND up to 70% MVC t/s ↑ with FL for MYO Pfx independent of FL for all three groups Ptotal ↑ with FL for all three groups sg ↓ with FL up to 70% MVC for all three groups sl ↑ with FL for all three groups [10,30,50,70,100%MVC, <i>concentric needle electrode</i>]

RESEARCH GROUP	YEAR	PARAMETERS EXTRACTED	NO OF SUBJECTS (AGE)	COMMENTS [recording time/resting time]
Feng et al	1998	EMG activity & P _{fmean}	8 NOR (23-31) 7 Spastic quadriplegia (21-32)	EMG activity Spastic subjects > NOR P _{fmean} Spastic subjects > NOR [Two special movement tasks, while subject was sitting

* Needle examination

FL (force level)
HFB (higher frequency band)
HG (healthy group)
LSB (lower frequency band)
MG (Myopathy group)
MVC (maximum voluntary contraction)
MYO (myopathy subject)
NEURO (neuropathy subject)
NOR (Normal subject)

P_{fmean} (mean power frequency)
P_{fmed} (median frequency)
P_{fx} (frequency at maximum power)

PS (Power Spectrum shape)
P_{total} (Total power)
RP (relative power)
sg (Gaussianity test)
sl (Linearity test)
t/s (turns per second)
zc (zero crossings)

NG (Neuropathy group)
EMG (electromyography)
→ (shifts), ↑ (increase), ↓ (decrease)

Table 3.3 A listing of studies performed on normal subjects, for muscles other than the biceps brachii in chronological order

RESEARCH GROUP	YEAR	PARAMETERS EXTRACTED	MUSCLES EXAMINED	No of subjects (age range)	COMMENTS
Westbury et al	1987	Pfmean	Masseter	10 (23.4, SD=4.1)	Pfmean ↓ with FL (for 7 out of 10 subjects) [10, 20, 40, 60, 80% MVC, brief and progressively stronger isometric contractions]
Gerdle et al	1988a	Pfmean	Shoulder muscles		Pfmean ↓ FL up to 50% MVC
Roy et al	1989	Pfmed	TA, Deltoid muscle & lower back muscles	1 6 (24±2.7) 21-40 (21-40)	Pfmed ↑ with FL 20 to 100% MVC Repeatability measurements showed that variability was greater between experiments than within experiments
Merletti et al	1992	Pfmean, Pfmed	TA	15 (65-84) 20 (18-43)	Pfmean, Pfmed↑ up to 80% MVC, independent of age Significant differences at 20% for Pfmean between the two groups No significant differences at 80% MVC for Pfmean between the two groups No significant differences at 20 or 80 % MVC for Pfmed between the two groups [20 & 80% MVC, 20 seconds/4 minutes]
Preece et al	1994	Pfmed, zc, t/s	TA, RF	13 (20-55)	For TA muscle SEMG and needle recordings quite comparable For RF muscle not, due to muscle depth [64 seconds at MVC]

RESEARCH GROUP	YEAR	PARAMETERS EXTRACTED	MUSCLES EXAMINED	No of subjects (age range)	COMMENTS
Bilodeau et al	1995	Pfmed, Pfmean, sg, P _{25%} , P _{75%} , P _{50%} , SD	TB, AN	29 (21-44)	For thick muscle skinfold layers there is a loss of power in the HFB. So Pfmean and Pfmed behave differently. In such a case frequency spectral parameters are not sufficient to fully characterise the PS [0-100% MVC, 5 seconds/2 minutes]
Cifrek et al	2000	Pfmed	RF, VL, VM	9 (22-26)	Pfmed ↓ fatigue Movement from 110° (flexion) to 180° (extension) at 50% MVC. Free selection of cycle frequency
TA (Tibialis Anterior) RF (Rectus Femoris) AN (Anconeus) VL (Vastus lateralis) VM (Vastus Medialis) FL (force level)		MVC (maximum voluntary contraction) N (number of subjects) P _{25%} (First quartile) P _{75%} (third quartile) Pfmean (mean power frequency)		Pfmed (median frequency) SEMG (Surface Electromyography) P _{med} (Fifty percent power range) PS (Power Spectrum shape) Ptotal (Total power) RP (relative power)	SE (Standard error) sg (Gaussianity test) t/s (turns per second) zc (zero crossings) (increase), ↓ (decrease)

Table 3.4 A listing of studies attending classification between normal subjects and subjects suffering from neuropathy or myopathy in chronological order.

RESEARCH GROUP	YEAR	METHOD	NO OF SUBJECTS	COMMENTS
Coatrieux et al*	1983	Pattern recognition	7 normals 9 myopathy	Combination of 8 parameters analysed, formed 12 classes used for classification using PCA. Satisfactory discrimination between groups.
Kumaravel et al*	1994	Feature extraction and Classification	42 patients	5 parameters from the time domain were applied to a Neural Network for classification. Results classified patients suffering or not suffering with polymyositis. These coincided with clinical findings.
Abel et al*	1995	IBPN, RBN, LVQ, SOFM	12 normals 18 myopathy 15 neuropathy	The first three methods being supervised Gave diagnostic yields of the order of 60-80%, whereas the SOFM being unsupervised gave slightly lower results
Christodoulou et al*	1999	SOFM, LVQ	12 normals 13 myopathy 15 motor neuron disease	SOFM with LVQ gave 97.6% CC and with SOFM alone 94.8% CC
Abou-Chadi et al	2000	Multilayer BPN, SOFM Probabilistic NN	14 normals 14 patients	All three ANN methods gave 90% CC

Note: * Needle recording

PCA (Principal Component Analysis)
 IBPN (Improved Back Propagation Network)
 RBN (Radial Basic Network)
 LVQ (Learning Vector Quantification Network)
 SOFM (Self Organising Feature Maps)
 BPN (Back Propagation Network)
 ANN (Neural Network)
 CC (Correct Classification)

Chaffin –1968

The objective of this study was to develop a diagnostic procedure enabling a verified discrimination between a normal skeletal muscle contraction, a contraction that involves an overly fatigued muscle, and a contraction, which involves a muscle or nerve that is pathological. Recordings were performed at 5 and 30% of Maximum Voluntary Contraction (MVC) for 15 seconds. Various muscles were examined, (Biceps brachii, finger flexors, triceps brachii, rectus medialis, rectus femoris).

Twelve healthy subjects participated in the biceps brachii recording. Furthermore six myopathy patients participated and 9 neuropathy patients. It was concluded that with excessive force demand on a muscle a shift of the frequency spectrum towards the lower frequency bands (i.e. towards the 10 to 20 Hz is evident) for normal subjects, and also that many common neuropathies and myopathies results in an EMG spectrum shift towards the higher frequency band. The finding of the shift towards the lower frequency region (which may be interpreted as a decrease in the median frequency) is in opposition with other findings. Bilodeau et al (1995), reports a general shift of the PS towards the high frequency region with increase of force.

Hagberg et al (1982)

The surface myoelectric signal was recorded from the BB muscle and two other muscles of the upper extremity. The influence of the strength of contraction on the recorded signal was studied for three elbow flexors.

Results showed:

- (i) for all four subjects participating, the MPF increased linearly and significantly with contraction level at low tensions,
- (ii) the relationship between MPF and contraction level, was found to be independent of contraction at levels between 20-50% of MVC. The authors concluded that the correlation of MPF versus force was poor, due to the large variance of MPF found in the study and hence the use of MPF as an indicator of contraction level was not suggested.

Muro et al (1982)

Possible differences among normal and patient subjects were investigated in this study, with the aid of SEMG by examining integrated EMG (IEMG), EMG power spectrum density, mean power frequency (MPF) and peak power frequency (PPK), with respect to force level. Five healthy male subjects (HL), five patients with myogenic disorders (MG) (progressive muscular dystrophy) and five patients with neurogenic disorders (NG) (Kugelberg-Welander) participated. Subjects were tested in two ways: (i) during a ten second isometric contraction at a 90 degree arm flexion with or without external weights and (ii) during isotonic contraction with arm flexion moving from zero to 90 degrees, 10 times (once every 2 seconds) with or without external weights. In both cases a bipolar lead system with surface electrodes was attached over the belly of the biceps brachii muscle. A rest period of 30 minutes between trails and a two-hour rest period between isometric and isotonic contractions were applied.

Results for the IEMG showed that (i) at high loads HL had significantly lower values than MG or NG and NG showed significantly higher IEMG values than MG (ii) at low loads NG showed significantly lower values than MG. Results for MPF showed that (i) values increased for HG and MG, (ii) values decrease for NG (iii) ANOVA applied on MPF results showed that during isometric contractions at different loads, the effect of load on MPF was not statistically significant (iv) values of MG are higher than those of HL and (v) no differences in MPF between the groups were found during isotonic contractions. Results on peak power frequency did not show any statistically significant difference with respect to the type of contraction, or level, between the groups.

Coatrieux et al (1983)

Weak contractions performed on 16 volunteers (7 normals and 9 myopathy subjects), with needle electrodes, enabled the clear recording of separate potentials. From the recorded signals eight parameters were analysed. Principal Component Analysis was used for signal description. Various classes combining parameters analysed, were formed and used for a satisfactory discrimination between normal and Duchenne's myopathy subjects.

Fuglsang et al (1984)

The integrated electrical activity and the number of zero crossings per unit time during a gradual increase in force in patients suffering from a neuromuscular disease, was investigated in this study. In subjects with no apparent disease the number of zero crossings were found to increase with increasing force level up to only mid force levels. From there on the number of zero crossings remained fairly stable. This was also observed with a patient suffering from myopathy. Particularly increased zero crossings were observed in one third of the 17 patients examined with myopathy at weak to moderate force levels. Neuropathy patients showed an increasing number of zero crossings with force level, except at a force level of 30% of MVC where 70% of the patients examined showed a decrease in zero crossings. The main conclusion of this study was however that the number of zero crossings increase only up to mid force levels, which is in opposition with the findings of this present study, where the number of zero crossings were found to increase considerably from low to high force levels.

Gander et al (1985)

Changes in the surface myoelectric power spectral density with muscle force was examined in this study. Six healthy male subjects participated. Four sessions were performed on each subject with one session on a given day and from 1 day to 4 months between sessions. Torques of 15 Nm to 50 Nm were applied sequentially with several minutes rest between each session. Two spectral parameters were examined, the median frequency (P_{fmed}) and the frequency at maximum power (P_{fx}). Both parameters were significantly increased with torque, although P_{fmed} presented less variability. However results obtained with applied torques above 35 Nm were excluded from result analysis since (i) not all subjects could produce high torque levels (ii) P_{fmed} and P_{fx} were found to decrease, which was contributed to muscle fatigue although the experimental protocol took every effort to avoid fatigue (resting time several minutes).

Inbar et al (1986)

The purpose of this study was to investigate whether ZCR could be used to estimate surface EMG spectral parameters and in particular mean and median frequencies. The biceps brachii muscle was one of the muscles used for the study. Results showed that no consistent

changes in median frequency or ZCR were observed with varying tensions. The authors concluded that a good correlation existed between ZCR and the median frequency and thus the ZCR could be used as a simple method to measure EMG spectral parameters.

Moritani et al (1987)

Their results taken from 12 male healthy subjects have shown that significant increases occur in (i) the surface EMG amplitude and (ii) the mean power frequency with increasing force from 0 to 80% of MVC. The increase in EMG followed a linear response, contradicting the results of others reporting a curvilinear response. Differences also exist between the findings of their study and other studies, regarding MPF behaviour with increasing force. These differences were contributed by the authors to (i) electrodes used, innervation ratios and fibre types as far as the differences in amplitude response and (ii) the different muscles examined, electrode size and inter-electrode distance as far as the differences in MPF are concerned.

Westbury et al (1987)

One of the objectives of this group was to investigate the influence of force increment from 10 to 80% of MVC on MPF. The muscle examined was the masseter and ten female adult subjects participated. Results showed a continuous decrease of MPF with force increment. Although a significant and continuous decrease of MPF with increasing force was reported from this present study as well, one should remember the statement by Moritani et al, (1987), concerning differences due to different muscles.

Gerdle et al (1988a)

The mean power frequency of the EMG of four shoulder muscles was found to be fairly constant up to a force level of the order 50% of MVC. However a significant decrease was recorded in the values of the mean power frequency after 50% of MVC.

Hagberg et al (1988)

The results of this study were in agreement with that of Gerdle et al (1988a), where a small but significant decrease in the values of mean power frequency was noted for force levels over 50% of MVC. Muscles examined here were the masticatory muscles

Roy et al (1989)

The authors of this paper explained in detail the significance of the median frequency and its advantages versus other means of characterizing an EMG signal. They have stated that despite the ease to quantify the amplitude of an EMG signal this parameter has decelerated the use of EMG signals as a quantitative clinical measure due to the many conflicting results reported. Results concerning the amplitude greatly depend on the force, velocity and duration of the contraction and the type of the electrode used. Spectral parameters are on the other hand according to authors more reliable for signal characterization. Particularly the median frequency provides a suitable characterization of the spectral changes with force transition, when noise is superimposed on the EMG signal. The repeatability of the median frequency was hence studied in this paper in two parts:

- Repeatability of the median frequency for long duration contractions. Six subjects performed two sustained isometric contractions of the deltoid muscle at 50% MVC. These contractions were performed on the same day with sufficient rest periods in between. Results showed an excellent repeatability
- Repeatability on the same day and different days for erector spine muscles of the lower back were also examined. Eight male subjects participated at an isometric back extension at 80% MVC for 30 seconds, with 15 minutes rest interval. Reliability of the initial frequency for adjacent days was found 0.83 and for the same day 0.98.

It should hence be obvious that median frequency analysis may provide useful information about the characterization of the EMG signal despite the fact that that the authors recorded that the median frequency was found also to be affected by physiological factors such as blood flow and temperature. In particular a linear relationship with temperature was verified.

Shankar et al (1989)

Possible effects of applied torque, velocity of contraction and muscle length on the median frequency of a recorded SEMG were studied. The experimental procedure consisted of two parts (i) the spectral analysis of signals obtained during non-fatiguing static contractions at different joint angles and (ii) the spectral analysis of signal obtained during non-fatiguing

isotonic contractions. For the first part of the study, two different loads were used; one at 8 joint positions and the other at 3. An oscilloscope dc line was used to help subjects hold constant the loads for 10 seconds with 5 to 10 minutes rest in between. In the second part the applied torque and angular velocity were used to study the effect on median and spectral power. Four loads associated with 4 angular velocities were used. The choice of torques was 1.23, 2.45, 3.68, and 7.35 Nm and those of the angular velocities were 40, 80, 120 and 160 deg/sec. A rest interval of 3 to 5 minutes was applied between tests. Results showed that (i) the median frequency varies with applied torque and with muscle length but not with the velocity of contraction and (ii) the power spectrum is influenced by the applied torque, velocity and muscle length.

Daanen et al (1990)

This investigation aimed in examining the reproducibility of mean power frequency (MPF), maintaining force level, muscle fatigue, muscle and skin temperature, muscle length, distribution of muscle fibre type, skin and tissue impedance and electrode properties and localization, controlled as much as possible. The study examined the reproducibility of the MPF of SEMG of the biceps brachii muscle of five normal subjects on five successive days. Subjects performed an isometric contraction equal to 40% of their maximum voluntary contraction (MVC) for five seconds. A resting time of five minutes was allowed. It was stated that MPF returns close to its starting value in 1-2 minutes at moderate force levels, i.e. 15 and 30% MVC and in exercise at high strength levels 60% MVC until exhaustion. Results showed that differences in MPF between subjects were large, which should be expected due to the interindividual differences existing in the properties of Motor Units (MU), muscle fibre type, skin and tissue impedance, and localisation of the electrodes (De Luca from Daamen references). However no significant differences in MPF between the five days for each subject were noted. The authors hence concluded that the MPF of the SEMG could be determined reliable for EMG recordings at intervals of several days.

Gerdle et al (1990)

The aims of this study were:

To investigate the influence of force and interelectrode on mean power frequency

Nine healthy women participated in the study which was broken down in three parts: Firstly a gradual increase up to 100% of MVC then a step increase from 20 up to 100% of MVC in steps of 20% with rest in between, and finally an endurance test at 30% of MVC.

The biceps brachii muscle was examined and the interelectrode distance used were 10, 20 and 30 mm. Results showed that:

- The mean power frequency increased up to 60% of MVC. Above 60% MVC no change in mean power frequency occurred.
- The interelectrode distance did not influence the mean power frequency (Which is in opposition to the finding of Deluca et al (1989)).
- For the same contraction level (step or ramp), the mean power frequency was nearly the same.
- The mean power frequency decreased linearly during the endurance test.

Bilodeau et al (1992)

The objective of this study was to examine differences in mean and median frequencies between the two genders, during increasing force level. Twenty-nine normal subjects participated. Recordings were obtained from the anconeus, triceps and biceps muscles during a ramp contraction of 5 seconds. A ramp (progressive) contraction offers advantages versus the steady (step), contraction as stated by the authors. This however is contradicting to the belief of others, Gerdle et al (1990). Significant differences were found between the two genders for the BB and TB muscles for the P_{fmed} parameter, with women presenting lower values than men. The calculated standard error of the mean values between the two genders may be summarised as follows:

TB muscle: P_{fmean}: 4.7-6.5 men, 2.7-5.8 women, P_{fmed}: 4.8-6.9 men, 2.2-2.9 women

BB muscle: P_{fmean}: 4.2-7.1 men, 2.2-5.5 women, P_{fmed}: 5.7-8.4 men, 2.6-4.9 women

AN muscle: P_{fmean}: 6.1-10.7 men, 4.6-6.7 women, P_{fmed}: 7.1-10.4 men, 5.6-6.5 women

Differences were contributed to fibre type content (women have a lower content of type II fibres) and fibre size (women have smaller type II fibres than men).

Merletti et al (1992)

The influence of isometric voluntary contraction at 20 and 80% of MVC, on conduction velocity, mean and median power frequencies, during a 20 second duration (4 minutes rest in between) recording from the tibialis anterior (TA) muscle, using a four-bar surface electrode was investigated.

Fifteen elderly normal subjects aged from 65 to 84 years old participated and results taken were compared with those of another study on healthy adults aged from 18 to 43 years old. The main related findings of this study were that the values of all parameters mentioned above, increase when voluntary contraction is increased from 20 to 80% MVC. This increase was found to be significantly smaller in elderly subjects. This was contributed to the decrease of a number and size of fast twitch fibres.

Linsen et al (1993)

The objectives of this study were (i) to investigate how reproducible were Power Density Spectrum (PSD) parameters, SEMG amplitude and MFCV within subjects and possible influences of gender and age and (ii) to analyse the relationship between the decrease of MFCV with the shift of the PDS and the SEMG amplitude. Twenty-six healthy volunteers were divided in three age groups (below 30, between 30 and 40 and above 40 years old). Thirty isometric contractions per minute of the biceps brachii muscle at 80% of the MVC were performed. Results showed (i) that the thirteen subjects asked to perform the experiment twice with at least a 1-week interval in between presented non-significant differences between the two sets of results. Furthermore gender and age were found to have no effect on any of the parameters studied (ii) the MFCV was proved to have the highest intraindividual reproducibility in contrast with many SEMG parameters, which did not always follow the pattern of the MFCV. In particular the MFCV and SEMG amplitude relationship was found quite difficult to interpret. The authors stressed also that conclusions based on a small number of observations being common in related studies might lead to erroneous results.

Kumaravel et al (1994)

An automatic diagnosis tool using ANN for neuromuscular diseases, based on the feature extraction and classification of signals collected from myopathy subjects was the objective of this study. Signals were collected from the Tibialis Anterior muscle and five domain parameters were analysed. Results taken from the 22 subjects suffering with polymyositis and the 20 not suffering coincided with clinical findings.

Pattichis et al. (1994)

This study examined the influence of FL on various parameters, a few of which were the same as the parameters looked into in this study. Three subjects were examined, one NOR, a patient suffering with Motor Neuron Disease (MND) and a patient suffering with myopathy (MYO). A good comparison between results obtained in Pattichis study and this study is possible, since the same muscle was used and the FLs are the same. The main difference though is that his group performed needle recordings whereas this study is based on non-invasive recordings. However his main findings were: (i) t/s increase with FL for NOR and MND up to 70% MVC, whereas the number of t/s increase all the way up to MVC, (ii) Pfx is independent with FL for all three subject groups, (iii) Ptotal increases with FL for all three groups (iv) Gaussianity is increased up to 70% MVC for all three groups and (v) signal's linearity increases with FL for all three groups.

Preece et al. (1994)

The objective of this study was to analyse an EMG interference pattern during a 64-second maximum voluntary contraction for turn and zero crossings per second and median frequency, from signal recorded with surface and needle electrodes. Muscles examined were the tibialis anterior and the rectus femoris, from thirteen normal subjects from both sexes aged between 20 and 55 years old. Results were found to be very comparable between the two methods of recording in tibialis anterior but not in rectus femoris, whose results were found to be dependent with the needle electrode depth. Furthermore, the variability between subjects was less with surface electrodes, except for the number of zero crossings per second of the tibialis anterior measurements, which was slightly higher with surface electrodes.

Abel et al (1995)

The performance of ANN in analysing and classifying EMG signals from 12 normal subjects, 18 myopathy, 15 neuropathy patients and 5 patients suffering from both type of disease was examined in this study. A 4 second recording was obtained from the biceps brachii muscle at or near the MVC. Parameters were obtained from the signals using recognized quantification techniques, using turns analysis, small segments analysis and frequency analysis. Both supervised (improved back-propagation network (IPPN), radial basis network (RBN), and learning vector quantification network (LVQ)) and unsupervised (SOFM) were used for classification. Supervised networks gave a diagnostic yield between 60-80% and the unsupervised slightly less. Interference pattern analysis gave higher number of turns in normal subjects than patients, which is in opposition with most previous studies. The authors concluded that interference pattern analysis offers more than ANN analysis, which was not even improved by including subject personal data (age and gender).

Bilodeau et al (1995)

The purpose of this study was to investigate the influence of various parameters extracted from the electromyography spectrum, during a progressive increase in force level from 10 to 90% MVC in steps of 10%. Recordings were made by SEMG on two muscles the triceps brachii (TB) and the anconeus (AN) for a 5 second period. Twenty-nine normal subjects participated in the experiment, divided in two groups for each muscle according to gender. Parameters examined were, MPF, MF, 25th and 75th percentiles (F25 & F75), standard deviation SD (f), skewness (ASYM) and half-power range (HPR). Differences between male and female were more pronounced for the TB, which were contributed to the thicker skinfold layer over female muscles, causing a loss of power in the high frequency region with increment of force. The results for the TB muscle could be summarised as: (i) the MPF, F75, and the HPR parameters remained constant with force increment with male subjects but decreased with female subjects. (ii) the median frequency increased with force for both genders, (iii) the F25 remained constant with force increment with both genders and (iv) the SD (f) and ASYM decreased with force increment with both genders. The AN muscle analysis gave the following results: (i) the MPF, MF, F25, F75 and HPR increase with force increment with both genders, however the increment of the first three mentioned is more pronounced with male subjects, (ii) the ASYM decreased with force for both

genders and (iii) the SD remains constant with force increment for both genders. As a conclusion a thin skinfold layer, causes a general shift of the spectrum towards higher frequencies without any significant change in the shape. In such a case the MPF and MED alone are sufficient to describe the changes in the PS. However the loss of power in the high frequency region as the force increases observed in the TB muscle of female subjects due to a considerable amount of skinfold layer, makes it necessary to describe the PS with more parameters than MPF and MED, which are also influenced in a different manner.

Li et al (1996)

The MPF and the total power at various locations of the BB muscle were obtained from the PS. Twelve healthy male subjects aged between 22 and 25 years of age participated in the study. The electrode array enabled the authors to investigate results at different locations of the BB muscle and found that the MPF of the PS was affected by the electrode location. There was a decrease of MPF with distance from the end plate. The total power was found to increase with increasing contraction and was also influenced with the location of the electrode. Lower values of TP were observed near the end plate and the tendon of the muscle.

Feng et al (1998)

Surface electromyography was recorded from the biceps brachii, the brachioradialis and the triceps brachii muscle. Seven young adults with spastic quadriplegia and eight normal subjects participated voluntarily in this study. Subjects were asked to: (i) move their hands from a proximal target plate to a distal and then back to the proximal target plate along a table plane and (ii) following the sound of a metronome, subjects were asked to perform 5 elbow flexion/extension cycles in the vertical plane. Both tasks were performed with the subjects being seated in an adjustable chair. Two parameters were analysed, the mean power frequency (MPF) from the frequency domain and the mean EMG activity from the time domain. The mean EMG activity, involved low pass filtering the raw SEMG signal, rectifying it and then applying moving average with a 100 ms window.

Results showed that spastic subjects, compared to normal subjects presented higher mean power frequency and significantly higher EMG activities.

Krivickas et al (1998)

Normal values of the initial median frequency (IMF) in four muscles including the BB were investigated in this study. Normal values could have been used clinically to evaluate patients suffering from myopathies, neuropathies or from motor neuro disease. However the lack of established normal values has limited significantly the clinical usefulness of spectral analysis. Thirty-one healthy subjects performed isometric contractions of the BB muscles at 60% MVC. Linear regression analysis was used to compute the initial median frequency and the slope of the median frequency as it decayed over 45 seconds. Results showed that IMF was greater in men than in women although the gender did not affect the slope. Authors established that the range of normal values was however so broad that clinical usefulness could be restricted.

Christodoulou et al (1999)

Classification of MUAPs, recorded from biceps brachii muscle for 5 seconds using needle electrodes at 30% MVC, containing all necessary information concerning neuromuscular disorders, were examined with (i) ANN technique based on unsupervised learning, using a modified version of SOFM algorithm and learning vector quantization (LVQ) and (ii) statistical pattern recognition technique based on Euclidean distance. Twelve normal subjects, 13 myopathy and 15 motor neuron disease patients participated. The success rate for the ANN technique was 97.6% and for the statistical technique 95.3%.

Rainoldi et al (1999)

The objective of this study was to investigate the repeatability of the mean spectral power (MNF), average rectified values (ARV) and muscle fibre conduction velocity (MFCV), as recorded from the BB of 10 normal subjects for four levels of contraction. Results showed that MFCV appeared to be very repeatable, both within and between subjects. This parameter presented a small but significant increase between 10 to 50% MVC but remained fairly constant with further force increase. The MNF parameter on the contrary, showed a small decrease with force increment, whose rate of decrease increased with force. The change in MNF and MFCV was more repeatable between subjects at 10% MVC than at

70%. Finally the authors commented on the resting time used, that five minutes might not be enough to prevent fatigue after a contraction at 50% or 70%.

Cifrek et al (2000)

The group presented a method for measurement and analysis of surface myoelectric signals in order to evaluate muscle fatigue of quadriceps muscle during cyclic dynamic contractions. The range of cyclic movements was between 110 to 180 degrees and the exercise for each of the ten subjects participating stopped at the moments the subject due to exhaustions was not able to perform full extension any more. As an indicator of muscle fatigue a change in the power spectrum median frequency was calculated. For analysis the maximum median frequency (corresponding to maximal extension, 180 degrees), was considered. Results showed that muscle with a higher conduction velocity exhibited greater initial values but also presented a greater reductions of median frequency over the course of the exercise. The authors believe that these findings may help towards understanding the differences in muscle fibre conduction velocity in various muscles. Furthermore these results may be applicable to a wide range of similar activities to monitor efficiencies in kinesiological rehabilitation.

Abou-Chadi et al (2001)

Three versions of ANN were used to facilitate automatic SEMG feature extraction were used in this study. The multilayer back-propagation, the self-organizing feature map and a probabilistic neural network model. Five normal subjects were compared with five myopathy patients at recordings taken from the deltoid muscle at 50% MVC for 5 seconds. The percentage of correct classification using SOFM techniques was as high as 80%.

Farina et al (2002)

The purpose of this study was to examine the possibilities and limitations of the use of global SEMG variables (including mean and median frequencies), as indicators of Motor Unit strategies and the random location of the Motor Unit in the volume conductor. The authors concluded that it was due to the many physical characteristics of the volume conductor that so many contradicting results have been published. They continued stating that SEMG global variables give poor indications about MU recruitment strategies and hence they do not support an establishment between spectral variables and force level.

Chapter 4
Methodology

Chapter 4

METHODOLOGY

4.1 Introduction

A total of 94 normal subjects and 20 patients (11 myopathy and 9 neuropathy) participated voluntarily in this study, which was approved by the Ethical Committee of the Cyprus Institute of Neurology and Genetics, CING. All 114 subjects gave informed consent before participation. The non-pathological-subjects were divided into age groups [mean (SD)], as follows: < 9 years, 12 subjects, (7 M and 5 F) [8.3 (1.4)], 10 – 19 years, 12 subjects, (8 M and 4 F) [17.3 (2.4)], 20 – 29 years, 20 subjects, (10 M and 10 F) [23.75 (2.6)], 30 – 39 years, 15 subjects, (10 M and 5 F) [36.0 (2.60)], 40 – 49 years, 12 subjects, (7 M and 5 F), [44.1 (1.9)], 50 - 59 years, 13 subjects, (7 M and 6 F), [55.0 (2.4)], and 60 – 69 years, 10 subjects, (7 M and 3 F) [65.1 (3.99)]. These subjects were mainly personal friends, relatives, colleagues and students from the University of Cyprus and the Higher Technical Institute, Nicosia. All were from the nearby district of Nicosia. No volunteer turned up as a result of announcements placed at various Hospitals, or Academic Institutes. All recordings of the non-pathological subjects took place either late in the evenings (after 19:00), or during weekends when the lab was available.

Most subjects were given before the recording a handout with a brief description of the study, Appendix 1. They did not have to fulfil any prerequisite regarding height, weight or gender. The systems repeatability performance was investigated with the participation of a female volunteer. Reliability measurements for two sets of recordings were performed on a randomly selected group of normal subjects (7 males and 3 females [43.4 (10.3)], whereas age and gender influence was examined for all 94 normal subjects. Correlation between parameter pairs was also examined for data collected from normal subjects and patients. The patients were divided according to the general type of neuromuscular disorder (myopathy or neuropathy), irrespective of their Medical Research Council (MRC) level, or any specific neuromuscular disorder. Eleven myopathy patients participated (8 M and 3 F), aged between 40 and 70 years [53 (9.5)]. Neuropathy patients (4 M and 5 F) were aged between 18 and 70 years, [52.4 (17.6)].

Patients referred were first examined and diagnosed by their Physician and then were asked to volunteer in the study. These were from all over the island.

Recording took place at a special Electromyography/Electroencephalography/ Evoked Potential (EMG/EEG/EP) lab, with controlled temperature and humidity at the Department of Clinical Neurophysiology at the Cyprus Institute of Neurology and Genetics, Nicosia, Cyprus between April 1998 and November 2002. The recording set-up and procedure, the data acquisition methodology, the feature extraction algorithms and the statistical analysis and classification techniques applied are described next.

4.2 Recording set-up

The design of the recording set-up was a most difficult and time-consuming task. The only suitable available electromyography unit at the CING was the Nicolet Viking IV system. Before purchasing any additional equipment the specifications and costs of any additional relevant items had to be looked into. The electromyography two-channel amplifier unit was according to manufacturers specifications, fully electrically isolated to IEC 601-1 and BSS 5724, Part 1 Type BF. The input impedance of the system Z_{in} was stated to be $> 1000 \text{ M}\Omega$. Through the system the low and high frequency values for recording were set at 20 and 500 Hz respectively. Apart from the existing electromyography system, the following additional items were also used:

- (i) A calibrated force measurement system, with a total weight of 40 kg placed at the foot end of the couch (Fig. 4.1). The weights were lifted via a strap placed at the subjects' wrist and connected to the system through a force transducer, which was connected directly to a calibration circuit. After many trials, with the required force levels (FL), the calibration was set at 2 kg/V.
- (ii) An oscilloscope to enable visual feedback of the FL exhibited by the subjects. The oscilloscope was placed at a height of 1.5 m above ground for better viewing.
- (iii) Recording electrodes: Several recording electrodes were tried and tested, before deciding on the most suitable ones. (The broadly used small

circular electrodes were not used, due to their relatively large size and the requirement of constant interelectrode distance, which was most difficult to achieve with individual electrodes).

- (iv) A suitable acquisition board with a 12-bit Analogue-to-Digital (A/D) converter to digitise the recorded signal. The input of the A/D board was connected to the output of the Nicolet Viking IV preamplifier. The A/D board was plugged into a PC. The characteristics of the board are given in Appendix 3.
- (v) A personal computer (PC-Pentium III/660 MHz) was used to store the recorded digitised signal, since the Nicolet system had limited memory capabilities. On the acquired PC, Labview 6.0 (National Instruments, Inc), a graphical programming environment for instrumentation, was installed and a software program enabled the controlling of the entire recording process, i.e. the number of channels, the start/stop of the recording (5 seconds), and the sampling frequency (1 kHz). Results were written continuously to a text (ASCII) file readable by spreadsheet programs for future analysis.

Figure 4.1 Photograph of the force measurement system

Chronologically the first attempt of the recording set-up was made in 1997. Trial recordings on various friends and colleagues were made with circular recording electrodes and a custom made matrix of electrodes. A flexible multi-channel gum matrix electrode of dimensions 5 x 10 cm accommodated 36 electrodes of 2 mm diameters being gold over nickel-plated cadmium, copper pin type. The acquisition board with the A/D converter was purchased in 1997 after a time consuming market research. The following year in 1998, the PC was introduced and placed next to the electromyography system. On the PC, LABVIEW and MATLAB were installed and actual recordings were initiated in April 1998, with the help of a new electrode block, overcoming the disadvantages of the custom-made electrode matrix. These disadvantages were:

- (i) The electrode matrix was not free from interference.
- (ii) It presented low input impedance.
- (iii) The structure of the multi-channel flexible electrode gum did not permit, accurate measurements especially on children, due to the relatively large size.
- (iv) The 2 mm diameter pins did cause some discomfort, which was undesirable.

With the new electrode block the recording set-up was now complete (a block diagram and a photo are shown in Fig. 4.2 & Fig. 4.3 respectively) and recordings were continued until November 2002. One disadvantage encountered during recordings (of normal subjects and of patients), was the time needed to prepare the set-up (approximate 30 minutes). Since the lab was used by the Neurophysiologists all day for routine examinations, before each recording the set-up had to be prepared (interconnecting the electromyography unit with the PC, the force measurement system with the calibration circuit and the oscilloscope, and the electrode block with the pre-amplifiers and the necessary +/- 12 volt power supply). All the above instruments were kept in the right corner of the lab, since they were not used (besides the electromyography unit) for routine examinations. At the end of each recording the instruments were disconnected and the laboratory was once again ready for routine use. Four patient recordings were performed in 1999, in order to get accustomed to patients recordings. Recordings of normal subjects were completed in October 2002 and of patients in November 2002.

Figure 4.2 Block diagram of the recording set-up.

Figure 4.3 A photograph of the recording set-up.

4.3 Recording procedure

The subject laid on his/her back having his/her dominant arm horizontal and abducted at 90°. The arm was placed side by side with the subject's body (Fig. 4.4).

Figure 4.4 Subject position during recording.

The weight lifting device strap was placed at the wrist of the subject. This arrangement was preferred (rather than having the subject sitting); because of possible unintentional movements, thereby eliminating or reducing to a large extent any unwanted signal interference from such movements, Rainoldi et al (1999).

Recording was carried out using a four-bar EMG active probe with an interelectrode distance of 10 mm and a bar width of 1 mm made by Dispositivi Elettronici Medicali of Italy, Fig. 4.7. A bar configuration has two main advantages versus the well-accepted and well-used circular configuration. Namely, (i) it minimises the electrical noise generated at the skin interface, and (ii) intersects more muscle fibres and, hence, greater amplitude is detected. The buffer amplifier of the electrode probe used in this set-up, had a zero-gain, with a phase margin of 50° and input impedance $Z_{in} > 1000 \text{ M}\Omega$ as per manufactures specifications. Skin preparation of the BB muscle and the dominant arm took place with an alcohol wash. A special conductive paste (Elefix, Model Z-402CE by Nihon Kohden) was placed on the four electrodes. Special care was taken to avoid excessive paste, which could influence results by short-circuiting the electrodes, but on the other hand enough paste was placed to

cover the entire length of the electrode. The subject was asked to bend his/her arm and the actual length of the BB muscle was then measured. The electrode block was then placed and secured with a 50 mm Micropore adhesive tape. Velcro straps of smaller width (10 mm), available in the market, were found to be inappropriate, since the pressure exhibited on the subjects BB muscle caused by strapping the electrode block, was uneven, through the entire 40 mm block length. This was verified by visualizing the two bipolar-recorded signals on the Nicolets monitor, one of which was of considerable smaller amplitude. The electrode block was placed on the BB in such a way, so that the second electrode towards the dominant arm was always at a distance equal to $1/3$ of the BB length (Fig. 4.5). This arrangement ensured that all 4 electrodes were between the motor point and the tendinous insertion and the electrode positioning was as consistent as possible for all subjects, without the necessity of electrically stimulating the BB muscle to find the exact location of the motor point. (The motor point is the point of the muscle where minimal electrical activity is required to cause a twitch of the muscle fibres).

Figure 4.5 Positioning of the electrode block on the BB. The 2nd electrode was placed at a distance equal to $1/3$ of the BB length (x).

The ground electrode was placed at a considerable distance from the recording electrode and in particular on the left flexor muscle closer to the wrist. The four electrodes were then connected in a differential configuration mode, in order to eliminate the noise signal from the power line sources and to reduce as much as

possible movement artefacts. Before the actual recording took place, the subject was asked to experiment at various Force Levels (FLs), to get accustomed with the process. Then the subject was asked to pull at MVC three times with an interval of two minutes in between. A note of the average MVC was made on the oscilloscope with a red or black tape. It was stressed to the subjects that they had to keep the FL each time as constant as possible for the 5 second duration. The subject had two minutes to relax before the actual recording started. The subject was then asked to pull the weights at MVC observing the oscilloscopes DC line, which had to reach the lower part of the tape. As an example if the MVC for a certain subject was 10 volts and the oscilloscope sensitivity was set at 1V/div, at 70% MVC the subject had to take the DC line at 7 volts as indicated at Fig. 4.6.

Figure 4.6 Oscilloscope screen, with the tape indicating the required force level to be reached.

Once this was reached, the signal was recorded for 5 seconds and sampled at 1 kHz. Afterwards the subject was asked to relax for a further 2 minutes. The same procedure was performed again, at the same FL. Then, the tape was placed at positions on the oscilloscope screen corresponding to 70, 50, 30, and 10% of MVC and the process was repeated.

Figure 4.7 Four bar EMG active probe electrode used in this study.

4.4 Data acquisition

From the 5-second recorded signals, sampled at 1 kHz, turns per second (t/s) and zero-crossings per second (zc/s), were estimated from the time domain; median frequency (P_{med}), mean frequency (P_{mean}), frequency at maximum power (P_{fx}), maximum power (P_{max}) and total power (P_{total}), were examined from the frequency domain. Furthermore, the signal was tested for its Gaussianity (sg) and Linearity (sl), the Bispectrum peak amplitude (B_{max}), its peak location in the x and y directions (B_{fx} and B_{fy}, respectively), and the slope of the peak in the x and y direction (B_{fxslope} and B_{fyslope}), with all seven latest parameters belonging to the bi-frequency domain.

Five different force levels (FL) were used: 10, 30, 50, 70 and 100% of maximum voluntary contraction (MVC), with each recording lasting 5 seconds. Wilcoxon signed-rank test was used to detect differences between the medians of samples at various force transitions. The Wilcoxon signed-rank test is the non-parametric alternative to the paired samples t-test. It is considered to be similar but more powerful than the t-test in detecting the differences between samples, since it takes into consideration the magnitude of the observations. The confidence interval (CI) of 95% employed was computed using the Hodges-Lehman method. Differences between groups (normal, myopathy and neuropathy groups) were investigated with

the aid of Mann-Whitney test (significance level 95%). The experimental protocol's repeatability was examined with the aid of repeated recordings of a female normal volunteer. Reliability of measurements was investigated from a random sample of 10 normal subjects. Both repeatability and reliability were examined with the aid of the Wilcoxon signed-rank test, calculation of the standard error of the mean and coefficient of variation. The same analysis was also used to investigate the influence of age and gender. The degree of association (correlation) between any two parameters was examined using the Spearman correlation coefficient utilizing once again a 95% CI. It is also a non-parametric solution and an alternative to the Pearson correlation coefficient.

Cluster analysis using the KNN algorithm was used, being the most widely recognised and used technique, to perform two (a. NORMAL/ABNORMAL (MYO and NEURO) and b. MYO/NEURO), and three class (NOR/MYO/NEURO) classification models. Self Organising Feature Maps were applied to give visually the mapping of two (a. NORMAL/ABNORMAL and b. MYO/NEURO) and three (NOR/MYO/NEURO) class models.

4.5 Feature extraction in the time-domain

For each EMG epoch, at each force level, the following parameters were measured in the time domain:

1. Turns per second (t/s): Number of slope reversals separated from the previous one and the following turn by an amplitude difference greater than 20 μV . Figure 4.8 shows an example with 4 visible turns.
2. Zero crossings per second (z/c): Defined as the number of sign reversals exceeding a threshold of 20 μV . Fig. 4.8 shows 3 visible crossings.

The threshold of 20 μV was selected after experimenting with thresholds at different levels. Initially 50 μV was selected, but this caused many values, especially at low FLs to be recorded as zero for both parameters as did 40 and 30 μV . Ten μV however proved to be too small, since signals recorded with this threshold were too noisy.

Figure 4.8 Turns per second estimation.

4.6 Feature extraction in the frequency domain

For each 512 ms epoch, the average power spectrum (PS) curve was computed by taking the FFT of 512 points, with 25% overlap segments. The following parameters were computed from the power spectrum curve:

1. Median frequency (Pf_{med}): Frequency dividing the area under the PS curve in to two equal parts. The median frequency presents, as mentioned earlier, the following advantages versus the mean frequency:
 - (i) The median frequency estimate is less affected by the noise imposed to the SEMG signal, Merletti et al (1989).
 - (ii) More appropriate for physiological signals, which do not present the characteristics of a normal distribution.
 - (iii) Being a zero-order parameter, all frequency components are weighted equally, in contrast with first-order parameters.

$$Pf_{med} = \int_0^{f_p} P(f)df = \int_{f_p}^{\infty} P(f)df = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^{\infty} P(f)df \quad (4.1)$$

2. Mean frequency (Pf_{mean})

$$Pf_{mean} = \frac{\int_0^{\infty} f P(f) df}{\int_0^{\infty} P(f) df} \quad (4.2)$$

The mean frequency, being a first order parameter, causes the power in the high frequency region to be weighted more. This would cause the mean frequency to be more sensitive and thus more appropriate when changes in the high frequency region are expected, unlike a SEMG signal where more changes are expected in the low frequency region.

3. Frequency at maximum power (Pf_x): The frequency corresponding to the peak of the (PS) curve.
4. Total power (P_{total}): Calculated as the total area under the PS curve.
5. Maximum power (P_{max}): Highest value of the PS curve.

For the last two parameters, values reported are in nV^2/Hz .

4.7 Feature extraction in the bi-frequency domain

For a real zero-mean, stationary process $\{X(k)\}$, the third-order cumulant (TOC) is defined as the expected value of the triple product, Hinich (1982):

$$R(m, n) = E\{X(k)X(k+m)X(k+n)\}, \quad (4.3)$$

and the bispectrum is defined as the Fourier transform of the TOC sequence:

$$B(\omega_1, \omega_2) = \sum_{m=-\infty}^{m=\infty} \sum_{n=-\infty}^{n=\infty} R(m, n) e^{-j(\omega_1 m + \omega_2 n)} \quad (4.4)$$

In addition, the sum of magnitudes of the estimated bispectrum is computed by

$$D = \sum_{(\omega_1, \omega_2)} |B(\omega_1, \omega_2)|. \quad (4.5)$$

To quantify the non-Gaussianity of a random process, the normalised bispectrum, or bicoherence is estimated as follows:

$$B_n(\omega_1, \omega_2) = \frac{B(\omega_1, \omega_2)}{\sqrt{P(\omega_1)P(\omega_2)P(\omega_1 + \omega_2)}}, \quad (4.6)$$

where $P(\cdot)$ is the estimated power spectrum. The test of Gaussianity is based on the mean bicoherence power, defined as follows:

$$S_g = \sum |B_n(\omega_1, \omega_2)|^2, \quad (4.7)$$

with the summation of P points performed over the non-redundant region, Nikias (1987).

For each epoch, the average bispectrum curve was computed using a window of 512 points in length with a 25% of overlap. The following tests and parameters were applied and computed respectively, based on the bispectrum curve:

1. Gaussianity test (sg), (actually zero-skewness test): it basically involves deciding whether or not the expected value of the estimated bicoherence index is zero, i.e., $E\{B_n(\omega_1, \omega_2)\} = 0$. When $B(\omega_1, \omega_2) = 0$ the S_g statistic in (4.7) is X^2 distributed, with $2P$ degrees of freedom, Hinich (1982). Consequently, by examining whether the observed S_g is consistent or not with a central chi-squared distribution, the assumption of Gaussianity or non-Gaussianity could be adopted, respectively. A measure of this consistency is the probability-of-false alarm value, that is, the probability of being wrong in the adoption of the non-zero bispectrum assumption, Hinich (1982). In this case, the non-Gaussianity assumption was accepted if the probability-of-false alarm was less than 5%.
2. Linearity test (sl): this is a measure of how constant the bicoherence index is in the bi-frequency domain, employing a measure of the absolute difference (dR) between a theoretical inter-quartile range, R' , which corresponds to a $X^2_2(\lambda)$, i.e., a chi-squared distributed random variable with two degrees of freedom and a non-centrality parameter λ , and the estimated inter-quartile range, R , derived from the estimated squared bicoherence, Hinich (1982). Here the non-Linearity hypothesis was adopted when $\frac{dR}{R} > 2$.

3. Bispectrum peak (Bmax): it was calculated as the peak of the bispectrum curve.
4. Location of the Bmax in the x-direction (Bfx): it was calculated as the location of the peak of the bispectrum curve in the x-direction.
5. Location of Bmax in the y-direction (Bfy): it was calculated as the location of the peak of the bispectrum curve in the y-direction.
6. Rate of change of Bmax in the x-direction (Bfxslope).
7. Rate of change of Bmax in the y-direction direction (Bfyslope).

4.8 Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis is an analysis of a set of data in order to draw inferences and information by means of analysing the data. Although statistical analysis, involves many tools, the most known is that of average or mean, said to be derived from the Latin word *Havaria*. The statistical analysis performed here with this set of data, involves the calculation of the following:

Mean or average value

This is one of the most important ways of describing a distribution. One measure of the mean is the arithmetic mean, denoted by:

$$mean = \frac{\sum_{n=1}^n x}{n} \quad (4.8)$$

where Σx is the sum of samples and n the sample size.

Median value

This is another method of evaluating the average or mean and is defined as being equal to the central value in a list of data given in a numerical order. In general, the median is the $\frac{1}{2}(n + 1)th$ number in a list of n values.

$$Median\ value: \frac{1}{2}(n + 1)th. \quad (4.9)$$

Standard deviation

The standard deviation is a refinement of the mean deviation and is considered to be the most important measure of the spread. It indicates how widely the values are

dispersed from the mean value. The standard deviation calculated here is using the nonbiased or the n-1 method with the help of the following formula:

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{n\sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2}{n(n-1)}} \quad (4.10)$$

Coefficient of variation

The coefficient of variation (CV) was employed to investigate the relative scatter in data with respect to the mean. It has no units. When CV is small, the data scatter compared to the mean is small. However when CV is large compared to the mean, the amount of variation is large. The disadvantage of CV is that it assumes a Gaussian distribution of data.

The CV is estimated as $CV = \frac{SD}{mean} \times 100\%$ (4.11)

Standard error of the mean (SEM)

This is the standard deviation of the sampling distribution of the mean. The larger the sample sizes the smaller the SEM. More specifically the size of the SEM is inversely proportional to the square root of the sample size. This parameter does not assume a normal distribution and hence it is an accurate estimation, used in repeatability measurements.

It may be calculated as: $SEM = \frac{SD}{\sqrt{n}}$ (4.12)

Quartiles. Another approach to the study of dispersion is by the examination of the given information in relation to the range of data examined. This is achieved by dividing the frequency of events in four equal parts, each one corresponding to 25% of the values.

- (i) First quartile range. $P_{25\%}$ is the number corresponding to 25% of the values, placed in ascending order.
- (ii) Third quartile range. $P_{75\%}$ is the number corresponding to 75% of the values placed in ascending order.
- (iii) Semi inter-quartile range. This is a measure of spread around the mean and is a useful method for comparing the dispersions in two parallel sets

of observations, such as the dispersion of median frequency for two groups of subjects performed at the same force level.

$$\text{SIQR} = \frac{1}{2} (P_{75\%} - P_{25\%}). \quad (4.13)$$

4.9 Repeatability and reliability

The purpose of applying repeatability measurements in this study was to investigate the effectiveness of the set-up and the recording protocol. One female normal subject was asked to participate. After one set of recordings, all attached electrodes were removed from her arm and she was asked to stand up, walk in the room but had to refrain from smoking, eating or drinking anything else besides water. After a fifteen-minute interval, she was asked to lie down on the couch once again, the electrodes were attached and the experiment was repeated.

The purpose of reliability as applied in this study was to investigate:

- (i) Whether there was a significant ($p < 0.05$) difference between two sets of recordings taken from an arbitrary sample of subjects irrespective of age or gender. The time elapsed between the two sets of recordings was ranging from 24 hours to nearly two years.
- (ii) To investigate if recordings were influenced significantly ($p < 0.05$) depending on increasing or decreasing force levels. All recordings in this study were performed in a downward force level, meaning that after 100% MVC, 70, 50, 30 and finally 10% MVC were performed. This downwards methodology was chosen to eliminate even more the remote possibility of fatigue despite the two-minute interval between efforts. However for the arbitrary sample mentioned above, recordings were taken in an upward methodology as well, meaning that recordings started with 10% and 30, 50, 70 and 100% MVC followed. The upward and downward set of samples was compared.

Repeatability and reliability were investigated here with the aid of detecting differences between the medians of samples using the Wilcoxon signed-rank test ($p < 0.05$), calculating and plotting the standard error of the mean. Wilcoxon signed rank-test is considered more accurate than similar repeatability methods such as the Interclass Correlation Coefficient ICC method, whenever a time interval of more than two weeks has elapsed between recordings since one cannot be sure that

individual conditions (physical and physiological), remain constant. In other words some confounding factors can arise, increasing the total variance.

4.10 Age and gender dependence

Age dependence was investigated in this study with three methods. It should be emphasised that since chronological age is not the same as physiological age, there may be little difference expected, when narrow age bands are compared.

Method 1: *Analysis of age based on the Wilcoxon signed-rank test.* Parameter changes were classified as significant or non-significant during three force transitions. From 10-50%, 50-100% and 10-100% MVC. These force transitions have been chosen since they represent force changes from low to mid, mid to high and low to high force levels. Wilcoxon-signed rank test ($p < 0.05$), investigated the influence of these three force transitions first for all 94 subjects for each parameter separately and then for each age decade separately.

Method 2: *Analysis of age based on coefficient of variation and the standard error of the mean.* In order to have a visual representation of the influence of age on the parameters examined, the coefficient of variation, CV, (standard deviation over the mean), was adopted. A small CV indicates that the data scatter compared to the mean is small, whereas a large CV indicates the opposite. Furthermore tables list the standard deviation, CV and SEM values.

Method 3. *Analysis of age based on the continuous descriptive analysis.* A visual representation of the results obtained helps towards understanding the trend of changes. This method shows an overall picture of the observations of the variable (age). The central tendency and the scatter/dispersion of the observations may be quantified. Box-plots shown identify possible outliers if exist. Confidence intervals are computed around the mean and median, indicating the range of values likely to contain the true population, mean or median.

Gender dependence. The same three methods explained above were also used to investigate gender dependence.

Method 1. *Analysis of gender based on the Wilcoxon signed-rank test.* The same force transition groups were used here.

Method 2: *Analysis of gender based on the coefficient of variation and standard error of the mean.* This method was applied for the same reasoning as described above

Method 3. *Analysis of gender based on the continuous descriptive analysis.* Gender analysis was performed for the same reasoning as described for the analysis of age.

4.11 Correlation analysis

Any correlation coefficient (r) indicates the extent to which a pair of numbers (variables), from two sets lies on a straight line. For two variables X and Y the correlation is the covariance of X with Y (covarXY), divided by the product of the standard deviation of X (SD_X) and the standard deviation of Y (SD_Y).

$$r = \frac{\text{cov ar } XY}{SD_X SD_Y} \quad (4.14)$$

The covariance is defined as the mean value of all the pairs of differences from the mean for X multiplied by the differences from the mean for Y. If X and Y are not closely related to each other, they do not *co-vary*, so the covariance is small and hence the correlation is small. If X and Y are closely related, covarXY turns out to be almost the same as $SD_X \times SD_Y$, so the correlation is almost 1.

There are different kinds of correlation and the selection should be based on the data sets under investigation. The degree of association between any two parameters in this study was examined using the Spearman correlation coefficient with a 95% CI. It is a non-parametric solution and an alternative to the Pearson correlation coefficient. Only those parameter pairs presenting a good (0.6-0.8) and an excellent correlation (0.8-1.0) are presented for normal subjects and the corresponding pairs for abnormal subjects.

4.12 Cluster Analysis

The KNN classifier was used in this study for classifying subjects, for two class models (NORMAL/ABNORMAL), (MYO/NEURO) and for three class models (NOR/MYO/NEURO) respectively. It is a classification technique in which the patterns are known. Whenever a new pattern needs to be classified, its k (say 3), nearest neighbours from the reference patterns are identified and the new pattern is classified to the most frequent class among its neighbours based on a similarity measure which is usually the Euclidean distance given below. In the simple nearest neighbour method the new pattern is classified to the first nearest pattern, (k=1).

$$Ed_{xy} = \|x - y\| = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - y_i)^2} \quad (4.15)$$

In order to evaluate the performance of a cluster analysis system the following parameters need to be first defined: (i) True positive (TP), decision occurs when the positive diagnosis of the system coincides with a positive diagnosis according to the Neurophysiologist (ii) False positive (FP) decision occurs when the system made a positive diagnosis that is not in agreement with the Neurophysiologist (iii) False negative (FN), occurs when the system made a negative diagnosis that is not in agreement with the Neurophysiologist and (iv) True negative (TN) both the physician and the system indicate the absence of a positive diagnosis. The following measures may then be defined, Tou et al (1974):

Percentage of correct classifications (%CC)

$$\%CC = 100 \times (TP + TN) / n \quad (4.16)$$

n is the number of subjects.

Percentage of false positives (%FP)

$$\%FP = 100 \times FP / (TN + FP) \quad (4.17)$$

Percentage of false negatives (%FN)

$$\%FN = 100 \times FN / (TP + FN) \quad (4.18)$$

Sensitivity

$$SE = 100 \times TP / (TP + FN) \quad (4.19)$$

Sensitivity is the likelihood that an event will be detected given that it is present.

Specificity

$$SP = 100 \times TN / (TN + FP) \quad (4.20)$$

Specificity is the likelihood that the absence of an event will be detected given that it is absent.

Recall

$$RE = 100 \times TP / (N_{NEUR} + N_{MYO}) \quad (4.21)$$

where N_{NEUR} is the number of NEURO patients and N_{MYO} is the number of MYO patients.

Recall is the number of positive diagnoses correctly made by the system, divided by the total number of positive diagnoses made by the physician.

Precision

$$PR = 100 \times TP / (TP + FP) \quad (4.22)$$

In this study, KNN two and three subject classification system was implemented for different values of $k=1,3,5$ and 7 . The following KNN classifier models were developed:

1. Two class classification models.

- (i) For 36 subjects, 18 normal subjects and 18 patients and for all 70 features (14 parameters at five force levels). Normal subjects were selected so that their gender and age matched as close as possible those of the patients.
- (ii) Same as above but for 25 selected features, which showed significant differences between the three groups. Turns and zero crossings per second t/s,

zc/s , median frequency P_{fmed} , total power P_{total} and the maximum bispectrum amplitude B_{max} .

- (iii) For a larger group of subjects, (111 in total), 91 normal and 20 patients for all 70 features.
- (iv) Same as above but for the 25 selected features.
- (v) For 20 subjects, 11 myopathy and 9 neuropathy patients for all 70 features.
- (vi) Same as above but for the 25 selected features.

2. Three class classification models.

- (i) For 27 subjects (9 from each group), for all 70 features.
- (ii) Same as above but for the 25 features.
- (iii) For 36 subjects (18 normal subjects, selected with the same method as mentioned above), 9 myopathy and 9 neuropathy patients and for all 70 features.
- (iv) Same as above but for 25 features.
- (v) For 111 subjects, 91 normals, 11 myopathy patients and 9 neuropathy patients, for all 70 features.
- (vi) Same as above but for 25 features.

The above are summarized in Table 4.1.

Table 4.1 KNN classifiers used for subject classification.

TWO CLASS CLASSIFICATION	NUMBER OF FEATURES
NORMALS/PATIENTS	
18/18	70
18/18	25
91/20	70
91/20	25
TWO CLASS CLASSIFICATION	NUMBER OF FEATURES
MYOPATHY/NEUROPATHY	
11/9	70
11/9	25
NUMBER OF SUBJECTS	NUMBER OF FEATURES
NORMALS/MYOPATHY/NEUROPATHY	
9/9/9	70
9/9/9	25
18/9/9	70
18/9/9	25
91/11/9	70
91/11/9	25

4.13 Self organizing Feature Maps

The Kohonen Self-Organizing Feature Maps (SOFM), Kohonen, (1990), can be seen as an extension of competitive learning. The basic difference to competitive learning is that not only the weights of the winner node are adapted but also the weights of all neighbouring output nodes to the winner. This results in an ordering of similar input patterns in neighbouring output nodes. The weights are adapted without supervision in such a way that the density distribution of the input data is preserved and represented on the output nodes. This mapping of similar input patterns to output nodes which are close to each other represents a discrimination of the input space and is said to be *topology preserving*. The Kohonen self-organizing feature maps can be used for the visualisation of the distribution of the input data.

The output nodes are usually ordered in a two-dimensional grid and the neighbourhood decreases in size over time. The weights of the output nodes in the neighbourhood are adapted with

$$w_{ij}(t+1) = w_{ij}(t) + \eta h_k(t)(x_i - w_{ij}(t)) \quad (4.23)$$

where η is a gain term ($0 < \eta \leq 1$) and $h_k(t)$ is a decreasing function that decreases in time. In general, $h_k(t)$ can be a Gaussian function defining the neighbourhood so that nodes near the winning node are adapted more strongly than nodes far away. Another neighbourhood function is the *Mexican hat*, where nodes near the winning node are changed positively (excitation) in order to match the input pattern whereas nodes further away negatively (inhibition).

The self-organization principle is also encountered in the organization of the various areas of the brain where neurons are ordered according to different sensory signals. For example, the visual, somatosensory or motor response signals are obtained in the same topographical order on the cortex in which they were received at the sensory organs. The basic principle of a topographically ordered system is that nearby units should respond in a similar way.

The SOFM algorithm finds applications in machine vision and image analysis, image coding and compression, image segmentation, medical imaging and analysis, medical diagnosis, optical character and script reading, speech analysis and recognition, speaker identification, signal processing and radar measurements, process control and robotics.

4.14 Feature Normalisation

All features used for classification in this study were normalised before use by subtracting their mean value and dividing with their standard deviation SD:

$$n(x_i) = (x_i - \text{mean}_i) / SD_i \quad (4.24)$$

where x_i is the value, mean_i is the mean value and SD_i is the standard deviation of the feature i .

Chapter 5

Results

Chapter 5

RESULTS

5.1 Introduction

The results presented in this chapter correspond to the analysis of the SEMG recordings from the left biceps brachii muscle of 94 normal (NOR) subjects aged between 5 and 69 years old, and 20 subjects, (11 myopathy (MYO) and 9 neuropathy (NEURO) disease subjects), as presented in Chapter 4.

Fourteen parameters were extracted: two from the time domain (turns per second and zero crossings per second), five from the frequency domain (median frequency, mean frequency, frequency at maximum power, maximum power, and total power) and seven from the bi-frequency domain (amplitude of the peak of bispectrum, test for Gaussianity, test for linearity, coordinates of the bispectrum peak in the x and y directions and the slope of the peak in the x and y directions). A statistical analysis based on force level, is presented for each parameter, separately for each group (NOR, MYO and NEURO), listing the mean, the standard deviation, the standard error of the mean, the coefficient of variation, the median, semi interquartile range, and the 5th (P_{5%}), 25th (P_{25%}), 75th (P_{75%}), and 95th (P_{95%}), percentile ranges. Descriptive box-plots for each parameter are shown for the three groups of subjects. Furthermore, a statistical analysis of all values, (those recorded at 10%, followed by those recorded at 30%, 50%, 70% and 100% MVC), was carried out enabling an easy comparison between the three groups of subjects. Differences among groups during all possible force level transitions were then derived for each parameter. The Wilcoxon signed-ranks tests, utilising a two-tailed significance level of 95% ($p < 0.05$) was utilised to classify differences as significant or non-significant. Classification of differences among values between the three groups for each parameter are then presented using the Mann-Whitney test. Histogram distributions of all the values recorded from all subjects for the five force levels are then presented.

Repeatability of measurements is also presented, indicating the validity of the recording set-up and protocols. Reliability measurements on ten normal subjects were also performed and shown, in order to:

- (i) investigate whether similar results are recorded after a period of time has elapsed, and
- (ii) investigate if analysis depends on whether a recording starts from a high force level going to a low force level or vice versa.

Furthermore analysis based on age and gender of the normal subjects was performed based on three different methods:

- (i) Wilcoxon signed-rank test.
- (ii) The coefficient of variation.
- (iii) Continuous descriptive analysis.

Correlation studies were also performed to investigate whether pairs of variables examined were correlated or not. Only the pairs of variables presenting a good and excellent correlation for NORMAL subjects are presented, and compared with the corresponding pairs for ABNORMAL subjects.

KNN classifier performance results, was performed for two class models (NORMAL/ABNORMAL), (MYO/NEURO) and for three class models (NOR/MYO/NEURO) respectively. Various models were investigated depending on the number of subjects, number of features and values for k . Performance results are given including: the percentage of correct classification, percentage of false positives, percentage of false negatives, sensitivity, specificity recall and precision.

Self Organising Feature Maps giving the mapping for the various classes selected are also provided.

5.2 Time domain analysis

In this section, the statistics of the turns per second parameter, t/s , at each force level, are given for the NOR, MYO and NEURO subjects in Tables 5.1 to 5.3 respectively. Descriptive box plots for t/s for the three groups are shown separately for values recorded at each force level and for all values together in Fig. 5.1. The vertical

notched lines next to all descriptive boxes represent the 95% of the parametric percentile range of that measurement, whereas the diamond shape Figs. show the mean and the requested confidences interval around it. The notched boxes, (non-parametric statistics) show the median, lower and upper quartiles and the confidence interval around the median. The dotted lines connect the nearest observations within 1.5 of the inter quartile range (IQR) of the lower and upper quartiles. Finally crosses (+) and circles (o) indicate possible outliers, observations more than 1.5 IQR and 3.0 IQR from the quartiles respectively. Table 5.4 tabulates the statistical analysis results for the values of t/s for all five-force levels together, between the three groups of subjects. Table 5.5 tabulates the Wilcoxon signed-ranks test from a lower to a higher force level for the t/s parameter for the three groups, whereas Table 5.6 tabulates the statistical differences between the three groups. Fig. 5.2 shows the histogram distribution for the three groups for the t/s parameter for the three groups at each force level. Tables 5.7 to 5.12 and Figs. 5.3 and 5.4 give the corresponding results and plots for the zero crosses per second parameter, zc/s.

Table 5.1 Statistics of the turns per second parameter, t/s, for the 94 NOR subjects with respect to force level FL, % MVC.

%MVC	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
10	6.0	7.5	0.8	125.0	3.0	4.0	0.0	0.0	8.0	22.0
30	12.0	10.5	1.1	88.0	10.0	9.0	0.0	2.0	20.0	28.0
50	17.0	12.4	1.3	73.0	17.0	10.0	0.0	7.0	26.0	42.0
70	22.0	13.0	1.4	59.0	23.0	9.0	0.0	13.0	30.0	42.0
100	28.0	12.8	1.3	46.0	22.0	9.0	1.1	20.0	37.0	46.0

Table 5.2 Statistics of the turns per second parameter, t/s, for the 11 MYO subjects with respect to FL, % MVC.

% MVC	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
10	23.0	26.0	8.0	113.0	20.0	13.0	0.0	1.0	26.0	53.0
30	29.0	28.0	8.4	97.0	32.0	17.0	0.0	4.0	37.0	56.0
50	35.0	32.0	9.7	91.0	34.0	20.0	1.0	8.0	48.0	63.0
70	38.0	35.0	10.7	92.0	41.0	22.0	3.0	5.0	49.0	72.0
100	47.0	33.0	10.0	70.0	48.0	19.0	13.0	22.0	60.0	80.0

Table 5.3 Statistics of the turns per second parameter, t/s, for the 9 NEURO subjects with respect to FL, % MVC.

% MVC	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
10	17.0	18.8	6.3	111.0	12.0	20.0	0.0	0.0	39.0	45.0
30	25.0	22.6	7.5	90.0	26.0	20.0	0.0	0.0	40.0	62.0
50	33.0	27.0	9.0	82.0	41.0	25.0	0.0	1.0	51.0	76.0
70	37.0	29.0	9.7	78.0	41.0	24.0	0.0	6.0	53.0	84.0
100	46.0	33.0	10.9	73.0	57.0	24.0	1.0	14.0	62.0	97.0

Figure 5.1 Descriptive box plots for the turns per second t/s parameter, for NOR, MYO (m) and NEURO (n) subjects, (a)-10%, (b)-30%, (c)-50%, (d)-70%, (e)-100% MVC and (f)-all FL, values 10-100% MVC.

Table 5.4 Statistics of the values of t/s for all force levels (those recorded at 10%, followed by those recorded at 30%, 50%, 70% and 100% MVC), between the three groups of subjects.

	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
NOR	16.8	13.7	0.6	82.0	15.4	11.5	0.0	4.0	27.0	43.0
MYO	34.4	31.1	4.2	91.5	31.6	21.5	0.0	6.0	49.0	93.0
NEURO	31.2	27.0	4.0	87.1	36.7	25.0	0.0	1.0	51.0	76.0

Table 5.5 Evaluation of the transition from a lower to a higher force level for the turns per second parameter, t/s, utilising the Wilcoxon signed-ranks test. S: significant at $p < 0.05$, NS: non-significant at $p \geq 0.05$.

% MVC	NOR	MYO	NEURO
10 – 30	S	S	S
10 – 50	S	S	S
10 – 70	S	S	S
10 – 100	S	S	S
30 – 50	S	S	S
30 – 70	S	S	S
30 – 100	S	S	S
50 – 70	S	NS	S
50 – 100	S	S	S
70 - 100	S	S	S

Table 5.6 Classification of differences between the three groups of subjects, for the t/s parameter, utilising the Mann-Whitney test (significance level 95% ($p < 0.05$)).

NOR	MYO	S
NOR	NEURO	S
MYO	NEURO	NS

Figure 5.2 Histogram distributions for the turns per second, t/s , parameter for the values for all force levels, 10-100% MVC for NOR, MYO and NEURO subjects.

Table 5.7 Statistics of the zero crossings per second parameter, zc/s , for the 94 NOR subjects with respect to FL, % MVC.

% MVC	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
10	3.0	6.0	0.6	200.0	0.0	1.0	0.0	0.0	2.0	16.0
30	7.0	8.8	0.9	126.0	4.0	6.0	0.0	0.0	11.0	24.0
50	12.0	11.2	1.2	93.0	10.0	10.0	0.0	1.0	21.0	32.0
70	16.0	11.7	1.2	73.0	17.0	10.0	0.0	6.0	25.0	35.0
100	22.0	11.8	1.2	54.0	23.0	7.0	0.0	16.0	30.0	39.0

Table 5.8 Statistics of the zero crossings per second parameter, zc/s , for the 11 MYO patients with respect to FL, % MVC.

% MVC	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
10	17.0	24.8	7.5	146.0	7.0	10.0	0.0	0.0	20.0	47.0
30	23.0	25.1	7.6	109.0	23.0	15.0	0.0	0.0	30.0	50.0
50	29.0	28.9	8.7	100.0	29.0	21.0	0.0	1.0	42.0	54.0
70	32.0	29.6	8.9	93.0	35.0	21.0	0.0	1.0	44.0	60.0
100	36.0	27.6	8.32	77.0	41.0	21.0	0.0	11.0	52.0	61.0

Table 5.9 Statistics of the zero crossings per second parameter, zc/s , for the 9 NEURO patients with respect to FL, % MVC.

% MVC	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
10	10.0	14.7	4.9	147.0	1.0	12.0	0.0	0.0	24.0	38.0
30	18.0	19.4	6.5	108.0	11.0	17.0	0.0	0.0	34.0	49.0
50	26.0	24.0	8.0	92.0	24.0	20.0	0.0	0.0	39.0	69.0
70	31.0	26.5	8.84	85.0	31.0	24.0	0.0	0.0	49.0	76.0
100	38.0	30.7	10.2	81.0	47.0	28.0	0.0	3.0	59.0	86.0

Figure 5.3 Descriptive box plots for the zero crossing per second zc/s parameter, for NOR, MYO (m) and NEURO (n) subjects, (a)-10%, (b)-30%, (c)-50%, (d)-70%, (e)-100% MVC and (f)-all FL values 10-100% MVC.

Table 5.10 Statistics of the values of *zc/s* for all force levels (those recorded at 10%, followed by those recorded at 30%, 50%, 70% and 100% MVC), between the three groups of subjects.

	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
NOR	12.1	12.0	0.6	99.2	8.5	10.5	0.0	0.0	21.0	34.0
MYO	27.3	27.1	3.7	99.3	26.0	20.5	0.0	1.0	42.0	81.0
NEURO	24.4	24.6	3.7	100.0	24.0	22.5	0.0	0.0	45.0	69.0

Table 5.11 Evaluation of the transition from a lower to a higher force level for the zero crossings per second parameter, *zc/s*, utilising the Wilcoxon signed-ranks test. S: significant at $p < 0.05$, NS: non significant at $p \geq 0.05$.

% MVC	NOR	MYO	NEURO
10 – 30	S	S	S
10 – 50	S	S	S
10 – 70	S	S	S
10 - 100	S	S	S
30 – 50	S	S	S
30 – 70	S	S	S
30 – 100	S	S	S
50 – 70	S	NS	S
50 – 100	S	S	S
70 - 100	S	S	S

Table 5.12 Classification of differences between the three groups of subjects, for the *zc/s* parameter, utilising the Mann-Whitney test (significance level 95% ($p < 0.05$)).

NOR	MYO	S
NOR	NEURO	S
MYO	NEURO	NS

Figure 5.4 Histogram distributions for the zero crossings per second, zc/s , parameter for the values for all force levels, 10-100% MVC for NOR, MYO and NEURO subjects.

5.3 Frequency domain analysis

In this section, the statistics of the median frequency, P_{fmed} , at each force level, are given for the NOR, MYO and NEURO subjects in Tables 5.13 to 5.15 respectively. Descriptive box plots for P_{fmed} for the three groups are shown separately for values recorded at each force level and for all values together in Fig. 5.5. Table 5.16 tabulates the statistical analysis results for the values of P_{fmed} for all five-force levels together between the three groups of subjects. Table 5.17 tabulates the Wilcoxon signed-ranks test from a lower to a higher force level for the P_{fmed} parameter for the three groups, whereas Table 5.18 tabulates the statistical differences between the three groups. Fig. 5.6 shows the histogram distribution for the three groups for the P_{fmed} parameter for the three groups at each force level. Tables 5.19 to 5.24 and Figs. 5.7 and 5.8 give the corresponding results and plots for the mean frequency parameter, P_{fmean} , whereas Tables 5.25 to 5.30 and Figs. 5.9 and 5.10 those of the frequency at maximum power parameter, P_{fx} . The section continues with Tables 5.31 to 5.36 and Figs. 5.11 and 5.12 those of the logarithm of maximum power parameter, P_{max} and Tables 5.37 to 5.42 and Figs. 5.13 and 5.14, being those for the total power parameter, P_{total} .

Table 5.13 Statistics of the median frequency parameter, P_{fmed}, for the 94 NOR subjects with respect to FL, % MVC.

% MVC	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
10	109.0	26.8	2.8	25.0	104.0	17.5	72.0	90.0	125.0	155.0
30	104.0	23.0	2.4	22.0	101.0	14.0	70.0	88.0	116.0	145.0
50	102.0	21.4	2.2	21.0	99.0	14.5	73.0	86.0	115.0	136.0
70	100.0	21.1	2.2	21.0	95.0	14.0	72.0	84.0	112.0	134.0
100	96.0	19.7	2.1	21.0	93.0	13.5	67.0	83.0	110.0	129.0

Table 5.14 Statistics of the median frequency parameter, P_{fmed}, for the 11 MYO subjects with respect to FL, % MVC.

% MVC	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
10	103.0	22.5	6.8	22.0	108.0	19.0	69.0	76.0	114.0	124.0
30	103.0	24.5	7.4	33.0	97.0	11.5	60.0	92.0	115.0	124.0
50	102.0	27.6	8.3	27.0	96.0	12.0	60.0	87.0	111.0	119.0
70	97.0	21.6	6.5	22.0	101.0	13.5	58.0	82.0	109.0	116.0
100	102.0	32.8	9.9	32.0	101.0	12.0	54.0	82.0	106.0	123.0

Table 5.15 Statistics of the median frequency parameter, P_{fmed}, for the 9 NEURO subjects with respect to FL, % MVC.

% MVC	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
10	120.0	23.5	7.8	20.0	109.0	22.0	92.0	97.0	141.0	153.0
30	118.0	21.0	7.0	18.0	116.0	13.0	97.0	98.0	124.0	167.0
50	121.0	31.0	10.3	26.0	115.0	17.5	91.0	99.0	134.0	191.0
70	117.0	32.0	10.7	27.0	109.0	13.5	88.0	92.0	119.0	194.0
100	117.0	32.0	10.7	27.0	108.0	13.5	77.0	92.0	129.0	183.0

Figure 5.5 Descriptive box plots for the median frequency parameter, Pfmед, for NOR, MYO (m) and NEURO (n) subjects, (a)-10%, (b)-30%, (c)-50%, (d)-70%, (e)-100% MVC and (f)-all FL values 10-100% MVC.

Table 5.16 Statistics of the all values of P_{fmed}, for all force levels (those recorded at 10%, followed by those recorded at 30%, 50%, 70% and 100% MVC), between the three groups of subjects.

	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
NOR	102.1	22.9	1.1	22.4	98.0	14.5	72.0	86.0	115.0	143.0
MYO	101.6	25.1	3.4	24.7	101.1	14.0	60.0	87.0	115.0	139.0
NEURO	118.5	26.9	4.0	22.7	110.0	17.0	88.0	98.0	132.0	183.0

Table 5.17 Evaluation of the transition from a lower to a higher force level for the median frequency parameter, P_{fmed}, utilising the Wilcoxon signed-ranks test. S: significant at $p < 0.05$, NS: non-significant at $p \geq 0.05$.

% MVC	NOR	MYO	NEURO
10 – 30	S	NS	NS
10 – 50	S	NS	NS
10 – 70	S	NS	NS
10 – 100	S	NS	NS
30 – 50	S	NS	NS
30 – 70	S	NS	NS
30 – 100	S	NS	NS
50 – 70	S	NS	NS
50 – 100	S	NS	NS
70 – 100	S	NS	NS

Table 5.18 Classification of differences between the three groups of subjects, for the P_{fmed} parameter, utilising the Mann-Whitney test (significance level 95% ($p < 0.05$)).

NOR	MYO	NS
NOR	NEURO	S
MYO	NEURO	S

Figure 5.6 Histogram distributions for the median frequency parameter, P_{fmed} , for the values for all force levels, 10-100% MVC, for NOR, MYO and NEURO subjects.

Table 5.19 Statistics of the mean frequency parameter, P_{fmean}, for the 94 NOR subjects with respect to FL, % MVC.

% MVC	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
10	136.0	31.8	3.3	23.0	130.0	22.0	82.0	110.0	154.0	187.0
30	125.0	28.9	3.0	23.0	124.0	20.0	78.0	104.0	144.0	175.0
50	121.0	27.5	2.9	23.0	118.0	18.0	75.0	101.0	137.0	170.0
70	117.0	26.7	2.8	23.0	114.0	16.5	71.0	101.0	134.0	165.0
100	112.0	24.4	2.6	22.0	112.0	13.5	65.0	98.0	125.0	157.0

Table 5.20 Statistics of the mean frequency parameter, P_{fmean}, for the 11 MYO subjects with respect to FL, % MVC.

% MVC	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
10	126.0	28.8	8.7	23.0	133.0	24.0	86.0	92.0	140.0	147.0
30	129.0	24.3	7.3	19.0	131.0	12.0	90.0	112.0	136.0	158.0
50	130.0	24.6	7.4	19.0	138.0	17.0	93.0	109.0	143.0	147.0
70	133.0	40.0	12.1	30.0	135.0	18.0	89.0	105.0	141.0	163.0
100	132.0	38.4	11.6	29.0	127.0	14.5	88.0	105.0	134.0	157.0

Table 5.21 Statistics of the mean frequency parameter, P_{fmean}, for the 9 NEURO subjects with respect to FL, % MVC.

% MVC	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
10	139.0	30.0	10.0	22.0	140.0	30.5	105.0	110.0	171.0	181.0
30	135.0	25.0	8.3	19.0	135.0	17.5	108.0	109.0	144.0	181.0
50	136.0	32.0	10.7	24.0	140.0	19.5	101.0	105.0	144.0	193.0
70	132.0	31.0	10.3	24.0	136.0	21.0	94.0	98.0	140.0	194.0
100	132.0	35.0	11.7	27.0	136.0	25.0	92.0	94.0	142.0	188.0

Figure 5.7 Descriptive box plots for the mean frequency P_{fmean} parameter, for NOR, MYO (m) and NEURO (n) subjects, (a)-10%, (b)-30%, (c)-50%, (d)-70%, (e)-100% MVC and (f)-all FL values 10-100% MVC.

Table 5.22 Statistics of the values of P_{fmean}, for all force levels (those recorded at 10%, followed by those recorded at 30%, 50%, 70% and 100% MVC), between the three groups of subjects.

	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
NOR	121.9	28.8	1.4	23.6	119.0	16.5	76.0	104.0	137.0	174.0
MYO	130.0	29.4	4.4	23.7	131.0	17.0	88.0	109.0	143.0	178.0
NEURO	134.7	29.4	4.4	21.8	133.0	19.0	94.0	109.0	146.0	188.0

Table 5.23 Evaluation of the transition from a lower to a higher force level for the mean frequency parameter, P_{fmean}, utilising the Wilcoxon signed-ranks test. S: significant at $p < 0.05$, NS: non-significant at $p \geq 0.05$.

% MVC	NOR	MYO	NEURO
10 – 30	S	NS	NS
10 – 50	S	NS	NS
10 – 70	S	NS	NS
10 100	S	NS	NS
30 – 50	S	NS	NS
30 – 70	S	NS	NS
30 – 100	S	NS	NS
50 – 70	S	NS	NS
50 – 100	S	NS	NS
70 – 100	S	NS	NS

Table 5.24 Classification of differences between the three groups of subjects, for the P_{fmean} parameter, utilising the Mann-Whitney test (significance level 95% ($p < 0.05$)).

NOR	MYO	NS
NOR	NEURO	S
MYO	NEURO	NS

Figure 5.8 Histogram distributions for the mean frequency parameter, P_{fmean} , for all values for all force levels, 10-100% MVC for NOR, MYO and NEURO subjects with respect to force level, % MVC.

Table 5.25 Statistics of the frequency at maximum power parameter, Pfx, for the 94 NOR subjects with respect to FL, % MVC.

% MVC	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
10	80.0	23.0	2.4	29.0	76.0	16.0	47.0	64.0	96.0	115.0
30	76.0	19.0	2.0	25.0	74.0	10.0	46.0	63.0	83.0	113.0
50	80.0	20.0	2.1	25.0	77.0	13.0	51.0	67.0	93.0	110.0
70	78.0	19.3	2.0	25.0	75.0	13.0	51.0	65.0	91.0	111.0
100	77.0	20.0	2.1	26.0	72.0	12.0	48.0	64.0	88.0	117.0

Table 5.26 Statistics of the frequency at maximum power parameter, Pfx, for the 11 MYO subjects with respect to FL, % MVC.

% MVC	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
10	74.0	26.0	7.8	35.0	60.0	21.0	51.0	51.0	93.0	114.0
30	70.0	22.8	6.9	33.0	60.0	16.5	44.0	50.0	83.0	104.0
50	68.0	17.4	5.2	26.0	61.0	16.0	45.0	51.0	83.0	86.0
70	75.0	19.3	5.8	26.0	67.0	17.0	51.0	58.0	92.0	98.0
100	73.0	14.7	4.4	20.0	76.0	14.5	51.0	56.0	85.0	88.0

Table 5.27 Statistics of the frequency at maximum power parameter, Pfx, for the 9 NEURO subjects with respect to FL, % MVC.

% MVC	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
10	88.0	13.0	4.3	15.0	85.0	12.0	67.0	74.0	98.0	105.0
30	82.0	16.0	5.3	20.0	76.0	8.5	67.0	68.0	85.0	111.0
50	93.0	37.0	12.3	40.0	84.0	18.5	51.0	65.0	102.0	180.0
70	91.0	51.0	17.0	56.0	77.0	12.5	53.0	63.0	88.0	224.0
100	90.0	26.0	8.7	29.0	84.0	16.5	47.0	69.0	102.0	134.0

Figure 5.9 Descriptive box plots for the frequency at maximum power P_{fx} parameter, for NOR, MYO (m) and NEURO (n) subjects, (a)-10%, (b)-30%, (c)-50%, (d)-70%, (e)-100% MVC and (f)-all FL values 10-100% MVC.

Table 5.28 Statistics of the values of Pfx for all force levels (those recorded at 10%, followed by those recorded at 30%, 50%, 70% and 100% MVC), between the three groups of subjects.

	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
NOR	77.8	20.4	0.9	26.2	75.0	13.5	47.0	64.0	91.0	114.0
MYO	71.9	19.8	2.6	27.5	69.0	18.5	50.0	51.0	88.0	104.0
NEURO	88.8	30.7	4.6	34.6	80.0	15.5	51.0	70.0	101.0	134.0

Table 5.29 Evaluation of the transition from a lower to a higher force level for the frequency at maximum power parameter, Pfx, utilising the Wilcoxon signed-ranks test. S: significant at $p < 0.05$, NS: non-significant at $p \geq 0.05$.

% MVC	NOR	MYO	NEURO
10 – 30	S	NS	NS
10 – 50	NS	NS	NS
10 – 70	NS	NS	NS
10 100	NS	NS	NS
30 – 50	NS	NS	NS
30 – 70	NS	NS	NS
30 – 100	NS	NS	NS
50 – 70	NS	NS	NS
50 – 100	NS	NS	NS
70 - 100	NS	NS	NS

Table 5.30 Classification of differences between the three groups of subjects, for the Pfx parameter, utilising the Mann-Whitney test (significance level 95% ($p < 0.05$)).

NOR	MYO	S
NOR	NEURO	S
MYO	NEURO	S

Figure 5.10 Histogram distribution for the frequency at maximum power parameter, P_{fx} , for the values for all force levels, 10-100% MVC for NOR, MYO and NEURO subjects.

Table 5.31 Statistics of the logarithm of maximum power parameter, Pmax, for the 94 NOR subjects with respect to FL, % MVC.

% MVC	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
10	-0.5	0.8	0.1	-160.0	-0.6	0.6	-1.8	-1.1	0.1	1.0
30	0.1	0.9	0.1	900.0	0.0	0.6	-1.4	-0.6	0.6	1.4
50	0.5	1.0	0.3	200.0	0.5	0.7	-1.1	-0.2	1.2	2.3
70	0.9	1.0	0.3	111.1	0.7	0.7	-0.7	0.2	1.5	2.4
100	1.3	1.0	0.3	76.9	1.3	0.7	-0.3	0.6	2.0	2.9

Table 5.32 Statistics of the logarithm of maximum power parameter, Pmax, for the 11 MYO subjects with respect to FL, % MVC.

% MVC	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
10	0.0	1.0	29.2	/	0.1	1.0	-1.5	-1.2	0.7	0.8
30	0.3	0.9	0.3	300.0	0.6	0.8	-1.2	-0.7	0.8	1.4
50	0.6	1.0	0.3	166.7	0.7	0.9	-0.6	-0.5	1.3	1.6
70	0.8	0.9	0.3	112.5	1.0	0.8	-0.4	-0.1	1.5	1.8
100	1.2	1.0	0.3	83.3	1.6	0.9	-0.3	0.1	1.8	2.2

Table 5.33 Statistics of the logarithm of maximum power parameter, Pmax, for the 9 NEURO subjects with respect to FL, % MVC.

% MVC	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
10	-0.5	1.0	0.3	-200.0	-0.6	0.9	-2.1	-1.5	0.2	0.9
30	-0.1	0.9	0.3	-900.0	0.1	0.7	-1.5	-0.9	0.5	1.2
50	0.2	0.9	0.3	450.0	0.5	0.8	-1.3	-0.6	0.9	1.3
70	0.4	0.9	0.3	225.0	0.6	0.8	-1.2	-0.4	1.2	1.5
100	0.7	0.9	0.3	128.6	1.1	0.9	-0.6	-0.2	1.5	1.7

Figure 5.11 Descriptive box plots for the maximum power P_{max} parameter, for NOR, MYO (m) and NEURO (n) subjects, (a)-10%, (b)-30%, (c)-50%, (d)-70%, (e)-100% MVC and (f)-all FL values 10-100% MVC.

Table 5.34 Statistics of the values of for Pmax, for all force levels (those recorded at 10%, followed by those recorded at 30%, 50%, 70% and 100% MVC), between the three groups of subjects.

	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
NOR	0.5	1.1	0.0	220.0	0.4	0.8	-1.4	-0.4	1.2	2.5
MYO	0.6	1.0	0.1	166.7	0.6	0.8	-1.2	-0.3	1.4	1.9
NEURO	0.2	1.0	0.1	500.0	0.1	0.8	-1.5	-0.6	1.0	1.5

Table 5.35 Evaluation of the transition from a lower to a higher force level for the logarithm of the maximum power parameter, Pmax, utilising the Wilcoxon signed-ranks test. S: significant at $p < 0.05$, NS: non-significant at $p \geq 0.05$.

% MVC	NOR	MYO	NEURO
10 – 30	S	S	S
10 – 50	S	S	S
10 – 70	S	S	S
10 100	S	S	S
30 – 50	S	S	S
30 – 70	S	S	S
30 – 100	S	S	S
50 – 70	S	S	S
50 – 100	S	S	S
70 - 100	S	S	S

Table 5.36 Classification of differences between the three groups of subjects, for the Pmax parameter, utilising the Mann-Whitney test (significance level 95% ($p < 0.05$)).

NOR	MYO	NS
NOR	NEURO	NS
MYO	NEURO	NS

Figure 5.12 Histogram distribution for the logarithm of the maximum power parameter, P_{max} , for the values for all force levels 10-100% MVC for NOR, MYO and NEURO subjects.

Table 5.37 Statistics of the logarithm of total power parameter, Ptotal, for the 94 NOR subjects with respect to FL, % MVC.

% MVC	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
10	0.5	0.8	0.1	160.0	0.4	0.5	-0.7	0.0	1.0	1.9
30	1.1	0.9	0.1	81.8	1.0	0.6	-0.3	0.4	1.6	2.4
50	1.5	0.9	0.1	60.0	1.5	0.6	0.1	0.9	2.1	2.8
70	1.8	0.9	0.1	50.0	1.8	0.7	0.3	1.1	2.4	3.2
100	2.2	0.9	0.1	40.9	2.2	0.6	0.7	1.6	2.8	3.7

Table 5.38 Statistics of the logarithm of total power parameter, Ptotal for the 11 MYO subjects with respect to FL, % MVC.

% MVC	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
10	1.2	0.9	0.3	80.0	1.4	0.7	-0.3	0.4	1.8	1.9
30	1.5	0.9	0.3	60.0	1.8	0.8	0.2	0.5	2.1	2.4
50	1.8	1.0	0.3	55.6	2.0	0.9	0.2	0.9	2.6	2.8
70	1.9	1.1	0.3	57.9	2.5	1.0	0.3	0.8	2.7	2.9
100	2.4	1.1	0.3	45.8	28.0	1.0	0.3	1.2	3.2	3.5

Table 5.39 Statistics of the logarithm of the total power parameter, Ptotal, for the 9 NEURO subjects with respect to FL, % MVC.

% MVC	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
10	0.7	1.0	0.3	142.8	0.7	0.9	-0.7	-0.3	1.4	2.1
30	1.1	0.9	0.3	81.8	1.4	0.9	-0.2	0.1	1.9	2.3
50	1.4	1.0	0.3	71.4	1.7	0.8	-0.1	0.4	2.0	2.7
70	1.6	1.0	0.3	62.5	1.9	0.9	0.1	0.5	2.3	2.8
100	1.9	1.0	0.3	52.6	2.3	1.0	0.5	0.6	2.6	3.0

Figure 5.13 Descriptive box plots for the total power P_{total} parameter, for NOR, MYO (m) and NEURO (n) subjects, (a)-10%, (b)-30%, (c)-50%, (d)-70%, (e)-100% MVC and (f)-all FL values 10-100% MVC.

Table 5.40 Statistics of the values of Ptotal, for all force levels (those recorded at 10%, followed by those recorded at 30%, 50%, 70% and 100% MVC), between the three groups of subjects.

	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
NOR	1.4	1.0	0.1	71.4	1.4	0.8	-0.3	0.6	2.2	3.2
MYO	1.8	1.0	0.1	55.6	1.4	0.9	0.2	0.9	2.7	3.2
NEURO	1.4	1.0	0.2	71.4	1.4	0.9	-0.3	0.5	2.2	2.8

Table 5.41 Evaluation of the transition from a lower to a higher force level for the logarithm of total power parameter, Ptotal, utilising the Wilcoxon signed-ranks test. S: significant at $p < 0.05$, NS: non-significant at $p \geq 0.05$.

% MVC	NOR	MYO	NEURO
10 – 30	S	S	S
10 – 50	S	S	S
10 – 70	S	S	S
10 – 100	S	S	S
30 – 50	S	S	S
30 – 70	S	S	S
30 – 100	S	S	S
50 – 70	S	NS	S
50 – 100	S	S	S
70 - 100	S	S	S

Table 5.42 Classification of differences between the three groups of subjects, for the Ptotal parameter, utilising the Mann-Whitney test (significance level 95% ($p < 0.05$)).

NOR	MYO	S
NOR	NEURO	NS
MYO	NEURO	S

Figure 5.14 Histogram distribution for the logarithm of the total power parameter, P_{total} , for the values for all force levels, 10-100% MVC for NOR, MYO and NEURO subjects.

5.4 Bi-frequency domain analysis

In this section, the statistics of the bispectrum peak amplitude, B_{max} , at each force level, are given for the NOR, MYO and NEURO subjects in Tables 5.43 to 5.45 respectively. Descriptive box plots for B_{max} for the three groups are shown separately for values recorded at each force level and for all values together in Fig. 5.15. Table 5.46 tabulates the statistical analysis results for the values of B_{max} for all five-force levels together between the three groups of subjects. Table 5.47 tabulates the Wilcoxon signed-ranks test from a lower to a higher force level for the B_{max} parameter for the three groups, whereas Table 5.48 tabulates the statistical differences between the three groups. Figure 5.16 shows the histogram distribution for the three groups for the B_{max} parameter for the three groups at each force level. Tables 5.49 to 5.54 and Figs. 5.17 and 5.18 give the corresponding results and plots for the gaussianity test parameter, sg , whereas Tables 5.55 to 5.60 and Figs. 5.19 and 5.20 those of the linearity test parameter, sl . The section continues with Tables 5.61 to 5.66 and Figs. 5.21 and 5.22 those of the location of the bispectrum peak amplitude in the x-direction, B_{fx} and Tables 5.67 to 5.72 and Figs. 5.23 and 5.24, being those of the bispectrum peak amplitude in the y-direction, B_{fy} . Furthermore Tables 5.73 to 5.78 and Figs. 5.25 and 5.26 give the statistics and plots of the bispectrum peak slope in the x-direction. Finally the respective Tables and Figs. for the bispectrum slope in the y-direction are given in Tables 5.79 to 5.84 and Figs. 5.27 and 5.28.

Table 5.43 Statistics of the logarithm of the bispectrum peak amplitude parameter, Bmax, for the 94 NOR subjects with respect to FL, % MVC.

% MVC	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
10	2.0	0.8	0.1	40.0	1.9	0.4	1.1	1.6	2.3	3.1
30	2.2	1.0	0.1	45.4	2.1	0.5	1.2	1.6	2.5	3.8
50	2.3	0.9	0.1	39.1	2.1	0.5	1.2	1.7	2.6	3.7
70	2.4	0.9	0.1	37.5	2.2	0.5	1.4	1.8	2.8	3.6
100	2.5	0.9	0.1	36.0	2.4	0.5	1.5	2.0	2.9	3.7

Table 5.44 Statistics of the logarithm of the bispectrum peak amplitude parameter, Bmax, for the 11 MYO subjects with respect to FL, % MVC.

% MVC	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
10	2.2	0.6	0.2	27.3	2.2	0.3	1.4	1.8	2.4	2.9
30	2.3	0.6	0.2	26.1	2.4	0.4	1.4	1.8	2.6	3.0
50	2.4	0.8	0.2	33.3	2.3	0.5	1.1	1.9	2.8	3.1
70	2.7	0.8	0.3	29.6	2.7	0.5	1.4	2.0	3.0	3.4
100	2.7	0.7	0.2	25.9	2.9	0.5	1.6	2.2	3.1	3.3

Table 5.45 Statistics of the logarithm of the bispectrum peak amplitude parameter, Bmax, for the 9 NEURO subjects with respect to FL, % MVC.

% MVC	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
10	1.9	0.7	0.2	36.8	2.1	0.7	1.0	1.1	2.5	2.7
30	2.0	0.6	0.2	30.0	2.0	0.4	1.2	1.3	2.1	3.2
50	1.8	0.7	0.2	38.8	1.9	0.6	0.7	1.2	2.3	2.9
70	1.8	0.7	0.2	38.8	1.7	0.4	0.7	1.4	2.2	3.2
100	2.0	0.9	0.3	40.9	1.8	0.7	0.8	1.2	2.6	3.4

Figure 5.15 Descriptive box plots for the logarithm of the bispectrum peak amplitude parameter B_{max} , for NOR, MYO (m) and NEURO (n) subjects, (a)-10%, (b)-30%, (c)-50%, (d)-70%, (e)-100% MVC and (f)-all FL values.

Table 5.46 Statistics of the values for of Bmax for all force levels, (those recorded at 10%, followed by those recorded at 30%, 50%, 70% and 100% MVC), between the three groups of subjects.

	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
NOR	2.3	0.9	0.0	39.1	2.1	0.5	1.2	1.7	2.7	3.8
MYO	2.5	0.7	0.1	28.0	2.4	0.5	1.4	1.9	2.9	3.5
NEURO	1.9	0.7	0.1	36.8	1.9	0.5	0.7	1.3	2.4	3.2

Table 5.47 Evaluation of the transition from a lower to a higher force level for the logarithm of the bispectrum peak amplitude parameter, Bmax, utilising the Wilcoxon signed-ranks test. S: significant at $p < 0.05$, NS: non-significant at $p \geq 0.05$.

% MVC	NOR	MYO	NEURO
10 – 30	S	NS	NS
10 – 50	S	NS	NS
10 – 70	S	S	NS
10 – 100	S	S	NS
30 – 50	NS	NS	S
30 – 70	S	NS	S
30 – 100	S	NS	NS
50 – 70	S	S	NS
50 – 100	S	NS	NS
70 – 100	S	NS	NS

Table 5.48 Classification of differences between the three groups of subjects, for the Bmax parameter, utilising the Mann-Whitney test (significance level 95% ($p < 0.05$)).

NOR	MYO	S
NOR	NEURO	S
MYO	NEURO	S

Figure 5.16 Histogram distribution for the logarithm of the bispectrum peak amplitude parameter, B_{max} , for the values for all force levels 10-100% MVC for NOR, MYO and NEURO subjects.

Table 5.49 Statistics of the gaussianity test parameter, sg, for the 94 NOR subjects with respect to FL, % MVC.

% MVC	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
10	239.0	121.0	12.7	50.6	198.0	63.0	134.0	166.0	292.0	519.0
30	237.0	116.0	12.2	49.9	213.0	42.0	136.0	169.0	253.0	481.0
50	225.0	84.0	8.8	37.3	202.0	40.0	137.0	171.0	250.0	442.0
70	215.0	84.0	8.7	39.1	199.0	37.0	142.0	173.0	247.0	481.0
100	236.0	118.0	12.3	50.0	205.0	49.0	134.0	158.0	255.0	687.0

Table 5.50 Statistics of the gaussianity test parameter, sg, for the 11 MYO subjects with respect to FL, % MVC.

% MVC	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
10	333.0	321.0	96.8	96.4	198.0	99.0	147.0	152.0	350.0	1240.0
30	281.0	243.0	73.3	86.5	224.0	38.5	139.0	164.0	241.0	321.0
50	256.0	145.0	43.7	56.6	190.0	67.0	143.0	161.0	295.0	622.0
70	202.0	60.0	18.1	29.7	197.0	27.5	129.0	159.0	214.0	258.0
100	312.0	289.0	87.1	92.6	216.0	40.5	122.0	201.0	282.0	347.0

Table 5.51 Statistics of the gaussianity test parameter, sg, for the 9 NEURO subjects with respect to FL, % MVC.

% MVC	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
10	330.0	202.0	67.3	61.2	281.0	93.5	173.0	175.0	362.0	791.0
30	317.0	101.0	33.7	31.8	312.0	68.5	165.0	221.0	358.0	516.0
50	406.0	416.0	138.7	102.4	218.0	34.0	166.0	173.0	241.0	1317.0
70	353.0	292.0	97.3	82.7	254.0	91.5	155.0	165.0	348.0	1093.0
100	266.0	143.0	47.7	53.7	218.0	90.0	147.0	149.0	329.0	603.0

Figure 5.17 Descriptive box plots for the gaussianity test parameter sg , for NOR, MYO (m) and NEURO (n) subjects, (a)-10%, (b)-30%, (c)-50%, (d)-70%, (e)-100% MVC and (f)-all FL values.

Table 5.52 Statistics of the values of sg for all force levels (those recorded at 10%, followed by those recorded at 30%, 50%, 70% and 100% MVC), between the three groups of subjects.

	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
NOR	232.0	106.0	5.0	45.7	203.0	43.5	136.0	169.0	256.0	508.0
MYO	277.0	228.0	30.7	82.3	207.0	55.0	139.0	163.0	273.0	622.0
NEURO	334.0	249.0	37.1	74.6	249.0	85.0	149.0	178.0	348.0	918.0

Table 5.53 Evaluation of the transition from a lower to a higher force level for the gaussianity test parameter, sg, utilising the Wilcoxon signed-ranks test. S: significant at $p < 0.05$, NS: non-significant at $p \geq 0.05$.

% MVC	NOR	MYO	NEURO
10 – 30	NS	NS	NS
10 – 50	NS	NS	NS
10 – 70	NS	NS	NS
10 100	NS	NS	NS
30 – 50	NS	NS	NS
30 – 70	NS	NS	NS
30 – 100	NS	NS	NS
50 – 70	NS	NS	NS
50 – 100	NS	NS	NS
70 - 100	NS	NS	NS

Table 5.54 Classification of differences between the three groups of subjects, for the sg parameter utilising the Mann-Whitney test (significance level 95% ($p < 0.05$)).

NOR	MYO	NS
NOR	NEURO	S
MYO	NEURO	S

Figure 5.18 Histogram distribution for the gaussianity test parameter, sg , for the values for all force levels 10-100% MVC for NOR, MYO and NEURO subjects.

Table 5.55 Statistics of the linearity test parameter, sl, for the 94 NOR subjects with respect to FL, % MVC.

% MVC	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
10	1.6	1.6	0.2	100.0	1.1	0.5	0.2	0.7	1.6	5.1
30	1.7	1.4	0.2	82.3	1.3	1.0	0.3	0.7	2.6	3.5
50	1.6	1.5	0.2	93.8	1.2	0.7	0.1	0.6	2.0	4.1
70	1.4	1.5	0.2	107.1	1.1	0.5	0.1	0.6	1.6	3.9
100	2.0	4.2	0.4	210.0	1.2	0.7	0.2	0.8	2.1	4.6

Table 5.56 Statistics of the linearity test parameter, sl, for the 11 MYO subjects with respect to FL, % MVC.

% MVC	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
10	1.4	2.8	0.9	200.0	1.1	0.6	0.5	0.6	1.7	4.8
30	1.5	8.3	2.5	533.3	1.6	0.7	0.4	0.4	1.7	2.2
50	1.3	14.7	4.4	1130.7	1.0	0.2	0.4	0.7	1.1	3.6
70	1.0	20.8	6.3	2080.0	1.0	0.6	0.2	0.3	1.4	1.6
100	1.6	29.7	9.0	1856.3	1.0	0.7	0.2	0.3	1.8	7.1

Table 5.57 Statistics of the linearity test parameter, sl, for the 9 NEURO subjects with respect to FL, % MVC.

% MVC	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
10	2.2	1.8	0.6	81.8	1.6	0.9	0.2	0.9	2.7	6.1
30	1.6	0.9	0.3	56.3	1.3	0.4	0.7	1.0	1.8	3.4
50	2.6	4.1	1.4	157.7	1.0	0.6	0.3	0.6	1.7	13.1
70	1.6	1.2	0.4	75.0	1.3	0.6	0.3	0.6	1.9	3.4
100	1.7	2.0	0.7	117.6	0.6	1.8	0.2	0.2	3.7	4.9

Figure 5.19 Descriptive box plots for the linearity test parameter, sl , for NOR, MYO (m) and NEURO (n) subjects, (a)-10%, (b)-30%, (c)-50%, (d)-70%, (e)-100% MVC and (f)-all FL values.

Table 5.58 Statistics of the values of sl, for all force levels (those recorded at 10%, followed by those recorded at 30%, 50%, 70% and 100% MVC), between the three groups of subjects.

	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
NOR	1.6	2.2	0.1	137.5	1.3	0.6	0.2	0.7	1.9	4.0
MYO	1.4	1.2	0.2	85.7	1.1	0.5	0.3	0.7	1.6	3.6
NEURO	1.9	2.2	0.3	115.8	1.2	0.8	0.2	0.7	2.2	4.9

Table 5.59 Evaluation of the transition from a lower to a higher force level for the linearity test parameter, sl, utilising the Wilcoxon signed-ranks test. S: significant at $p < 0.05$, NS: non-significant at $p \geq 0.05$.

% MVC	NOR	MYO	NEURO
10 – 30	NS	NS	NS
10 – 50	NS	NS	NS
10 – 70	NS	NS	NS
10 100	NS	NS	NS
30 – 50	NS	NS	NS
30 – 70	NS	NS	NS
30 – 100	NS	NS	NS
50 – 70	NS	NS	NS
50 – 100	NS	NS	NS
70 – 100	S	NS	NS

Table 5.60 Classification of differences between the three groups of subjects, for the sl parameter, utilising the Mann-Whitney test (significance level 95% ($p < 0.05$)).

NOR	MYO	NS
NOR	NEURO	NS
MYO	NEURO	NS

Figure 5.20 Histogram distribution for the linearity test parameter, sl , for the values for all force levels 10-100% MVC for NOR, MYO and NEURO subjects.

Table 5.61 Statistics of the parameter for the location of the bispectrum peak amplitude in the x-direction, Bfx, for the 94 NOR subjects with respect to FL, % MVC.

% MVC	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
10	54.0	26.0	2.7	48.0	52.0	7.0	33.0	45.0	59.0	69.0
30	57.0	30.0	3.1	53.0	52.0	7.0	33.0	46.0	60.0	80.0
50	53.0	11.0	1.2	21.0	53.0	6.5	29.0	46.0	59.0	70.0
70	55.0	13.0	1.4	24.0	53.0	6.0	35.0	48.0	60.0	75.0
100	55.0	13.0	1.4	24.0	54.0	6.0	41.0	48.0	60.0	71.0

Table 5.62 Statistics of the parameter for the location of the bispectrum peak amplitude in the x-direction, Bfx, for the 11 MYO subjects with respect to FL, % MVC.

% MVC	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
10	63.0	29.3	8.8	47.0	53.0	4.5	32.0	48.0	57.0	93.0
30	60.0	20.5	6.2	34.0	54.0	8.0	38.0	47.0	63.0	90.0
50	57.0	13.9	4.2	24.0	53.0	5.5	42.0	49.0	60.0	64.0
70	55.0	9.7	2.9	18.0	53.0	4.5	42.0	48.0	57.0	64.0
100	53.0	9.0	2.7	17.0	51.0	4.5	43.0	45.0	54.0	68.0

Table 5.63 Statistics of the parameter for the location of the bispectrum peak amplitude in the x-direction, Bfx, for the 9 NEURO subjects with respect to FL, % MVC.

% MVC	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
10	55.0	6.6	2.2	12.0	52.0	4.5	46.0	49.0	58.0	65.0
30	58.0	10.2	3.4	17.6	55.0	7.5	43.0	51.0	66.0	76.0
50	71.0	41.1	13.7	57.9	57.0	7.5	44.0	46.0	61.0	172.0
70	70.0	29.0	9.7	41.4	59.0	8.0	43.0	52.0	76.0	141.0
100	71.0	39.6	13.2	55.8	60.0	12.5	36.0	48.0	73.0	169.0

Figure 5.21 Descriptive box plots for the location of the bispectrum peak in the x-direction Bfx parameter, for NOR, MYO (m) and NEURO (n) subjects, (a)-10%, (b)-30%, (c)-50%, (d)-70%, (e)-100% MVC and (f)-all FL values.

Table 5.64 Statistics of the values of Bfx for all force levels (those recorded at 10%, followed by those recorded at 30%, 50%, 70% and 100% MVC), between the three groups of subjects.

	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
NOR	55.0	20.0	1.0	36.4	53.0	6.5	34.0	47.0	60.0	74.0
MYO	58.0	17.8	2.4	30.7	53.0	7.5	38.0	48.0	63.0	93.0
NEURO	65.0	28.7	4.3	44.1	57.0	7.5	43.0	51.0	66.0	141.0

Table 5.65 Evaluation of the transition from a lower to a higher force level of the parameter for the location of the bispectrum peak amplitude in the x-direction Bfx, utilising the Wilcoxon signed-ranks test. S: significant at $p < 0.05$, NS: non-significant at $p \geq 0.05$.

	NOR	MYO	NEURO
10 – 30	NS	NS	NS
10 – 50	NS	NS	NS
10 – 70	NS	NS	NS
10 – 100	NS	NS	NS
30 – 50	NS	NS	NS
30 – 70	NS	NS	S
30 – 100	NS	NS	NS
50 – 70	NS	NS	NS
50 – 100	NS	NS	NS
70 - 100	NS	NS	NS

Table 5.66 Classification of differences between the three groups of subjects, for the Bfx parameter, utilising the Mann-Whitney test (significance level 95% ($p < 0.05$)).

NOR	MYO	NS
NOR	NEURO	S
MYO	NEURO	NS

Figure 5.22 Histogram distribution of the parameter for the location of the bispectrum peak in the x-direction, B_{fx} , for the values for all force levels 10-100% MVC for NOR, MYO and NEURO subjects.

Table 5.67 Statistics for the parameter of the location of the bispectrum peak amplitude in the y-direction, Bfy, for the 94 NOR subjects with respect to FL, % MVC.

% MVC	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
10	37.0	24.0	2.5	64.8	47.0	17.5	0.0	22.0	57.0	64.0
30	40.0	24.0	2.5	60.0	48.0	18.0	0.0	21.0	57.0	70.0
50	39.0	24.0	2.5	61.5	47.0	16.5	0.0	24.0	57.0	66.0
70	40.0	26.0	2.7	65.0	49.0	18.0	0.0	22.0	58.0	68.0
100	39.0	24.0	2.5	61.5	47.0	17.5	0.0	22.0	57.0	66.0

Table 5.68 Statistics for the parameter of the location of the bispectrum peak amplitude in the y-direction, Bfy, for the 11 MYO subjects with respect to FL, % MVC.

% MVC	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
10	47.0	20.0	6.0	42.5	53.0	8.0	11.0	40.0	56.0	58.0
30	43.0	30.4	9.2	70.7	47.0	17.5	0.0	19.0	54.0	84.0
50	38.0	27.4	8.3	72.1	53.0	29.5	0.0	0.0	59.0	64.0
70	38.0	26.4	8.0	69.5	45.0	27.5	0.0	19.0	54.0	64.0
100	42.0	19.3	5.8	45.9	49.0	16.0	20.0	21.0	53.0	68.0

Table 5.69 Statistics for the parameter of the location of the bispectrum peak amplitude in the y-direction, Bfy, for the 9 NEURO subjects with respect to FL, % MVC.

% MVC	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
10	44.0	22.5	7.5	51.1	51.0	17.5	0.0	23.0	58.0	64.0
30	49.0	23.6	7.9	48.2	55.0	21.5	0.0	23.0	66.0	73.0
50	55.0	38.1	12.7	69.3	54.0	15.0	0.0	30.0	60.0	143.0
70	54.0	25.3	8.4	46.9	58.0	26.5	19.0	23.0	76.0	82.0
100	50.0	26.0	8.7	52.0	60.0	24.0	0.0	23.0	71.0	77.0

Figure 5.23 Descriptive box plots for the location of the bispectrum peak amplitude in the y-direction Bfy parameter, for NOR, MYO (m) and NEURO (n) subjects, (a)-10%, (b)-30%, (c)-50%, (d)-70%, (e)-100% MVC and (f)-all FL values.

Table 5.70 Statistics of the values of Bfy, for all force levels (those recorded at 10%, followed by those recorded at 30%, 50%, 70% and 100% MVC), between the three groups of subjects.

	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
NOR	39.0	24.0	1.1	61.5	48.0	18.0	0.0	22.0	58.0	68.0
MYO	42.0	24.0	3.3	57.1	48.0	17.5	0.0	21.0	56.0	76.0
NEURO	50.0	27.0	4.0	54.0	56.0	19.0	0.0	26.0	64.0	82.0

Table 5.71 Evaluation of the transition from a lower to a higher force level for the parameter of the location of the bispectrum peak amplitude in the y-direction, Bfy, utilising the Wilcoxon signed-ranks test. S: significant at $p < 0.05$, NS: non-significant at $p \geq 0.05$.

% MVC	NOR	MYO	NEURO
10 – 30	NS	NS	NS
10 – 50	NS	NS	NS
10 – 70	NS	NS	S
10 – 100	NS	NS	S
30 – 50	NS	NS	NS
30 – 70	NS	NS	NS
30 – 100	NS	NS	S
50 – 70	NS	NS	NS
50 – 100	NS	NS	NS
70 – 100	NS	NS	NS

Table 5.72 Classification of differences between the three groups of subjects, for the Bfy parameter, utilising the Mann-Whitney test (significance level 95% ($p < 0.05$)).

NOR	MYO	NS
NOR	NEURO	S
MYO	NEURO	NS

Figure 5.24 Histogram distribution for the parameter of the bispectrum peak location in the y-direction, B_{fy} , for the values for all force levels 10-100% MVC for NOR, MYO and NEURO subjects.

Table 5.73 Statistics for the parameter of the slope of the bispectrum peak in the x-direction, Bfxslope, for the 94 NOR subjects with respect to FL, % MVC.

% MVC	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
10	60.0	25.0	2.6	41.6	57.0	15.5	24.0	40.0	71.0	104.0
30	58.0	24.0	2.5	41.3	56.0	15.0	23.0	41.0	71.0	102.0
50	56.0	23.0	2.4	41.1	54.0	15.5	23.0	42.0	73.0	86.0
70	54.0	22.0	2.3	41.1	53.0	17.0	24.0	37.0	71.0	88.0
100	51.0	20.0	2.1	39.2	49.0	16.0	22.0	37.0	69.0	79.0

Table 5.74 Statistics for the parameter of the slope of the bispectrum peak in the x-direction, Bfxslope, for the 11 MYO subjects with respect to FL, % MVC.

% MVC	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
10	60.0	21.3	6.4	35.5	60.0	12.0	25.0	48.0	72.0	78.0
30	61.0	30.1	9.1	49.3	57.0	17.0	25.0	33.0	67.0	96.0
50	59.0	26.5	8.0	44.9	58.0	23.0	24.0	29.0	75.0	96.0
70	54.0	23.3	7.0	43.1	52.0	19.0	25.0	36.0	74.0	80.0
100	56.0	21.9	6.6	39.1	48.0	19.0	28.0	37.0	75.0	83.0

Table 5.75 Statistics for the parameter of the slope of the bispectrum peak in the x-direction, Bfxslope, for the 9 NEURO subjects with respect to FL, % MVC.

% MVC	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
10	70.0	30.5	10.2	43.4	68.0	27.0	24.0	32.0	86.0	111.0
30	66.0	24.0	8.0	36.4	64.0	19.5	29.0	39.0	78.0	107.0
50	75.0	40.0	13.3	53.3	62.0	52.0	27.0	34.0	86.0	160.0
70	74.0	31.0	10.3	41.9	78.0	22.5	26.0	47.0	92.0	128.0
100	69.0	31.5	10.5	45.6	66.0	21.5	19.0	45.0	88.0	124.0

Figure 5.25 Descriptive box plots for the slope of the bispectrum peak amplitude in the x-direction Bfxslope parameter, for NOR, MYO (m) and NEURO (n) subjects, (a)-10%, (b)-30%, (c)-50%, (d)-70%, (e)-100% MVC and (f)-all FL values.

Table 5.76 Statistics of the values of Bfxslope, for all force levels (those recorded at 10%, followed by those recorded at 30%, 50%, 70% and 100% MVC), between the three groups of subjects.

	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
NOR	56.0	23.0	1.1	41.1	54.0	15.5	23.0	39.0	70.0	98.0
MYO	58.0	24.0	3.2	41.3	57.0	19.0	25.0	37.0	75.0	96.0
NEURO	71.0	30.4	4.5	42.8	66.0	19.5	24.0	49.0	88.0	124.0

Table 5.77 Evaluation of the transition from a lower to a higher force level for the parameter of the slope of the bispectrum peak in the x direction, Bfxslope, utilising the Wilcoxon signed-ranks test. S: significant at $p < 0.05$, NS: non-significant at $p \geq 0.05$.

% MVC	NOR	MYO	NEURO
10 – 30	NS	NS	NS
10 – 50	NS	NS	NS
10 – 70	NS	NS	NS
10 – 100	NS	NS	NS
30 – 50	NS	NS	NS
30 – 70	NS	NS	NS
30 – 100	NS	NS	NS
50 – 70	NS	NS	NS
50 – 100	NS	NS	NS
70 – 100	NS	NS	NS

Table 5.78 Classification of differences between the three groups of subjects, for the Bfxslope parameter, utilising the Mann-Whitney test (significance level 95% ($p < 0.05$)).

NOR	MYO	NS
NOR	NEURO	S
MYO	NEURO	S

Figure 5.26 Histogram distribution for the parameter of the bispectrum peak slope in the x-direction, Bfxslope, for the values for all force levels 10-100% MVC for NOR, MYO and NEURO subjects.

Table 5.79 Statistics for the parameter of the slope of the bispectrum peak in the y-direction, Bfyslope, for the 94 NOR subjects with respect to FL, % MVC.

% MVC	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
10	13.0	5.4	0.6	41.5	12.0	3.0	6.0	10.0	16.0	23.0
30	14.0	5.4	0.6	38.6	14.0	3.0	6.0	10.0	16.0	23.0
50	13.0	4.7	0.5	36.1	13.0	3.0	6.0	10.0	16.0	22.0
70	14.0	5.3	0.6	37.9	13.0	2.5	7.0	11.0	16.0	21.0
100	14.0	5.3	0.6	37.9	13.0	3.0	7.0	10.0	16.0	22.0

Table 5.80 Statistics for the parameter of the slope of the bispectrum peak in the y-direction, Bfyslope, for the 11 MYO subjects with respect to FL, % MVC.

% MVC	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
10	18.0	9.6	2.9	53.3	15.0	6.0	7.0	11.0	23.0	34.0
30	18.0	10.7	3.2	59.4	13.0	3.0	10.0	11.0	17.0	37.0
50	16.0	7.6	2.3	47.5	14.0	2.0	9.0	11.0	15.0	28.0
70	16.0	5.7	1.7	35.6	14.0	3.5	10.0	11.0	18.0	22.0
100	15.0	6.7	2.0	44.7	12.0	2.0	9.0	11.0	15.0	23.0

Table 5.81 Statistics for the parameter of the slope of the bispectrum peak in the y-direction, Bfyslope, for the 9 NEURO subjects with respect to FL, % MVC.

% MVC	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
10	16.0	6.3	2.1	39.4	17.0	6.0	7.0	9.0	21.0	24.0
30	16.0	5.8	1.9	36.3	16.0	5.0	8.0	11.0	21.0	26.0
50	21.0	16.4	5.5	78.1	16.0	6.5	7.0	7.0	20.0	60.0
70	21.0	12.7	4.2	60.5	18.0	7.0	8.0	9.0	23.0	51.0
100	20.0	14.5	4.8	72.5	18.0	7.5	6.0	9.0	24.0	55.0

Figure 5.27 Descriptive box plots for the slope of the bispectrum peak amplitude in the y-direction parameter Bfyslope, for NOR, MYO (m) and NEURO (n) subjects, (a)-10%, (b)-30%, (c)-50%, (d)-70%, (e)-100% MVC and (f)-all FL values.

Table 5.82 Statistics of the values of Bfyslope for all force levels, (those recorded at 10%, followed by those recorded at 30%, 50%, 70% and 100% MVC), between the three groups of subjects.

	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
NOR	13.7	5.2	0.2	38.0	13.0	3.0	7.0	10.0	16.0	22.0
MYO	16.6	8.1	1.1	48.8	14.4	5.0	9.0	11.0	21.0	34.0
NEURO	18.8	12.0	1.7	63.8	17.0	5.5	7.0	11.0	22.0	51.0

Table 5.83 Evaluation of the transition from a lower to a higher force level for the parameter of the slope of the bispectrum peak in the y direction, Bfyslope, utilising the Wilcoxon signed-ranks test. S: significant at $p < 0.05$, NS: non-significant at $p \geq 0.05$.

% MVC	NOR	MYO	NEURO
10 – 30	NS	NS	NS
10 – 50	NS	NS	NS
10 – 70	NS	NS	NS
10 – 100	NS	NS	NS
30 – 50	NS	NS	NS
30 – 70	NS	NS	NS
30 – 100	NS	NS	NS
50 – 70	NS	NS	NS
50 – 100	NS	NS	NS
70 – 100	NS	NS	NS

Table 5.84 Classification of differences between the three groups of subjects, for the Bfyslope parameter, utilising the Mann-Whitney test (significance level 95% ($p < 0.05$)).

NOR	MYO	NS
NOR	NEURO	S
MYO	NEURO	NS

Figure 5.28 Histogram distribution for the parameter of the bispectrum peak slope in the y-direction, Bfyslope, for the values for all force levels 10-100% MVC for NOR, MYO and NEURO subjects.

5.5 Repeatability of measurements

In this section repeatability measurements for subject NK (female, 46 years old) are presented. Table 5.85 classifies the repeatability results between sets of data, whereas Table 5.86 gives a statistical analysis of all parameters at all five force levels (14 x 5 values). Descriptive box-plots give a representation of these 70 values, Fig. 5.29, whereas Figs. 5.30 to 5.33, give the mean values \pm standard error of the mean of the repeated measurements for the turns per second, median frequency, total power and bispectrum peak amplitude respectively. Finally Table 5.87 gives a statistical analysis including the standard deviation, the standard error of the mean and the coefficient of variation for these four selected parameters at the five force levels.

Table 5.85 Classification of repeatability measurements for subject NK.

Recordings	P-Value between the two sets	Significance Level S/NS
1 st - 2 nd	0.2	NS
1 st - 3 rd	0.3	NS
1 st - 4 th	0.4	NS
2 nd - 3 rd	0.5	NS
2 nd - 4 th	0.1	NS
3 rd - 4 th	0.8	NS

Table 5.86 Statistical analysis for the repeatability measurements analysis for subject NK.

SUBJECT NK	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
1 st effort	62.5	61.8	7.4	98.9	51.0	57.9	0.1	2.0	116.0	163.0
2 nd effort	63.8	58.9	7.0	92.3	60.0	48.0	0.1	3.0	98.0	180.0
3 rd effort	63.7	60.5	7.2	94.9	57.5	47.0	0.1	2.1	96.0	184.0
4 th effort	65.3	62.3	7.4	95.4	62.5	52.0	0.0	2.6	106.0	176.0

Figure 5.29 Descriptive box plots representing the 70 values recorded each time.

Figure 5.30 Mean \pm SEM of repeated measurements for the turns per second parameter at the five force levels, FLs. (Mean is represented with the black box and the lines extended represent the \pm SEM)

Figure 5.31 Mean \pm SEM of repeated measurements for the median frequency parameter at the five FLs.

Figure 5.32 Mean \pm SEM of repeated measurements for the total power parameter at the five FLs.

Figure 5.33 Mean \pm SEM of repeated measurements for the bispectrum peak amplitude at the five FLs.

Table 5.87 Standard deviation, SD, standard error of the mean, SEM and coefficient of variation, CV, values for the repeatability measurements at the five force levels.

%MVC	t/s			P _{med}			P _{total}			B _{max}		
	SD	SEM	%CV	SD	SEM	%CV	SD	SEM	%CV	SD	SEM	%CV
10	1.7	0.9	115.0	14.7	7.4	12.0	0.01	0.005	17.0	37.8	18.9	67.0
30	6.2	3.1	67.0	15.9	7.9	15.0	0.07	0.04	98.0	34.9	11.5	32.0
50	9.1	4.5	32.0	6.7	3.4	6.0	0.12	0.06	97.0	18.5	9.3	20.0
70	11.2	5.6	33.0	4.8	2.4	4.0	0.24	0.12	99.0	35.7	17.9	38.0
100	5.8	2.9	11.0	5.9	2.9	6.0	0.22	0.11	77.0	45.2	22.6	34.0

5.6 Reliability of measurements

The objective of these measurements was to investigate if significant differences existed between two sets of recordings after a time interval and if recordings taken from a low force level going up to a high force level or vice-versa presented significant differences. Table 5.88 tabulates information for the ten participating subjects, including subject's code, age, gender, the time elapsed between the two decreasing recordings, p-value between the two force decreasing efforts, p-value between decreasing and increasing efforts and whether these were classified as having significant differences or not. Table 5.89 lists the statistical analysis for all ten participated subjects for the three sets of data (two decreasing efforts and one increasing). Values are listed for all parameters at the five force levels (14 parameters at five force levels). Figs. 5.34 to 5.37 plot the mean \pm standard error of the mean for the ten subjects for the turns per second, the median frequency the total power and the bispectrum peak amplitude respectively.

Table 5.88 Classification of reliability measurements for the ten normal subjects.

Item	Subject's Code	Age in years	Gender M/F	Time elapsed between the two decreasing recordings	P-Value between the two decreasing efforts	Significance Level S/NS	P-Value between the decreasing and increasing efforts	Significance Level S/NS
1	GP	25	M	12 months	<0.01	S	0.27	NS
2	NN	35	M	48 hours	0.38	NS	0.47	NS
3	DK	37	M	24 hours	0.16	NS	0.44	NS
4	PP	44	M	24 months	0.82	NS	0.93	NS
5	SV	48	M	15 months	0.82	NS	0.81	NS
6	ACK	55	M	13 months	0.16	NS	0.61	NS
7	SK	57	M	15 months	0.02	S	0.02	S
8	MV	35	F	21 months	0.67	NS	0.02	S
9	NK	45	F	24 months	0.65	NS	0.51	NS
10	TI	53	F	24 months	0.31	NS	0.11	NS

Table 5.89 Statistical analysis for the reliability measurements analysis for the ten normal subjects.

SUBJECT GP	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
1 st decreasing effort	29.1	32.4	3.9	111.3	13.6	21.9	0.9	2.3	46.0	101.1
2 nd decreasing effort	24.6	33.9	4.1	137.8	6.0	19.8	0.0	1.4	41.0	98.0
Increasing effort	25.0	33.3	4.0	133.2	6.0	18.7	0.0	1.7	39.0	96.0

SUBJECT NN	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
1 st decreasing effort	34.7	40.1	4.8	115.6	11.5	28.4	0.4	2.2	59.0	122.0
2 nd decreasing effort	31.8	41.6	4.9	130.8	7.5	26.2	0.0	1.7	54.0	129.0
Increasing effort	32.7	44.0	5.3	134.6	7.0	25.3	0.0	1.5	52.0	136.0

SUBJECT DK	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
1 st decreasing effort	40.0	53.5	6.4	134.0	7.5	39.2	-0.2	1.6	80.0	152.0
2 nd decreasing effort	41.4	41.4	5.0	100.0	36.5	29.4	1.1	2.2	61.0	129.0
Increasing effort	40.7	41.6	4.9	102.2	37.5	27.4	0.8	2.2	57.0	132

SUBJECT PP	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
1 st decreasing effort	37.0	46.8	5.6	126.6	18.0	31.9	-7.2	2.1	66.0	137.0
2 nd decreasing effort	29.7	35.5	4.2	123.2	16.0	22.9	-6.9	2.3	48.0	105.0
Increasing effort	27.5	38.0	4.5	138.2	6.0	21.8	-6.4	1.4	45.0	114.0

SUBJECT SV	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
1 st decreasing effort	43.8	53.1	6.3	113.2	16.0	62.5	0.0	1.8	83.0	146.0
2 nd decreasing effort	64.4	125.8	15.0	195.3	23.5	43.8	0.8	2.5	90.0	410.0
Increasing effort	62.0	134.9	16.1	217.6	21.7	39.9	0.6	2.3	80.0	463

Table 5.89 Continued

SUBJECT ACK	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
1 st decreasing effort	37.6	47.9	5.7	127.4	7.7	35.6	0.0	1.9	73.0	135
2 nd decreasing effort	34.9	46.9	5.6	134.4	8.5	27.0	-0.1	1.0	55.0	144.0
Increasing effort	35.3	46.5	5.6	131.7	9.0	24.4	0.0	1.1	50.0	139.0

SUBJECT SK	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
1 st decreasing effort	37.1	43.9	5.3	118.3	11.0	30.1	0.0	1.7	62.0	127.0
2 nd decreasing effort	29.6	33.6	4.0	113.5	13.6	23.3	0.2	2.4	49.0	98.0
Increasing effort	30.9	34.4	4.1	111.3	11.9	23.8	0.3	2.4	50.0	102.0

SUBJECT MV	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
1 st decreasing effort	42.6	45.6	5.6	107.0	21.0	41.5	0.0	1.0	84.0	131.0
2 nd decreasing effort	28.8	35.5	4.2	123.2	16.0	22.9	-6.9	-2.3	48.0	105.0
Increasing effort	23.6	32.9	3.9	139.4	7.0	20.0	-7.7	1.0	41.0	98.0

SUBJECT NK	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
1 st decreasing effort	45.4	45.0	5.4	82.7	31.0	37.9	0.8	2.3	78.0	140.0
2 nd decreasing effort	49.3	61.7	7.4	125.1	14.0	35.9	0.2	1.2	73.0	186.0
Increasing effort	50.0	62.3	7.4	124.6	14.2	36.0	0.0	1.0	73.0	188.0

SUBJECT TI	Mean	SD	SEM	% CV	Median	SIQR	P _{5%}	P _{25%}	P _{75%}	P _{95%}
1 st decreasing effort	35.2	46.2	5.5	131.2	9.2	24.7	0.0	1.7	51.0	147.0
2 nd decreasing effort	34.4	48.4	5.8	140.7	8.0	24.3	0.0	1.4	50.0	152.0
Increasing effort	35.4	48.2	5.8	136.2	8.0	25.2	0.1	1.6	52.0	143.0

Figure 5.34 Mean \pm SEM for the turns per second parameter for the ten normal subjects.

Figure 5.35 Mean \pm SEM for median frequency parameter for the ten normal subjects.

Figure 5.36 Mean ± SEM for total power parameter for the ten normal subjects.

Figure 5.37 Mean \pm SEM for bispectrum peak amplitude parameter for the ten normal subjects.

5.7 Age and gender analysis

The age and gender analysis was based on: (i) the Wilcoxon sign-ranks test (ii) the coefficient of variation and (iii) continuous descriptive analysis. The latter was performed only on selected parameters. One parameter from the time domain, two from the frequency domain and one from the bi-frequency domain. All four parameters were significantly influenced with force level.

5.7.1 Age analysis based on Wilcoxon sign rank test

Table 5.90 classifies the transition from 10 to 50% of MVC for all 14 parameters as significant or non-significant for all 94 subjects and then for subjects based on age decades, using the Wilcoxon signed –rank test. Tables 5.91 and 5.92 present the differences for force transitions 50 to 100% and 10 to 100% MVC respectively.

Table 5.90 Evaluation of the transition from 10 to 50% of MVC based on age using the Wilcoxon signed-ranks test (S: significant, S, ($p < 0.05$), NS: non-significant, NS, ($p \geq 0.05$)).

PARAMETER	ALL 94	12	12	20	15	12	13	10
	SUBJECTS							
		AGED						
		< 9	10-19	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60-69
t/s	S	NS	S	S	S	S	S	S
zc/s	S	NS	NS	S	S	S	S	NS
Pfmed	S	NS	NS	NS	NS	S	S	S
Pfmean	S	S	S	S	NS	S	NS	S
Pfx	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	S	NS
Pmax	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
Ptotal	S	S	S	S	NS	S	S	S
Bmax	S	S	NS	S	NS	S	NS	S
sg	NS	NS	NS	NS	S	NS	NS	S
sl	NS	S						
Bfx	NS							
Bfy	NS							
Bfxslope	S	S	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	S
Bfyslope	S	NS						

Table 5.91 Evaluation of the transition from 50 to 100% of MVC based on age using the Wilcoxon signed-ranks test (S: significant, S, ($p < 0.05$), NS: non-significant, NS, ($p \geq 0.05$).

PARAMETER	ALL SUBJECTS	SUBJECTS AGED < 9	SUBJECTS AGED 10-19	SUBJECTS AGED 20-29	SUBJECTS AGED 30-39	SUBJECTS AGED 40-49	SUBJECTS AGED 50-59	SUBJECTS AGED 60-69
t/s	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
zc/s	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	NS
Pfmed	S	NS	NS	NS	S	NS	S	NS
Pfmean	S	S	S	NS	S	NS	S	S
Pfx	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
Pmax	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
Ptotal	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
Bmax	S	NS	S	NS	S	NS	S	NS
sg	NS	NS	NS	S	NS	NS	NS	NS
sl	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	S
Bfx	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
Bfy	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
Bfxslope	S	NS	NS	S	NS	NS	S	NS
Bfyslope	S	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS

Table 5.92 Evaluation of the transition from 10 to 100% of MVC based on age using the Wilcoxon signed-ranks test (S: significant, S, ($p < 0.05$), NS: non-significant, NS, ($p \geq 0.05$).

PARAMETER	ALL SUBJECTS	SUBJECTS AGED < 9	SUBJECTS AGED 10-19	SUBJECTS AGED 20-29	SUBJECTS AGED 30-39	SUBJECTS AGED 40-49	SUBJECTS AGED 50-59	SUBJECTS AGED 60-69
t/s	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
zc/s	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
Pfmed	S	S	NS	NS	S	S	S	S
Pfmean	S	S	S	S	NS	S	S	S
Pfx	NS	NS	S	S	NS	S	NS	NS
Pmax	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
Ptotal	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
Bmax	S	S	NS	S	S	S	NS	S
sg	NS	NS	NS	S	NS	NS	NS	S
sl	NS	NS	NS	S	NS	NS	NS	S
Bfx	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
Bfy	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
Bfxslope	S	S	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
Bfyslope	S	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS

5.7.2 Analysis of age based on coefficient of variation

Tables 5.93 to 5.106 tabulate the average values, the standard deviation, the percentage coefficient of variation and the standard error of the mean values for the fourteen parameters investigated followed by Figs. 5.38 to 5.51 giving the corresponding graphs of the percentage coefficient of variation with age decade.

Table 5.93 Mean, standard deviation, SD, percentage coefficient of variation, CV, and standard error of the mean, SEM values for the turns per second parameter t/s based on subject's age.

	<9	10-19	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60-69
mean	17.0	16.0	16.0	19.0	17.0	17.0	16.0
SD	14.0	13.0	12.0	14.0	12.0	14.0	17.0
CV	82.3	81.3	75.0	73.6	70.6	82.3	106.3
SEM	1.80	1.70	1.20	1.60	1.50	1.80	2.40

Figure 5.38 The influence of force on the percentage CV for the turns per second parameter, t/s, based on subject's age.

Table 5.94 Mean, standard deviation, SD, percentage coefficient of variation, CV and standard error of the mean, SEM, values for the zero crossings per second parameter z/s, based on subject's age.

	<9	10-19	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60-69
mean	11.0	12.0	12.0	13.0	12.0	12.0	12.0
SD	12.0	12.0	11.0	12.0	11.0	13.0	14.0
CV	109.1	100.0	91.6	92.3	91.6	108.3	116.7
SEM	1.50	1.50	1.10	1.40	1.40	1.70	1.90

Figure 5.39 The influence of force on the percentage CV for the zero crossings per second parameter z/s based on subject's age.

Table 5.95 Mean, standard deviation, SD, percentage coefficient of variation, CV and standard error of the mean, SEM, values for the median frequency parameter P_{fmed}, based on subject's age.

	<9	10-19	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60-69
mean	95.0	100.0	98.0	97.0	102.0	119.0	107.0
SD	23.0	21.5	16.0	21.0	19.0	31.0	23.0
CV	24.2	21.5	16.3	21.6	18.6	26.0	21.5
SEM	2.90	2.80	1.60	2.40	2.10	4.00	3.30

Figure 5.40 The influence of force on the percentage CV for the median frequency parameter P_{fmed}, based on subject's age.

Table 5.96 Mean, standard deviation, SD, percentage coefficient of variation, CV and standard error of the mean, SEM, values for the mean frequency parameter P_{fmean}, based on subject's age.

	<9	10-19	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60-69
mean	122.0	121.0	114.0	121.0	110.0	142.0	130.0
SD	25.0	23.0	26.0	23.0	32.0	34.0	28.0
CV	20.5	19.0	22.8	19.0	29.0	23.9	21.5
SEM	3.20	3.00	2.60	2.60	4.10	4.40	3.90

Figure 5.41 The influence of force on the percentage CV for the mean frequency parameter P_{fmean}, based on subject's age.

Table 5.97 Mean, standard deviation, SD, percentage coefficient of variation, CV and standard error of the mean, SEM, values for the frequency at maximum power parameter P_{fx}, based on subject's age.

	<9	10-19	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60-69
mean	81.0	72.0	75.0	74.0	79.0	92.0	80.0
SD	21.0	18.0	17.0	15.0	25.0	23.0	19.0
CV	25.9	25.0	22.6	20.3	31.6	25.0	23.8
SEM	2.70	2.30	1.70	1.70	3.20	3.00	2.70

Figure 5.42 The influence of force on the percentage CV for the frequency at maximum power parameter P_{fx}, based on subject's age.

Table 5.98 Mean, standard deviation, SD, percentage coefficient of variation, CV, and standard error of the mean, SEM, values for the log of the maximum power parameter Pmax, based on subject's age.

	<9	10-19	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60-69
mean	0.1	0.1	0.7	0.8	0.7	0.3	0.2
SD	0.9	1.0	1.0	1.3	1.2	0.9	1.4
CV	900	1000	142.8	162.5	171.4	300	700
SEM	0.10	0.13	0.10	0.15	0.15	0.12	0.20

Figure 5.43 The influence of force on the percentage CV for the logarithm of max power, Pmax, based on subject's age.

Table 5.99 Mean, standard deviation, SD, percentage coefficient of variation, CV, and standard error of the mean, SEM values for the logarithm of the total power parameter, Ptotal, based on subject's age.

	<9	10-19	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60-69
mean	1.2	1.1	1.7	1.7	1.6	1.3	1.3
SD	0.9	0.9	1.0	1.2	1.0	1.0	1.0
CV	75	81.8	58.8	70.6	62.5	76.9	76.9
SEM	0.12	0.12	0.10	0.14	0.13	0.13	0.14

Figure 5.44 The influence of force on the percentage CV for the logarithm of total power, Ptotal, based on subject's age.

Table 5.100 Mean, standard deviation, SD, percentage coefficient of variation, CV, and standard error of the mean, SEM values for the gaussianity, sg, based on subject's age.

	<9	10-19	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60-69
mean	2.3	2.3	2.3	2.3	2.4	2.3	2.4
SD	0.1	0.1	0.5	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.2
CV	4.3	4.3	21.7	8.7	8.3	4.3	8.3
SEM	0.01	0.01	0.05	0.03	0.03	0.01	0.03

Figure 5.45 The influence of force on the percentage CV for the test of gaussianity, sg, based on subject's age.

Table 5.101 Mean, standard deviation, SD, percentage coefficient of variation, CV and standard error of the mean, SEM, values for the linearity parameter, sl, based on subject's age.

	<9	10-19	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60-69
mean	1.3	1.3	1.6	1.6	2.7	1.3	1.8
SD	0.6	0.9	1.4	1.4	5.1	0.9	1.7
CV	46.1	69.2	87.5	87.5	188.9	69.2	94.4
SEM	0.08	0.12	0.14	0.16	0.66	0.12	0.24

Figure 5.46 The influence of force on the percentage CV for test of linearity parameter, sl, based on subject's age.

Table 5.102 Mean, standard deviation, SD, percentage coefficient of variation, CV, and standard error of the mean, SEM, values, for the logarithm of the bispectrum peak amplitude parameter, Bmax, based on subject's age.

	<9	10-19	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60-69
mean	2.3	2.3	2.5	2.3	2.6	1.8	2.0
SD	0.7	0.6	1.0	1.0	1.1	0.6	0.8
CV	30.4	26.0	40.0	43.4	42.3	33.3	40.0
SEM	0.09	0.08	0.10	0.11	0.14	0.08	0.11

Figure 5.47 The influence of force on the percentage CV of maximum amplitude of the logarithm of the bispectrum peak amplitude parameter, Bmax, based on subject's age.

Table 5.103 Mean, standard deviation, SD, percentage coefficient of variation, CV, and standard error of the mean, SEM, values, for the position of the bispectrum peak amplitude in the x-direction, Bfx, based on subject's age.

	<9	10-19	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60-69
Mean	56.3	57.0	52.0	56.0	49.0	60.0	56.0
SD	24.0	31.0	11.0	15.0	15.0	12.0	32.0
CV	42.6	54.4	21.1	26.8	30.6	20.0	57.1
SEM	3.10	4.00	1.10	1.70	1.90	1.50	4.50

Figure 5.48 The influence of force on the percentage CV of the position of the bispectrum peak amplitude in the x-direction, Bfx, based on subject's age.

Table 5.104 Mean, standard deviation, SD, percentage coefficient of variation, CV, and standard error of the mean, SEM, values for the position of the bispectrum peak amplitude in the y-direction, Bfy, based on subject's age.

	<9	10-19	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60-69
Mean	39.0	40.0	38.0	37.0	32.0	51.0	36.0
SD	22.0	23.0	22.0	25.0	26.0	24.0	25.0
CV	56.0	57.5	57.9	67.6	81.3	47.0	69.4
SEM	2.80	3.00	2.20	2.80	3.40	3.10	3.50

Figure 5.49 The influence of force on the percentage coefficient of variation for test of the position of the bispectrum peak amplitude in the y-direction, Bfy, based on subject's age.

Table 5.105 Mean, standard deviation, SD, percentage coefficient of variation, CV, and standard error of the mean, SEM, values for the slope of the bispectrum peak amplitude in the x-direction, Bfxslope, based on subject's age.

	<9	10-19	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60-69
mean	64.0	55.0	57.0	53.0	49.0	61.0	51.0
SD	29.0	18.0	20.0	20.0	30.0	20.0	20.0
CV	45.3	32.7	35.1	37.8	61.2	32.8	39.2
SEM	3.70	2.30	2.00	2.30	3.90	2.60	2.80

Figure 5.50 The influence of force on the percentage CV of the slope of the bispectrum peak amplitude in the x-direction, Bfxslope, based on subject's age.

Table 5.106 Mean, standard deviation, SD, percentage coefficient of variation, CV and standard error of the mean, SEM, values for the slope of the bispectrum peak amplitude in the y-direction, Bfyslope, based on subject's age.

F	<9	10-19	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60-69
mean	16.0	14.0	14.0	14.0	12.0	14.0	12.0
SD	7.4	4.5	4.0	4.4	7.0	3.6	3.9
CV	46.0	32.1	28.6	31.4	58.3	25.7	32.5
SEM	0.96	0.58	0.40	0.50	0.90	0.56	0.55

Figure 5.51 The influence of force on the percentage CV of the slope of the bispectrum peak amplitude in the y-direction, Bfyslope, based on subject's age.

5.7.3 Analysis of age based on continuous descriptive analysis

Figures 5.52 to 5.55 show descriptive box plots indicating the distribution of values with age at 10, 50, and 100% MVC for turns per second, median frequency, total power and the bispectrum peak amplitude, respectively.

Figure 5.52 Influence of age on turns per second parameter, t/s, at (a) 10%, (b) 50% and (c) 100% MVC, respectively.

Figure 5.53 Influence of age on the median frequency parameter, P_{fmed} , at (a) 10%, (b) 50% and (c) 100% MVC, respectively.

Figure 5.54 Influence of age on the log of the total power parameter, P_{total} , at (a) 10%, (b) 50% and (c) 100% MVC, respectively.

Figure 5.55 Influence of age on the logarithm of Bispectrum peak amplitude, parameter, Bmax, at (a) 10%, (b) 50% and (c) 100% MVC, respectively.

5.7.4 Gender analysis using Wilcoxon sign-rank test

Tables 5.107 to 5.109 classify the transition from 10 to 50%, 50 to 100% and 10 to 100% of MVC, respectively for all 14 parameters as significant or non-significant for all 94 subjects (Group 1) and then for subjects based on gender (Group 2 for female and Group 3 for male subjects), using the Wilcoxon signed –rank test.

Table 5.107 Evaluation of the transition from 10 to 50% of MVC based on gender using the Wilcoxon signed-ranks test (S: significant, S, ($p < 0.05$), (NS): non-significant, NS, ($p \geq 0.05$)).

	GROUP 1 94 SUBJECTS	GROUP 2 38 FEMALE SUBJECTS	GROUP 3 56 MALE SUBJECTS
t/s	S	S	S
zc/s	S	S	S
Pfmed	S	NS	S
Pfmean	S	S	S
Pfx	NS	NS	NS
Pmax	S	S	S
Ptotal	S	S	S
sg	NS	S	NS
sl	NS	NS	NS
Bmax	S	NS	S
Bfx	NS	S	NS
Bfy	NS	NS	NS
Bfxslope	S	NS	S
Bfyslope	NS	NS	NS

Table 5.108 Evaluation of the transition from 50 to 100% of MVC based on gender using the Wilcoxon signed-ranks test (S: significant, S, ($p < 0.05$), (NS): non-significant, NS, ($p \geq 0.05$)).

	GROUP 1 94 SUBJECTS	GROUP 2 38 FEMALE SUBJECTS	GROUP 3 56 MALE SUBJECTS
t/s	S	S	S
zc/s	S	S	S
Pfmed	S	S	S
Pfmean	S	S	S
Pfx	NS	NS	NS
Pmax	S	S	S
Ptotal	S	S	S
sg	NS	NS	NS
sl	NS	NS	NS
Bmax	S	S	S
Bfx	NS	NS	NS
Bfy	NS	NS	NS
Bfxslope	S	S	S
Bfyslope	NS	NS	NS

Table 5.109 Evaluation of the transition from 10 to 100% of MVC based on gender using the Wilcoxon signed-ranks test (S: significant, S, ($p < 0.05$), (NS): non-significant, NS, ($p \geq 0.05$).

	GROUP 1 94 SUBJECTS	GROUP 2 38 FEMALE SUBJECTS	GROUP 3 56 MALE SUBJECTS
t/s	S	S	S
zc/s	S	S	S
Pfmed	S	S	S
Pfmean	S	S	S
Pfx	NS	NS	NS
Pmax	S	S	S
Ptotal	S	S	S
sg	NS	NS	NS
sl	NS	NS	NS
Bmax	S	S	S
Bfx	NS	S	NS
Bfy	NS	S	NS
Bfxslope	S	S	S
Bfyslope	NS	NS	NS

5.7.5 Gender analysis based on coefficient of variation

Table 5.110 tabulates the mean values, the standard deviation, the percentage coefficient of variation and the standard error of the mean of the fourteen parameters investigated based on gender

Table 5.110 Mean, standard deviation, coefficient of variation and standard error of the mean values, for the 14 parameters, based on subject's gender.

Parameter	MEAN		STANDARD DEVIATION, SD		PPERCENTAGE COEFFICIENT OF VARIATION, %CV		STANDARD ERROR OF THE MEAN, SEM	
	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F
t/s	18.0	15.0	14.0	12.0	78.0	80.0	1.9	1.9
zc/s	13.0	11.0	12.0	12.0	92.0	109.0	1.6	1.9
Pfmed	101.0	104.0	22.0	25.0	22.0	24.0	2.9	4.1
Pfmean	120.0	124.0	26.0	30.0	22.0	24.0	3.5	4.9
Pfx	79.0	78.0	21.0	19.0	27.0	24.0	2.8	3.1
Pmax	0.6	0.3	1.2	1.0	216.0	396.0	0.2	0.2
Ptotal	1.5	1.3	1.1	0.9	71.0	75.0	0.1	0.1
Bmax	2.3	2.2	0.8	1.0	34.0	45.0	0.1	0.2
sg	2.4	2.3	0.2	0.2	8.0	8.0	0.02	0.03
sl	1.9	1.3	2.7	1.2	145.0	92.0	0.4	0.2
Bfx	53.0	56.3	23.3	14.5	44.0	26.0	3.1	2.4
Bfy	33.8	46.7	24.7	21.2	73.0	45.0	3.3	3.4
Bfxslope	52.4	61.6	22.6	22.0	43.0	36.0	3.0	3.6
Bfyslope	12.8	15.2	4.9	5.4	38.0	36.0	0.7	0.9

5.7.6 Analysis of gender based on continuous descriptive analysis

Figures 5.56 to 5.59 show descriptive box plots indicating the distribution of values with gender at 10, 50, and 100% MVC for turns per second, median frequency, total power and the bispectrum peak amplitude, respectively.

Figure 5.56 Influence of gender on turns per second, t/s, at (a) 10%, (b) 50% and (c) 100% MVC, respectively.

Figure 5.57 Influence of gender on the median frequency, P_{fmed} , at (a) 10% (b) 50% and (c) 100% MVC, respectively.

Figure 5.58 Influence of gender on the log of the total power, P_{total} , at (a) 10%, (b) 50% and (c) 100% MVC, respectively.

Figure 5.59 Influence of gender on the log of the bispectrum peak amplitude, B_{max} , at (a) 10% (b) 50% and (c) 100% MVC, respectively.

5.8 Correlation analysis

Correlation analysis between the fourteen variables (parameters) was investigated for the 94 normal, 11 myopathy and 9 neuropathy subjects using the Spearman rank correlation. Only the pairs of variables presenting a good (0.6-0.79) and excellent (0.8-1.0) correlation coefficient (CC) for the normal subjects and the corresponding results for the myopathy and neuropathy subjects are listed in Table 5.111, together with the 95% Confidence Interval (CI). Figure 5.60 shows correlation analysis plots for parameter pairs, t/s-zc/s, Pmedian-Pfmean, Pmax-Ptotal, and Bfxslope-Bfyslope, for the three groups of subjects.

Table 5.111 Correlation analysis for pair of variables presenting an excellent and good correlation.

PARAMETER PAIR	NORMALS		MYOPATHY		NEUROPATHY	
	CC	95% CI	CC	95% CI	CC	95% CI
t/s - zc/s	0.65	0.59 to 0.70	0.99	0.99 to 1.00	0.98	0.96 to 0.96
t/s - Pmax	0.67	0.62 to 0.72	0.06	-0.21 to 0.32	0.87	0.78 to 0.93
t/s - Ptotal	0.73	0.69 to 0.77	0.93	0.88 to 0.96	0.92	0.87 to 0.96
zc/s - Pmax	0.69	0.64 to 0.71	0.05	-0.22 to 0.31	0.90	0.83 to 0.95
zc/s - Ptotal	0.66	0.61 to 0.71	0.92	0.87 to 0.96	0.94	0.90 to 0.98
Pmax - Ptotal	0.87	0.85 to 0.89	0.20	-0.06 to 0.45	0.98	0.97 to 0.99
Pfmedian - Pfmean	0.75	0.70 to 0.79	0.52	0.30 to 0.69	0.92	0.86 to 0.96
Pfmean - Bmax	-0.75	-0.79 to -0.71	-0.58	-0.73 to -0.37	-0.45	-0.66 to -0.18
Pfmedian - Bmax	-0.65	-0.70 to -0.60	-0.68	-0.80 to -0.50	-0.43	-0.64 to -0.15
Bfx - Bmax	-0.62	-0.68 to -0.56	-0.64	-0.77 to -0.45	-0.71	-0.83 to -0.53
Bfy - Bmax	-0.60	-0.66 to -0.54	-0.76	-0.85 to -0.61	-0.20	-0.47 to 0.09
Bfxslope - Bfyslope	0.84	0.81 to 0.87	0.89	0.82 to 0.93	0.75	0.59 to 0.86
Pfmedian - Bfxslope	0.60	0.53 to 0.65	0.40	0.16 to 0.60	0.48	0.21 to 0.68
Bfx - Bfy	0.71	0.66 to 0.75	0.69	0.51 to 0.80	0.44	0.17 to 0.65
Bfx - Bfxslope	0.62	0.57 to 0.68	0.65	0.46 to 0.78	0.66	0.45 to 0.80
Bfx - Bfyslope	0.73	0.68 to 0.77	0.77	0.64 to 0.86	0.62	0.40 to 0.77
Bfy - Bfxslope	0.69	0.64 to 0.73	0.89	0.82 to 0.94	0.01	-0.28 to 0.31
Bfy - Bfyslope	0.64	0.58 to 0.69	0.88	0.80 to 0.93	0.09	-0.21 to 0.37
Bfxslope - Bmax	-0.71	-0.75 to -0.66	-0.76	-0.85 to -0.61	-0.77	-0.87 to -0.61

NOR

MYO

NEURO

(a)

(b)

Figure 5.60 continued...

Figure 5.60 Correlation analysis plots for parameter pairs, (a) $t/s-zc/s$, (b) $P_{\text{median}}-P_{\text{mean}}$, (c) $P_{\text{max}}-P_{\text{total}}$, and (d) $B_{\text{fxslope}}-B_{\text{fyslope}}$, for the three groups of subjects, NORMALS, MYO and NEURO.

5.9 Cluster analysis

Tables 5.112 and 5.113 tabulate the KNN classifier performance results for two classes (a. NORMAL/ABNORMAL and b. MYO/NEURO) and on three classes (NOR/MYO/NEURO). Tables list number of subjects, number of features, values of k, percentage of correct classification, %CC, percentage of false positives, %FP, percentage of false negatives, %FN, sensitivity, SE, specificity, SP, recall, RE, and precision, PR.

Table 5.112 KNN classifier performance results for two classes. The upper part of the table presents the NORMAL/ABNORMAL (MYO and NEURO) classification and the lower part the MYO/NEURO classification.

Model	No. of subjects NORMAL/ABNORMAL	No. of features	Value of k	%CC	%FP	%FN	SE	SP	RE	PR
1	18/18	70	1	94.4	5.6	5.6	94.4	94.4	94.4	94.4
2	18/18	70	3	91.7	0.0	16.7	83.3	100.0	83.3	100.0
3	18/18	70	5	83.3	0.0	33.3	66.7	100.0	66.7	100.0
4	18/18	70	7	83.3	0.0	33.3	66.7	100.0	66.7	100.0
5	18/18	25	1	61.1	27.8	50.0	50.0	72.2	50.0	64.3
6	18/18	25	3	58.3	33.3	50.0	50.0	66.7	50.0	60.0
7	18/18	25	5	69.4	22.2	38.9	61.1	77.8	61.1	73.3
8	18/18	25	7	66.7	27.8	38.9	61.1	72.2	61.1	68.8
9	91/20	70	1	86.5	3.3	60.0	40.0	96.7	44.4	72.7
10	91/20	70	3	73.9	22.0	45.0	55.0	78.0	61.1	35.5
11	91/20	70	5	62.2	37.4	40.0	60.0	62.6	66.7	26.1
12	91/20	70	7	85.6	7.7	45.0	55.0	92.3	61.1	61.1
13	91/20	25	1	82.9	7.7	60.0	40.0	92.3	44.4	53.3
14	91/20	25	3	76.6	24.2	20.0	80.0	75.8	88.9	42.1
15	91/20	25	5	72.1	30.8	15.0	85.0	69.2	94.4	37.8
16	91/20	25	7	81.1	14.3	40.0	60.0	85.7	66.7	48.0
Model	No. of patients MYO/NEURO	No. of features	Value of k	%CC	%FP	%FN	SE	SP	RE	PR
17	11/9	70	1	40.0	72.7	44.4	55.6	27.3	25.0	38.5
18	11/9	70	3	55.5	63.6	33.2	77.8	36.4	35.0	50.0
19	11/9	70	5	50.0	45.5	55.6	44.4	54.5	20.0	44.4
20	11/9	70	7	65.0	45.4	22.2	77.8	54.5	35.0	58.3
21	11/9	25	1	40.0	54.5	66.7	33.3	45.5	15.0	33.3
22	11/9	25	3	50.0	45.5	55.5	45.5	54.5	20.0	44.4
23	11/9	25	5	50.0	36.4	66.7	33.3	63.6	15.0	42.9
24	11/9	25	7	70.0	36.4	22.2	77.8	63.4	35.0	63.6

Table 5.113 KNN classifier performance results for three classes
(NOR/MYO/NEURO).

Model	No. of subjects NOR/MYO/NEURO	No. of features	Value of k	%CC	%FP	%FN	SE	SP	RE	PR
25	9/9/9	70	1	40.7	33.3	61.5	38.5	66.7	27.8	62.5
26	9/9/9	70	3	59.3	0.0	46.2	53.8	100.0	38.9	100.0
27	9/9/9	70	5	44.4	0.0	75.0	25.0	100.0	16.7	100.0
28	9/9/9	70	7	48.1	11.1	64.3	35.7	88.9	27.8	83.3
29	9/9/9	25	1	22.2	77.8	63.6	36.4	22.2	22.2	36.4
30	9/9/9	25	3	51.9	44.4	25.0	75.0	55.6	50.0	69.2
31	9/9/9	25	5	44.4	50.0	27.3	72.7	50.0	44.4	66.7
32	9/9/9	25	7	51.9	33.3	33.3	66.7	66.7	44.4	72.7
33	18/9/9	70	1	63.9	27.3	53.3	46.7	72.7	38.9	53.8
34	18/9/9	70	3	66.7	5.9	38.5	61.5	94.1	44.4	88.9
35	18/9/9	70	5	55.6	16.7	61.5	38.5	83.3	27.8	62.5
36	18/9/9	70	7	58.3	11.8	57.1	42.9	88.2	33.3	75.0
37	18/9/9	25	1	41.7	27.8	81.8	18.2	72.2	11.1	28.6
38	18/9/9	25	3	61.1	25.0	28.6	71.4	75.0	55.6	71.4
39	18/9/9	25	5	47.2	35.3	53.8	46.2	64.7	33.3	50.0
40	18/9/9	25	7	55.6	25.0	33.3	66.7	75.0	44.4	66.7
41	91/11/9	70	1	82.9	3.3	75.0	25.0	96.7	22.2	57.1
42	91/11/9	70	3	68.5	22.0	64.3	35.7	78.0	27.8	20.0
43	91/11/9	70	5	57.7	37.4	53.3	46.7	62.6	38.9	17.1
44	91/11/9	70	7	42.3	54.9	45.5	54.5	45.1	33.3	10.7
45	91/11/9	25	1	77.5	7.7	85.7	14.3	92.3	11.1	22.2
46	91/11/9	25	3	68.5	24.2	36.4	63.6	75.8	38.9	24.1
47	91/11/9	25	5	64.9	30.8	25.0	75.0	69.2	50.0	24.3
48	91/11/9	25	7	60.4	37.4	16.7	83.3	62.6	55.6	22.7

5.10 SOFM analysis

Figures 5.61 to 5.72 present the SOFM mapping for the various classes selected based on the number of subjects and the parameters used.

Figure 5.61 SOFM mapping of the 70 features for 18 NORMAL subjects (x), and 18 ABNORMAL subjects (o).

Figure 5.62 SOFM mapping of the 25 features for 18 NORMAL subjects (x), and 18 ABNORMAL subjects (o).

Figure 5.63 SOFM mapping of the 70 features for 91 NORMAL subjects (x), and 20 ABNORMAL subjects (o).

Figure 5.64 SOFM mapping of the 25 features for 91 NORMAL subjects (x), and 20 ABNORMAL subjects (o).

Figure 5.65 SOFM mapping of the 70 features for 11 myopathy (MYO) subjects (x) and 9 neuropathy (NEURO) subjects (o).

Figure 5.66 SOFM mapping of the 25 features for 11 myopathy (MYO) subjects (x) and 9 neuropathy (NEURO) subjects (o).

Figure 5.67 SOFM mapping of the 70 features for 9 normal (NOR) subjects (x), 9 myopathy (MYO) subjects (+) and 9 neuropathy (NEURO) subject (o).

Figure 5.68 SOFM mapping of the 25 features for 9 normal (NOR) subjects (x), 9 myopathy (MYO) subjects (+) and 9 neuropathy (NEURO) subject (o).

Figure 5.69 SOFM mapping of the 70 features for 18 normal (NOR) subjects (x), 9 myopathy (MYO) subjects (+) and 9 neuropathy (NEURO) subject (o).

Figure 5.70 SOFM mapping of the 25 features for 18 normal (NOR) subjects (x), 9 myopathy (MYO) subjects (+) and 9 neuropathy (NEURO) subject (o).

Figure 5.71 SOFM mapping of the 70 features for 91 normal (NOR) subjects (x), 11 myopathy (MYO) subjects (+) and 9 neuropathy (NEURO) subject (o).

Figure 5.72 SOFM mapping of the 25 features for 91 normal (NOR) subjects (x), 11 myopathy (MYO) subjects (+) and 9 neuropathy (NEURO) subject (o).

Chapter 6
Discussion

Chapter 6

DISCUSSION

6.1 Introduction

In this chapter, the recording set-up, procedure and data acquisition methods together with the results presented in chapter 5 are discussed. Although these results have been obtained from analysing recordings taken from the biceps brachii (BB) alone, the same methods may easily be applied on other muscles, such as the gastrocnemius and the triceps. Nevertheless, recordings were performed on the BB muscle alone for the purpose of this study. The BB muscle has been credited for high quality estimation of EMG variables, because of its anatomy and more precisely due to the long and parallel fibres consisting the muscle, Rainoldi et al (1999). This results in sufficient space to accommodate a four bar electrode of 40 mm length as the one used in this study. As mentioned earlier it is important that the electrode is placed between the motor points and the tendon endings. Furthermore, in many muscles other than the BB, repeatability of parameters, depends on the contraction type (voluntary or electrically) and in the experimental modalities used, Rainoldi et al (1999). It has also been recorded that for the same muscle (not excluding the BB), some parameters obtained from various SEMG studies, show conflicting results, (Tables 3.1, 3.2 and 3.3). Hence it should not be a surprise that SEMG has not yet been globally accepted for the assessment of neuromuscular diseases. It is believed that this study will help towards the wider use of SEMG for the assessment of neuromuscular function.

6.2 Recording set-up

This section describes possible sources of errors or limitations and whether these may have influenced results obtained. The main parts of the set-up as discussed in Chapter 4 are:

- (i) The EMG Nicolet Viking IV system. Since this was a FDA approved dedicated electromyography recording system and well accepted in the market for routine examinations and research, it can easily be assumed that it was not the source of any significant errors affecting the reliability of results.

- (ii) A calibrated force measurement system. This was designed and calibrated to a 2kg/Volt, meaning that if a subject pulled a total of 10kg, a shift of 5 Volts would be displayed on the oscilloscope. When the belt attached to the wrist of the subject (and at the other end attached at the transducer) was tight some muscle activity was noticeable. The belt length was readjusted each time successive subjects height was considerably different in order to make sure that no activity was recorded at zero force level. The only disadvantage of the force measurement system was the small weight of the belt. This occasionally caused a minor activity of the muscle. When this occurred, readjustment of the belt's length was necessary.
- (iii) The oscilloscope, placed 1.5 metres above the ground level, was not itself a possible source of wrong recordings but its position and location were. The scope was positioned at an angle of approximately 60 degrees from the subject and hence the exact location of the observed zero line was not possible. This may have caused very small differences in the % of the MVCs requested by the subject to perform, since it was difficult to observe the ground line from his/her position. The instructions and help of the person performing the recording were hence necessary. However it would be better if the oscilloscope was placed directly opposite the subject instead of at an angle.
- (iv) Electrode block used. The active surface electrode used was connected in a bipolar configuration mode where noise is less likely to interfere with the signal, due to common mode rejection, since common signals to both electrodes (such as background electrical artefacts or electromagnetic radiation) are subtracted out. The characteristics of the electrode, the input impedance being greater than 1000 M Ω , and the 0 dB gain ensured that the input signal did not suffer any considerable distortion. Special gel Elefix, Model Z-401CE Nihon Kohden was used to improve the contact between electrodes and skin.
- (v) The personal PC used for storing the data before the analysis, could not cause any possible errors in the recording, nor it was necessary to have a PC of the latest technology.

- (vi) Acquisition board. A 16 single ended, 12-bit resolution (1 in 4096) was selected and proved quite sufficient for the purpose needed. If a 16-bit board was chosen instead, the resolution would be 1 in 65536, however the accuracy could not compromise the cost of the board nor most importantly the difference in results.

6.3 Recording procedure

The recording procedure is also described in detail in Chapter 4. Any recording procedure may be the source of various errors. Although in this set-up, every effort was made through the entire process to keep these minimal, minor errors in result's analysis, may have occurred due to the following reasons:

- (i) Electrode block positioning. The exact location of the electrode block was positioned according to biceps brachii length. However for children and female subjects (for non-symptomatic volunteers), and for severely damaged biceps muscles, this presented considerable difficulties, since muscle length could not be accurately measured. In such cases the electrode block was positioned empirically and/or was moved along the muscle longitudinal axis visually inspecting the signals amplitude, until a signal of considerable amplitude was visible.
- (ii) Unstable force level. This may be caused either due to subject anxiety, muscle fatigue, or due to muscle weakness. Subject anxiety is usually caused due to the phenomenon of the unknown of the unexpected or of fear. None of these reasons are justified for this study, since; the subjects were well informed before hand about the entire recording procedure by a written and an oral description. Furthermore the subjects were talked to during the procedure, and were reminded of the next step. The recording time was 5 seconds; a time long enough to obtain a reliable signal length for analysis but also short enough to avoid fatigue. After each recording an interval of 2 minutes proved sufficient, to avoid fatigue. All recordings (non-symptomatic & patients) were visually inspected, before these were analysed. Only two recordings were rejected. That of a boy aged 7,

who could not stay still for 5 seconds, and that of a severely diseased patient who could not lift any weights whatsoever.

- (iii) Movement artefacts. This is a common source of errors and noise. Unwanted electrical potentials may be produced as a result of mechanical or movement artefacts. The unwanted signals produced by this type of error usually do not exceed 30 Hz due to the fact that body tissues cannot oscillate at higher frequencies. Since however the 30 Hz component is a common one in SEMG signals, artefacts that are produced by rapid displacement of limbs may become indistinguishable from SEMG signals, especially when they occur simultaneously. Hence these should be recognised and eliminated on the raw EMG signal before any modification (filtering, amplification) is performed as done in this study. The force measurement system's strap was usually a source of error. Special care was taken to avoid movement artefacts by asking the subject to practice, and the experiment did not start until a straight line at zero force level was achieved. Although special care was taken in this study to avoid any movement artefacts, this sometimes proved difficult with young children and patients. Sometimes, recording was taken 3 or 4 times, to achieve a desirable reading.
- (iv) Environmental conditions. Since the recording procedure was performed in a special isolated EMG/EEG laboratory with temperature and humidity conditions controlled and monitored continuously, no errors were expected due to environmental conditions.

6.4 Data acquisition

Parameters were extracted from the recorded waveforms using analysis algorithms written in MATLAB 5.3. The analysis of these parameters was performed with the help of an addition of EXCEL 2000, named Analyse it for Microsoft EXCEL. Well-accepted and widely used methods were employed: (Wilcoxon signed-rank test, descriptive analysis, Mann-Whitney test, coefficient of variation, Spearman rank correlation, the KNN leave-one out method and the Self organising Feature Maps). Throughout the analysis, it was never neglected, that the signal could not be

represented accurately by a Gaussian distribution, and hence it may be assumed that the signal analysis methods adopted were not the source of any serious errors.

6.5 Time domain analysis

Two parameters were extracted from the time domain. The turns per second t/s and the zero crossings per second zc/s . A detailed analysis for each follows.

6.5.1 Turns per second

The mean values of the turns per second parameter t/s , increase steadily and significantly, with force, Tables 5.1, 5.2, 5.3 and 5.5 together with the median values and the corresponding $P_{5\%}$, $P_{25\%}$, $P_{75\%}$, and $P_{95\%}$, for all three groups NOR, MYO and NEURO indicating clearly the influence of FL increment on this parameter. On the contrary the coefficient of variation CV, decreased in all three groups with FL, with the decrease being more obvious for the NOR group. This decrease could be contributed to the larger increment of the mean values in comparison to the increment of the standard deviation SD values. The SD, (lower in the NOR group), increased slightly with FL (up to 70% for the NOR and MYO groups), as did the standard error of the mean SEM, (considerably less in the NOR group). A small SEM value indicates that there is a high probability that the sample mean is close to the population mean. Table 5.4 provides a statistical analysis having all values recorded as one entity per group (those recorded at 10%, followed by those recorded at 30%, 50%, 70% and 100% MVC). When the mean and median of all 470, 55 and 45 values for the NOR, MYO and NEURO groups respectively (94, 11 and 9 subjects each at all 5 FL's), are compared, it could be seen that these are considerably less in the NOR group, than the two patient groups, as is the SD and the standard error of the mean SEM. The coefficient of variation CV is nearly the same for all three groups. An examination of the quartile ranges also show, the influence of FL on the increase of number of the turns per second parameter. Differences between the NOR group and the two patient groups may be visualized with the help of the descriptive comparative analysis using box-plots shown in Fig. 5.1. Wilcoxon signed-rank test significance level ($p < 0.05$), classifies differences in values as significant, or non-significant, during FL transitions within each group. All transitions from a low to a high FL are classified as significant for all three groups, (with only one exemption in the mid force region for the MYO group). Mann-

Whitney test significance level ($p < 0.05$), then classifies differences between groups, on the same basis as the values recorded in Table 5.4. Mann-Whitney test was used for this particular comparison, instead of Wilcoxon sign-rank test, since the former is more powerful for independent samples (NOR, MYO and NEURO). As can be seen there is a significant difference in values between NOR and MYO, as well as between NOR and NEURO groups, but not between the two groups of patients, Table 5.6. Hence this test may easily and quickly be implemented to distinguish between normals and patients but not between the types of patients (MYO or NEURO). It is however a most reliable, accurate and simple test to discriminate between normal subjects and subjects suffering from a neuromuscular disorder.

From the histogram distributions of Fig. 5.2, the shift of values towards the right hand side is obvious for all three groups, as values increase with FL. Another observation may be that the values for the NOR group are lower than those of the NEURO group, which in turn are lower than those of the MYO group.

Other studies examining the t/s parameter are listed below.

Pattichis et al (1993) examined the influence of this parameter at the same FLs as this study for the biceps brachii muscle for a recording period of 1 second with the aid of needle electrodes. Three subjects were examined, one NOR, one MND and one MYO. In the NOR and the MND subjects the t/s parameter increased with FL up to 70%. For the MYO subject the number of t/s increased steadily all the way up to MVC.

A study by Preece et al (1994) was aimed at comparing quantitative studies of surface and needle recordings. Results showed that turns per second may be a useful measure of analysis in either method of recording (surface or needle) in some muscles such as the tibialis anterior, but different in other muscles such as rectus femoris. The difference was not due to SEMG drawbacks but due to the disadvantage of needle recordings being depth dependent. Furthermore SEMG recordings showed a smaller degree of variability between individuals and a high degree of repeatability when recordings were made over a relatively long period of time, (30 seconds). Preece defined a turn as a signal reversal greater than 1% of full-

scale deflection and results showed that at MVC, the mean value of 13 healthy subjects was 417.2 with a standard deviation of 82.1, when recorded with surface electrodes as compared with 490.2 and a standard deviation of 82.2 for needle recordings for the tibialis anterior muscle. For the rectus femoris muscle the mean value of turns per second at MVC was 260.9, with a standard deviation of 72.0, as compared with 425.5 and 124.7 for needle recordings. In this study at MVC, the mean value of turns per second from 94 normal subjects with SEMG for 5 seconds was 28.0 with a standard deviation of 12.8. Through his study Preece proved that SEMG might prove more reliable than needle EMG for some muscles (tibialis anterior), as far as turns per second analysis is concerned. This study has proved that not only the turns per second parameter is a most reliable parameter, since it is influenced consistently with FL increment, but most importantly it may be used to discriminate between normal subjects and neuromuscular patients.

6.5.2 Zero crossings per second

Tables 5.7, 5.8 and 5.9 give the statistical analysis for the results obtained for the zero crossings per second parameter. As in the turns per second, the mean, the median and the $P_{5\%}$, $P_{25\%}$, $P_{75\%}$, and $P_{95\%}$, values increase steadily with FL. The SD and the SEM are once again considerably less for the NOR group. The CV decreases for all three groups, with the decrease being more obvious for the NOR group. Table 5.10 provides a statistical analysis of all values recorded in each group, showing clearly that mean, median, SD and SEM values are considerably smaller for the NOR group, than the two patient groups. The CV is once again nearly the same of all three groups. Finally from Table 5.10, an increase in the number of zero crossings per second with FL may be concluded, by observing the quartile ranges. Differences between the three groups may be seen from the descriptive comparative analysis of Fig. 5.3, which shows not only the reduced number of zero crossings for the NOR group, but also that many near outliers exist for the NOR group at 10% MVC. This could be contributed, to the large value of the CV at 10% MVC (200%). All force transitions were evaluated as significant with only one exception in the MYO group, (the same one as for turns per second). The total amount of zero crossings per second was so different between the three groups, that as with the turns per second, Mann-Whitney, classified differences between normal subjects and the two group of patients as significant, Table 5.12. The histogram distributions of Fig. 5.4 show a

clear shift to the right since all values increase considerably with FL. The increased values for the MYO and NEURO group as compared with those of the NORMAL group are also obvious.

An early study performed on zero crossings rate performed by Inbar et al (1986), concluded that no consistent changes in zc/s were observed with varying tensions, which is in contradiction with the results of this study. The study of Preece et al (1994), investigated also the usefulness of zero crossing analysis. A zero crossing was defined in their study as deviations of signal from baseline of greater than 1% of full-scale deflection. Conclusions as for the effectiveness of SEMG compared with needle EMG recordings were encouraging for zero crossings as well. Their results showed that the mean values of zero crossings per second of the 13 healthy subjects at MVC was 267.2 with a standard deviation of 68.9, as compared with 271.6 and 44.7 with needle electrodes for the tibialis anterior muscle. For the rectus femoris muscle, mean value for zero crossings were 139.4 with a standard deviation of 29.1, in comparison with 223.8 and a standard deviation of 68.5 with needle recordings. Results of this study show for normal subjects a mean for zero crossings of 22.0 at MVC, with a standard deviation of 11.8. However a direct comparison between results obtained Preece et al (1994) and this study could not be made since muscles, recording set-up and procedure are different. Another study performed on the analysis of zero crossings was that of Fuglsang et al (1984). That study revealed that in patients with myopathy as well as in controls one should observe an increase in the number of zero crossings up to approximately mid force levels. From there on, there is constancy in the number of zero crossings. Patients suffering with neuropathy generally showed an increase in zero crossings with force level, with the exemption at 30% of MVC where approximately 70% of the patients showed a decrease. These results are in contradiction with this study, where the number of zero crossings per second was found to increase in both groups of patients. Furthermore the analysis of the zero crossings per second parameter may be used accurately and easily to discriminate between normal subjects and patients suffering with neuromuscular disorders.

Having in mind the conclusions of Preece et al (1994), stating that SEMG may be used with higher precision than needle EMG recordings, which suffer with muscle

depth dependence, the findings for both time domain parameters presented in this study are believed to be of the utmost importance.

6.6 Frequency domain analysis

Parameters analysed were the median frequency P_{fmed} , the mean frequency P_{fmean} , the frequency at maximum power P_{fx} , the maximum power P_{max} , and the total power P_{total} . Although one may argue that it was a surplus to examine both median and mean power frequencies, since their behaviour is similar, both were examined, having in mind that this statement is not always true. Four groups (see Tables 3.1 and 3.3) analysed both types of frequencies as this present study, Bilodeau et al (1992), Farina et al (2002), Merletti et al (1992) and Bilodeau et al (1995). In the first study, it was concluded that P_{fmed} and P_{fmean} do not follow the same pattern between genders, whereas Farina et al (2002), concluded that neither parameter may be related with force level. Merletti et al (1992), when examining the two spectral frequencies reached similar conclusions for both frequencies (increase up to 80% MVC, independent of age), whereas Bilodeau et al (1995) concluded that behaviour of the spectral frequencies was found to be depended on the muscle examined. Two muscles were examined in the Bilodeau study. The triceps brachii, and the anconeus muscle. The behaviour of the mean and median frequencies in these two muscles depended on the amount of skin fold layer. Muscles with a considerable amount of skin fold layer caused a loss of power in the high frequency region with an increase of force. This resulted in a change of the power spectrum shape and hence the two types of frequencies behaved differently. The same may apply for the same muscle if the division is made between genders according to the Bilodeau study. For instance in their study, the mean frequency was found to decrease in the TB muscle in women, whereas the median was found to increase, since women presented a larger amount of skin fold layer in the TB muscle.

Although power domain analysis seems to be by far the most favourite and has been utilised most by researches, this study may also help with the development of the data bank containing an analysis of the five parameters from the power domain. This data bank may well be used as a reference in the future.

6.6.1 Median frequency

This power frequency parameter has not been fully exploited. Particularly in patients, no study to my knowledge has investigated the median frequency P_{fmed} , on BB muscles, despite the fact that the BB muscle offers great advantages for reliable recordings, mentioned earlier in this study. Furthermore the P_{fmed} , (i) is more reliable than the mean frequency P_{fmean} when examining signals affected by noise such as the SEMG, Merletti et al (1989), (ii) is a better parameter from a statistical point of view since the recorded EMG does not present the characteristics of a normal distribution; on the contrary it is often skewed to the right, Bilodeau et al (1995), (iii) is affected less than the mean frequency from the low pass filtering of the skin, Bilodeau et al (1995).

This study has shown that the mean and median values of P_{fmed} , decrease with FL only for the NOR group, whereas for the MYO and NEURO group they do not follow a consistent pattern. The SD values for all 3 groups are similar, but they tend to decrease with FL only for the NOR group. The SEM values are once again less for the NOR group, indicating a high probability that the sample mean is close to the population mean, (Tables 5.13, 5.14 and 5.15). The corresponding values for $P_{25\%}$, $P_{75\%}$, and $P_{95\%}$, decrease also with FL for the NOR group. The decrease in the mean values of the NOR group was classified as significant (Table 5.17), and hence may be used to distinguish between normal and pathological subjects when examining the influence of FL on the BB muscle. Although this finding is in contradiction with other studies (Table 3.1), it is in full agreement with a well-accepted review paper, by Haig et al (1999), which clearly states that “the analysis of decline in median frequency with fatigue or increasing force is a measure which has no single correlate in standard needle EMG”. It is possible that fellow researchers may contribute this decline of median frequency to muscle fatigue. However, every effort was made to avoid this phenomenon and even so, decline in median frequency did not occur with patients, who are less fatigue resistant.

A similar statistical analysis (Table 5.16), (all values recorded as one entity per group), as for the other parameters has shown that the mean, median and the quartile ranges of the NOR and MYO groups, are quite similar and less than the corresponding values of the NEURO group. The SEM is once again less for the

NOR group. Descriptive comparative analysis, in Fig. 5.5 shows the distribution of values, similarities and differences among groups. The decrease in values during transition from a low to a high FL, was always classified as significant for the NOR group only, Table 5.17. No significant differences were detected through the Mann-Whitney test between the NOR and MYO group but both other combination pairs proved to be significantly different, Table 5.18.

Figure 5.6 shows the histogram distributions of the P_{fmed} parameter for all three groups. As can be seen for the NOR group there is a shift of values to the left, in contrast to the values for the two patient groups which remain fairly constant. Furthermore it may be seen that the values of the NEURO group are higher than those of the other two groups.

Contradicting findings have been reported from various other researches. One of the earliest studies performed on PS analysis, was that of Chaffin (1968). Out of the 29 asymptomatic (NOR) subjects, twelve were examined through the BB muscle. It was found that the power spectrum shifted towards the lower frequency region with an increase of force. Although not mentioned by Chaffin, this would have resulted in a median frequency decrease as this study has found. Another finding of the Chaffin study was that many common neuropathies and myopathies result in an EMG frequency spectrum being shifted towards the high frequency region, as compared to asymptomatic subjects. A shift of PS towards the high frequency region and hence an increase of P_{fmed} was noted by Gander et al (1985). Inbar et al (1986), concluded that the P_{fmed} parameter is independent of FL. Linsen et al (1993), examined the variation of P_{fmed} within normal subjects and concluded that it varied considerably. Merletti et al (1989), agreed with this statement, when recordings were made at high FL. Krivickas et al (1998), reported that the initial median frequency (IMF) was greater in male than in female subjects. No significant differences were noted in this study. Furthermore the Krivickas group reported that the slope of IMF was not affected with gender. This is in agreement with the findings of this study, in which the findings regarding age and gender influence are analysed later in this chapter.

Shankar et al (1989), found that the median frequency analysed from the BB muscle varied considerably with applied torque, though he eventually reached the

conclusion that the MUAP suffered less high frequency filtering and hence a median frequency increase would be observed.

6.6.2 Mean frequency

Similar findings as those obtained for the median frequency are obtained here. The mean and median values decrease only for the NOR group, as the $P_{5\%}$, $P_{25\%}$, $P_{75\%}$ and $P_{95\%}$ with FL increment, but not for the MYO or NEURO groups, (Tables 5.19, 5.20, 5.21). The SD and the SEM values were also reduced for the NOR group alone, whereas corresponding CV values remained quite constant with FL. On the contrary SD, SEM and CV values for the two patient groups were not influenced consistently with FL increment. When the three groups are compared (Table 5.22), smaller mean, median and SEM values have been recorded for the NOR group. The distribution and dispersion of values for the three groups, shown in Fig. 5.7 indicate clearly the smaller numerical values and scatter for the NOR group. Wilcoxon signed-rank test, classified reduction in values during all FL transitions as significant, for the NOR group alone. A clear distinction between NOR and NEURO groups was found with the Mann-Whitney test, (Table 5.24).

The histogram distributions of Fig. 5.8 are similar to those of Fig. 5.6 plotting the distributions of P_{fmed} . Here the shift for the NOR group towards the lower values is even more obvious than before with P_{fmed} , since the initial values are higher.

As with P_{fmed} , the findings for P_{fmean} are quite important, since there is a distinguishable difference between normal subjects and neuromuscular patients, not only in the behaviour of the mean power frequency with FL increment, but also between values recorded, enabling a discrimination between NOR and NEURO subjects.

Despite the disadvantages present in the P_{fmean} , this parameter has been more exploited than median frequency, again though with some contradicting results.

Muro et al (1982), examining this parameter on normal subjects as well as with patients, showed that for NOR and MYO subjects the P_{fmean} parameter increases with FL but decreases for the NEURO subjects. Moritani et al (1987), showed that

the increase of P_{fmean} with FL for NOR subjects is up to 80% and then values stabilize. Gerdle et al (1990), agrees with the findings of Moritani et al (1987), but noted an increase up to 60% and not up to 80% MVC. Linsen et al (1993) came to the same conclusion regarding intersubject variability as with for the P_{fmed}, i.e. that the variability is high, reducing the potential of SEMG. Feng et al (1998) noticed higher values of P_{fmean} in spastic patients than in normal subjects. Finally Rainoldi et al (1999) concluded that P_{fmean} decreases with FL. His group found the decrease to occur between 30 to 70% MVC, whereas this study proved a continuous decrease with FL from 10 to 100% MVC.

6.6.3 Frequency at maximum power

Although besides this study, only a few studies were traced in the literature dealing with this parameter, results are once again contradicting.

This study has shown that the mean, median and SD values as well as the SEM and the CV remain unaffected with FL increase for all three groups, (Tables 5.25, 5.26 and 5.27).

A comparison between all values recorded from the three groups, Table 5.28, shows that differences exist between the three groups, with the standard error of the mean being considerably less for the NOR group, indicating that the probability that the sample mean for the two patient groups is considerably higher to be far away from the population mean, than the corresponding NOR sample mean. The descriptive box-plots analysis presented in Fig. 5.9, shows that the values for the NOR group are higher than those of the MYO group, with a smaller dispersion also, but lower than the corresponding NEURO values. The small change in values caused by the increase of the FL for the three groups was classified as non-significant for the three groups with only one exemption in the NOR group, Table 5.29. However differences between values among the three groups were classified as significant, Table 5.30.

From the histogram distributions of Fig. 5.10, one may see once again, that the FL does not influence the value distribution for either three groups.

Although the examination of the frequency at maximum power parameter has shown that this parameter is not influenced with FL for any group, there is a clear and significant difference among values recorded between the three groups, enabling a distinction between the three groups.

Muro et al (1982), examining the influence of FL on the Pfx parameter, on 5 normal and 10 pathological subjects reached the same conclusion as this study, i.e. that the FL has no significant influence on the values of Pfx. However no comparison was made between values recorded among groups. Different findings were found though by Gander et al (1985), who concluded that Pfx values increase with FL up to 35 Nm but for higher torques Pfx values were reduced. Pattichis et al. (1993), has shown (as this present study) that this parameter is independent of FL for all three groups of subjects, and the mean values recorded do not follow a consistent pattern.

6.6.4 Maximum power

In normal subjects, an increase in maximum power with force level should be expected since more fibres are recruited. The statistical analysis is presented in Tables, 5.31, 5.32 and 5.33. Values between NOR and MYO groups are generally quite similar, but values for the NEURO group are smaller. Table 5.34 gives a statistical analysis of all values recorded, and once again, mean values for the NEURO group are of reduced magnitude. The same may be concluded by observing the descriptive box plots shown in Fig. 5.11. As expected force increment caused a significant change in values for all three groups, Table 5.35, whereas no significant differences were noticeable with the Mann-Whitney test, performed and presented in Table 5.36.

Figure 5.12, shows the histogram distribution of the Pmax parameter. The first conclusion that may be drawn from the histograms is that there is a shift towards higher values as expected for all three groups, since they are all influenced significantly with FL. Furthermore in comparison with the NOR group, values of the NEURO group are smaller.

The maximum power parameter also presents contradicting results although one would expect that it would be a straightforward parameter. Merletti and De Luca

1989 concluded that a quasi-linear relationship between signal amplitude and force existed. In contrast larger muscles (biceps brachii, deltoid, soleus etc), present a non-linear relationship with force increment. This statement is in agreement with the findings of this study where the maximum power was found to increase considerably with force but not in a linear matter. Linssen et al (1993), at 80% of MVC noticed an initial increase in SEMG amplitude between the first 50 seconds in a 60 second cycle. This was contributed to changes in the firing frequency of individual motor units, recruitment of additional motor units and synchronization between MU firing patterns. Roy et al (1989), also contributes the increase in amplitude that can be observed with fatigue to the second order effect caused by low pass filtering of the body tissues in SEMG. Although the recording in this study was 5 seconds, a much lesser recording time than the one mentioned in Linssen's study, no decrease in amplitude for any force level was observed.

6.6.5 Total power

The standard error of the mean values SEM, that are smaller in the NOR group remain unaffected with FL. The CV values decrease with FL for the NOR group, whereas they do not follow a consistent pattern with FL for the two patient groups. The interquartile ranges increase with FL for all three groups, (Tables 5.37, 5.38 and 5.39). When all values are compared among the three groups (Table 5.40), differences between the MYO group and the two other groups are visible. This is an interesting finding, when one considers that as in peripheral neuropathies, EMG recordings from a diseased myopathy subject, may present increased or decreased MUAP amplitude and/or duration. This phenomenon makes diagnosis at some instances, difficult and confusing. Here, however, a distinct and significant difference was found between MYO subjects and the other two groups of subjects, based on the recording amplitude. The increased numerical values recorded from the MYO group and their dispersion may be seen graphically at Fig. 5.13, showing the descriptive box-plots for the three groups. Values tend to increase from one FL to another and the increase is significant, Table 5.41 for all three groups, with the exemption of one transition in the MYO group in the mid force region. As mentioned earlier, values recorded from the MYO group are higher than those recorded from the other two groups. These differences were large enough to classify

significant differences between the MYO group and the other two groups, Table 5.42.

The histogram distribution presented in Fig. 5.14, shows a shift towards higher values with FL for all three groups, which was expected since all three groups are influenced significantly with FL.

Pattichis et al (1993) has shown that the total power increases steadily with FL for all three groups of subjects, as this study has shown. Bilodeau et al (1995) also examined the distribution of power in the power spectrum, by examining the $P_{25\%}$, and $P_{75\%}$, the half power range (HPR) and their influence with force contraction. They have found that there is a loss of power in the high frequency region only with subjects who present an increased skin fold layer (TB muscle of female subjects). Otherwise $P_{75\%}$, which is a very good representation of power distribution in the high frequency region, remains constant or increases. This study has found a constant increase of $P_{75\%}$, with force level, which is in agreement with Gander et al (1985).

6.7 Bi-frequency domain analysis

The advantages of bi-frequency domain analysis have been mentioned in detail elsewhere in this study. The idea behind performing this type of analysis was to eliminate or reduce possible drawbacks due to the non-Gaussianity of the SEMG recorded. Seven parameters have been examined. The Bispectrum peak amplitude B_{max} , the signals gaussianity sg , the signals linearity sl , the Bispectrum peaks amplitude location in the x and y direction B_{fx} and B_{fy} , as well as their slope $B_{fxslope}$ and $B_{fyslope}$ have been examined. However Bi-frequency analysis, besides the fact that has offered reliable results not depending upon assumptions, did not produce any crystal clear distinctions among groups. Having said that, from the analysis performed, differences have been found between the three groups of subjects for the B_{max} parameter, and between the NOR group and the NEURO group, for all parameters related to the Bispectrum peaks location and slope.

6.7.1 Bispectrum peak amplitude

The logarithmic values of those recorded were calculated and presented here.

The bispectrum peak amplitude followed the same pattern (i.e. increased with FL), as the maximum power did for the NOR and the MYO group alone. It did not increase consistently with FL for the NEURO group.

From Tables 5.43, 5.44 and 5.45, the increase in mean, median and interquartile ranges is obvious, whereas the SD, SEM and CV values remain fairly constant.

When the three groups were compared together Table 5.46, differences in the mean and median values may be noticed, with those of the NEURO group being smaller. The corresponding descriptive box-plots Fig. 5.15, show the value distribution and dispersion, showing clearly the many near and far (to a lesser degree) outliers, in the NOR group. The reason, although investigated could not be traced. The increase of Bispectrum peak amplitude values with FL, was classified as significant (with only one exemption in the NOR group), whereas generally the increase of FL did not cause a significant change in values for the two patient groups (with a few exemptions), Table 5.47. When all values are compared, significant differences were detected between the three groups of subjects, Table 5.48.

Figure 5.16 shows the histogram distribution of the logarithm of the Bispectrum peak amplitude. There is a continuous shift towards higher values with FL for the NOR group and for the MYO group up to 70% MVC but not for the NEURO group. The Bispectrum peak amplitude may easily be considered as the maximum amplitude of the power spectrum in the bi-frequency domain. Hence one might have expected that the behaviour of the two parameters would be the same. They are not the same in two respects:

(i) Although maximum power values increase with FL for all three group, the same does not occur with Bispectrum peak amplitude, which increases only for the NOR group and (ii) No significant differences were detected when all values of the maximum power were compared (Table 5.36), whereas only significant differences

were detected when Bispectrum peak amplitude values of the three groups were compared, (Table 5.48).

In both of the above statements, it is obvious that the Bispectrum analysis has helped towards distinguishing between normals and patients, whereas the power spectrum through the maximum power analysis has failed. Hence this may be considered as a great advantage of the Bispectrum analysis.

Unfortunately no studies investigating this parameter were traced in the literature, so a comparison with other studies is not possible.

6.7.2 Gaussianity test

In this study, the Gaussianity of the signal was found to improve with FL increment, (i.e. values were reduced), up to 70% MVC for the NOR and the MYO group, (Tables 5.49, 5.50 and 5.51). This indicates that the signal distribution approximates a normal distribution with FL increase up to 70% MVC and then becomes non-normally distributed once again.

When all values recorded are compared Table 5.52, considerable smaller values for the SD, SEM and CV may be seen for the NOR group. Many outliers (near and far) have been recorded and presented with the corresponding box-plots of Fig. 5.17, which also show that FL does not influence considerably the values, as listed in Table 5.53. However the increased value recorded for the NEURO group, enables this group to be distinguishable and significantly different from the other two groups. Histogram distribution, presented in Fig. 5.18 shows the wide spread of values caused by the near and far outliers.

Only one paper was traced in the literature examining this parameter, that of Pattichis et al (1993). The results of the two studies compare similarly for the NOR subjects and MYO patients, where the Gaussianity was found to increase with increasing FL, up to 70% and then reducing again. Pattichis has shown that the same applies for a MND patient, but this present study has shown opposing results.

6.7.3 Linearity test

The linearity test involves deciding whether or not the estimated bicoherence is constant. A high value indicates tendency towards constancy, whereas a low value indicates highly non-constancy. From the results obtained, it may be seen that the mean values of bicoherence are more constant at high force level, i.e. 100% of MVC for the NOR and MYO groups and at 50% for the NEURO group (Tables 5.55, 5.56 and 5.57). At the same FLs the signals present their highest degree of non-Gaussianity (Tables 5.49, 5.50 and 5.51). As can be seen the SD, SEM and CV values fluctuate considerably between low to high FLs especially for the two patient groups. When all values are compared, Table 5.58, no major differences among the three groups may be detected. The large amount of outliers especially for the NOR group prevents a valuable comparison among groups through the descriptive box-plots, Fig. 5.19. As expected, since FL increment caused either no or very small differences in values no significant differences were detected, Table 5.59. No significant differences were detected either among groups, when all values recorded were compared, Table 5.60. Fig. 5.20 showing the histogram distribution of the test for linearity shows clearly that due to the large dispersion of values distribution is quite broad and hence not much may be concluded from this graph alone.

In all three groups of subjects, Pattichis et al (1993), has shown that the linearity of the signal is maximum at MVC. This study has shown the same for the NOR and MYO groups but the same does not apply for the NEURO group.

6.7.4 Bispectrum peak amplitude location in the x-direction

Both mean and median values of this parameter, not only are not influenced significantly with FL, but remain fairly constant for the NOR group (53-57), whereas for the MYO group the spreading is a bit higher (53-63) and for the NEURO group (55-71), (Tables 5.61, 5.62, 5.63). Table 5.64 presents the analysis of all recorded values, showing differences between the NOR group and the NEURO group. Figure 5.21 shows the descriptive analysis plots for the three groups, showing also the large amount of near and far outliers. Increase from one FL to another did not cause any significant difference, Table 5.65, although the increased values recorded for the

NEURO group makes this group distinguishable and significantly different from the NOR group, Table 5.66.

Figure 5.22 shows the histogram distribution of the Bfx parameter. Force increment does not influence, as can be seen, the distribution of values.

Unfortunately no studies have been traced in the literature, examining this parameter on SEMG or EMG studies so no comparison is possible.

6.7.5 Bispectrum peak amplitude location in the y-direction

The behaviour of the Bispectrum peak in the y-direction is very similar to that of the Bispectrum peak in the x-direction. The values of the NOR group are smaller than the corresponding values of Bfx, but also remain quite constant with force (37-40). Once again the MYO group mean values are spreading more (38-47), with the NEURO group mean values being (44-55). Tables 5.67, 5.68 and 5.69 give the statistical analysis for the three groups, showing clearly that FL does not influence this parameter. When all values are recorded and compared, once again the NEURO group presents higher mean and median values, Table 5.70, which may be seen also from the descriptive box-plot analysis of Fig. 5.23. This presents considerably less outliers compared to the corresponding Bfx parameter.

No significant differences in values were detected with force increase, Table 5.71, however as with Bfx, there is a significant difference between all the values recorded for the NOR and NEURO groups, Table 5.72. Figure 5.24, shows the histogram distribution of values for the Bfy parameter and as can be seen the FL does not influence the distribution of values.

No other published studies have analysed this parameter, hence no comparison of results is possible.

6.7.6 Slope of the maximum amplitude of the Bispectrum in the x-direction

A consistent decrease in the mean values of this parameter has been recorded for the NOR group, Table 5.73, whereas the same does not apply for the two patient groups, Tables 5.74 and 5.75. By analysing all values recorded, differences were noted between the NEURO group and the other two groups, Table 5.76, which may be seen also at the descriptive box-plots analysis Fig. 5.25, presenting higher spread of values for the NEURO group, with higher mean and median values and only a few outliers. No force transition for any group was classified as significant, Table 5.77. However significant differences were detected among values of the NEURO group with the two other groups, Table 5.78.

Figure 5.26 shows the histogram distribution of values for the Bfxslope parameter. There is a shift towards lower values for the NOR group but not for the other patient groups.

6.7.7 Slope of the maximum amplitude of the Bispectrum in the y-direction

The mean and median values for all groups remain fairly unchanged with FL, with the SD and the CV being approximately the same between groups, whereas, the SE for the NOR group being considerably smaller, Tables 5.79, 5.80 and 5.81. When all values are analysed together, Table 5.82, higher values may be noted for the NEURO group, especially with the CV and the P_{95%} quartile range. As expected once values were not influenced with FL, no significant differences were detected in values with FL increment. However once again as with all parameters, of the bispectrum peak amplitude location and slope, significant differences were detected between NEURO and NOR subjects, Table 5.84.

Figure 5.28, shows the histogram distribution of values for this parameter and as can be seen FL does not influence the distribution of values with these being higher for the NEURO group at higher FLs.

For the last two parameters (Bfxslope and Bfyslope), as for all parameters relevant with the Bispectrum peak amplitude, location and slope, no other studies have been traced in the literature, so comparison of these results and others is not possible.

However these results, from the large group of 94 normal subjects and 20 patients, may be used as a reference data bank and compared with future studies.

6.8 Repeatability

A subject was asked to perform this test to verify the repeatability of measurements taken during the same day. Results presented in Table 5.86 show that the sets of measurements are extremely similar. The mean of all 70 recorded values was 63.8 (2nd effort) and 63.7 (3rd effort) for the two sets, the standard deviation 58.9 and 60.5 respectively and the standard error of the mean 7.0 and 7.2. The coefficient of variation was 92.3 and 94.9 percent for the two sets, whereas the median values were 60.0 and 57.5 respectively. The semi-inter quartile ranges, the 5th, 25th, 75th and 95th ranges are also very similar. A graphical representation of the value distribution of the two sets of values is shown in Fig. 5.29. The mean \pm standard error of the mean values, are plotted for four selected parameters, those of turns per second, median frequency, total power and the bispectrum peak amplitude. Table 5.87 lists the SD, SEM and CV values for the four selected parameters at the five FLs. The standard error of the mean for the turns per second parameter ranges from 0.9-5.6, whereas the corresponding ranges for the median frequency, total power and the bispectrum amplitude are 2.9-7.9, 0.005-0.12 and 9.3-22.6 respectively. Falla et al (2002) listed in his study the SEM results obtained from various muscles and from various research groups. One of those studies examined the repeatability of the mean frequency on the biceps brachii muscle and hence results may be compared with a degree of caution, with the results obtained from the median frequency from this study. Hence this study obtained repeatability measurements for the median frequency between 2.4 and 7.9 and that reported by Rainoldi et al (1999) was 4.4.

In overall the repeatability measurements being an indication of possible sources of errors caused mainly by electrode misplacement show small variability only, and hence a reliable assumption as to the set-up effectiveness may be drawn.

6.9 Reliability

The first objective of reliability measurements applied in this study, was to investigate whether an arbitrary sample of subjects irrespective of age or gender, provided significantly different recordings between two sets of measurements. The

second objective of applying reliability measurements was to investigate whether increasing or decreasing force levels influenced significantly the analysis. It is reminded that in this study all recordings started with 100% followed by 70, 50, 30 and 10% MVC, following a decreasing drift, which reduced even more the small chances of muscle fatigue.

The time interval between the two sets of decreasing efforts ranged from 24 hours to 24 months, whereas the investigation of decreasing-increasing force influence was performed in the same day. Table 5.88 lists, subject's code, age, gender, time elapsed between the two decreasing recordings, p-value, whether the difference was classified as significant or non-significant, the p-value between the decreasing and increasing efforts and once again whether the difference was classified as significant or non-significant. Results presented in Table 5.88 were produced after appropriate pairs of the 70 values (5 force levels x 14 parameters) were compared. Table 5.89 gives the mean, standard deviation, standard error of the mean, the coefficient of variation, the median values, the semi inter quartile range, the 5th, 25th, 75th and 95th percentile value, for the ten participating normal subjects. Values are given for the 1st and 2nd downward and the upward force efforts. These values were produced by examining once again all 70 values, (5 force levels x 14 parameters). From Table 5.88, it may be seen that significant differences exist between the two decreasing force efforts, for subjects GP and SK, and between the decreasing and increasing force efforts for subjects SK and MV. Although large differences for these subjects are not clearly indicated in Table 5.89, it should be remembered that the Wilcoxon signed-rank test does not simply detect differences between the medians of related samples, but takes into account the magnitude of the observations, once these observations can be quantified. It is for this reason that the Wilcoxon signed rank test is more powerful and accurate than the similar sign test. Differences in reliability measurements among the ten subjects also, were examined for certain parameters, and plots (Figs. 5.34 to 5.37), give the mean \pm standard error of the mean for the turns per second, the median frequency, the total power and the bispectrum peak amplitude, at a low force level (10% MVC), a medium force level (50% MVC) and a high force level (100% MVC). These Figs. have been developed by comparing the four values for each subject at the corresponding FL and parameter. As mentioned earlier each FL was performed twice and since the experiment was also performed

twice, the total number of efforts for each FL was four. From Fig. 5.34, as can be seen most values are equal to zero at 10%, however the same does not apply for 50% and 100% MVC. The average percentage errors are 36.4 and 25.4 for all 10 subjects at 50 and 100% MVC respectively. Figure 5.35 plots the mean \pm SEM for the median frequency. At 10% the highest percentage error is 13% for subject 4, at 50% 11.6% for subject 3 and at 100% MVC 11.4% for subject 7. The average percentage errors for all ten normal subjects are 5.1, 6.6 and 4.4%.

The reliability of the total power P_{total} parameter, for the ten normal subjects is illustrated at Fig. 5.36. At 10% MVC, the highest percentage error was that of subject 3 and was 250% (being extremely high), whereas the average group percentage error was 48%. At 50% MVC the same subject presented the highest error being equal to 30% with the group average equal to 15%. Finally at 100% MVC, once again subject 3 presented a high percentage error equal to 25% with the group average equal to 12%.

The last parameter examined was the logarithm of the Bispectrum peak amplitude. This parameter was selected because it is a representative parameter of the bi-frequency domain. Figure 5.37 shows the mean values \pm SEM for the 10 selected normal subjects. Subject 9 at 10% presented the highest error equal to 44%, with the group average equal to 10%. At 50% MVC, the same subject gave the highest error equal to 41% and the group average was 9.6%. And finally at 100% MVC, once again subject 9 presented the highest error equal to 38% with the group average equal to 9.5%. From the above it may be seen that when a subject presents a high percentage error for the total power parameter and the bispectrum peak amplitude parameter, it presents the highest value from the group for all three FL selected.

The mean and median power frequencies were among the parameters selected by many researchers examining the aspect of repeatability. Rainoldi et al (1999) had found statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) differences in $1/4$ to $2/3$ of the experimental sessions, examining the mean frequency, the average rectified value and the muscle fibre conduction velocity. The same group found an average standard deviation among subjects for the mean power frequency equal to 11-14 depending upon the force level, as compared with 9.2-14.8 found in this study for the median frequency

for force levels 10, 50 and 100% MVC. Felici et al (1997), examining the initial values of P_{fmed} for six normal subjects in five consecutive days at 80% MVC, found that the standard deviation of these average values was 4.5% of the mean. Daamen et al (1990), found an average standard deviation for the mean power frequency equal to 11.5 Hz between individuals, which was contributed to the properties of the Motor Unit, muscle fibre type, tissue impedance and the localization of the electrodes.

6.10 Age analysis

As mentioned both age and gender analysis were performed for the normal group only and were based on three different methods:

- (i) The Wilcoxon signed-rank test was used to classify three FL transitions within each age group and compare corresponding results with those taken from the entire group. A FL transition from low (10%) to mid (50%), from mid to high (100%) and from low to high FL were selected. Although as expected from such a detailed analysis, differences may exist for some parameters and between certain age groups and the total 94 normal subject group, the overall conclusion, especially between a transition from a low to a high FL is that age dependence examined showed no significant differences. The only major exemption concerns the slope of the Bispectrum peak amplitude in the x and y-directions, where all the FL transitions are classified as significant (Tables 5.90, 5.91 and 5.92) when the overall group is examined, whereas to a great majority no significant differences were found within age groups. Merletti et al (1992 and 2002) examined age dependence using the same method with SEMG recordings. In the first study results from an adult group (18-43 years) were “borrowed” from Knaflitz et al (1990), and were compared with an elderly group (65-84 years) examined by the Merletti group. In both cases 20 second recordings were obtained from the tibialis anterior muscle at 20 and 80% MVC. Two spectral parameters were examined, the P_{fmed} and the P_{fmean} . Results had shown that only the P_{fmean} increased significantly ($p < 0.01$) with FL transition in the elderly group, whereas both spectral parameters increased significantly for the adult group.

However these results are contradicting with results obtained from the same group ten years later by Merletti et al (2002). The more recent paper showed that no significant differences existed between an elderly group (67-86 years) and a young group (23-34 years) with increment of FL from 20 to 60% MVC for the P_{fmean} parameter. This study has shown that there is a consistent decrease (and not an increase) of P_{fmean} and P_{fmed} with increase of FL. This decrease is significant ($p < 0.05$), when all 94 subjects are taken as a group and for most individual age groups. Hence the results of this present study are contradicting with the results of the two studies by Merletti mentioned above.

- (ii) The age analysis based on the coefficient of variation, Tables 5.93-106 and Figs. 5.38-5.51, shows that both time domain parameters have similar coefficient of variations, whereas the three frequency components P_{fmed}, P_{fmean} and P_{fx} have all very small CVs. On the contrary the CV for the P_{max} parameter is quite high especially at young and elderly subjects. The CVs for the P_{total} are significantly smaller, but even smaller are those of the sg parameter. All the rest parameters are nearly of the same order. Unfortunately no studies examining age dependence using this method were traced in the literature.
- (iii) A graphical representation of the influence of age on four selected parameters, using descriptive box-plots are shown on Figs. 5.52- 5.55. For each of the parameters selected, three sets of box-plots are shown one for 10, 50 and 100% MVC. For the turns per second, at 10 and 50% MVC, the age groups 31<40 and 61<70 present a large parametric percentile range. The same applies for the group 61<70 at 100% MVC. A large parametric percentile range is present at the age group 51<60 for the P_{fmed} parameter, whereas the total power parameter, presents the highest parametric percentile ranges at the age groups 31<40 and 61<70 for all three selected FLs. The Bispectrum peak amplitude of the age group 41<50 at 10% presents a parametric percentile range larger than any other age group at any FL. The two studies mentioned above by Merletti et al (1992 and 2002), examined

age dependence, looking at the initial values of Pf_{med} and Pf_{mean} for the same age groups. In the 1992 study, only the initial values of Pf_{mean} at 20% MVC were significantly different between the two groups of subjects (18-43 years and 65-84 years). Median frequency at 20% MVC and both spectral parameters at 20 and 80% MVC did not show any significant differences. In the other study by Merletti et al (2002), although initial values of the younger subjects were higher than the corresponding values of the elderly group, differences were classified as non-significant.

6.11 Gender analysis

The influence of gender was once again examined with the aid of three techniques; The Wilcoxon signed rank test ($p < 0.05$), the coefficient of variation and the continuous descriptive analysis method enabling a visual representation of value distribution. A separate discussion on the results obtained by each method follows:

- (i) Wilcoxon signed rank test. Three FL transitions (the same used for the age analysis) were used to classify changes for the 14 parameters examined within three groups; group 1 including all 94 normal subjects, group 2 including 38 female subjects and group 3 including 56 male subjects. Transitions were classified as significant ($p < 0.05$) or non-significant and results were compared. In nearly 1/3 (5 out of 14) parameters examined for FL transition 10 to 50% MVC (Table 5.107), the female group gave different results than group 1 (all subjects) and group 3 (male subjects), with the last two groups coinciding perfectly. For FL transition from 50 to 100% MVC (Table 5.108), all results were perfectly matched, whereas for FL transitions 10 to 100% MVC (Table 5.109), only 2 parameters of the female group gave different results.
- (ii) The coefficient of variation (CV) was estimated for all 14 parameters within the two groups of genders and compared, (Table 5.110). Besides though, the CV, mean values, standard deviation and the standard error of the mean were calculated. The mean values and the standard deviation values for the two groups of genders are quite similar. A few exemptions concern the parameters of the position and

slope of the Bispectrum peak. As expected the coefficient of variation, was large for parameters like the maximum power, where a large range of values was recorded, but also for parameters like the test of linearity and the location of the bispectrum peak amplitude in the x and y direction. The standard error of the mean provides an even more accurate measure of dispersion, since it takes into account the number of samples. By comparing this measure between the two groups, no major differences can be observed between the two groups.

- (iii) A graphical representation of the influence of gender on four selected parameters, using descriptive box-plots are shown on Figs. 5.56- 5.59. For each of the parameters selected three sets of box-plots are shown one for 10, 50 and 100% MVC.

For the first parameter, turns per second t/s, box plots for each gender and for each FL selected look quite similar, with the exemption of the many near outliers present in the male box plot for 10% MVC, which is though to a degree expected due to the large amount of samples. The next parameter examined the median frequency, indicates that the value distribution is similar for all three FL for both genders. The logarithm of the total power P_{total} , has shown a larger dispersion (larger interquartile range) for the female group at 10% MVC but a larger for the male group at 50 and 100% MVC. In the last two force levels, the male group presented higher mean and median values. For the last parameter examined the logarithm of the Bispectrum peak amplitude, far as well as near outliers were detected, with the interquartile ranges being similar.

Gender influence with the aid of SEMG was examined also by Bilodeau et al (1992), who investigated differences between the two genders from 5-second ramp contractions from the triceps brachii, the anconeus muscle and the biceps brachii muscle. Particularly for the BB muscle, significant differences (two –way analyses of variance ANOVA ($p < 0.05$)), between the two genders were detected for the P_{fmean} and the P_{fmed} spectral parameters. These parameters increased more in male subjects than in female subjects. The group found significant differences between the two genders for the P_{fmed} muscle but not for the P_{fmean} , although this

parameter was also smaller for female subjects. The standard error of the mean for the P_{fmean} parameter was calculated by the Bilodeau et al (1992) group, to be between 4.2 to 7.1 (3.5) for male subjects and between 2.2 and 5.5 (4.9) for female subjects, whereas for the P_{fmed} parameter values were between 5.7 and 8.4 (2.9) and 2.6 and 4.9 (4.1) for male and female subjects respectively. In parenthesis the mean values of the standard error of the mean of this present study are given for easy comparison and as can be seen these are quite comparable. The group by Bilodeau found the coefficient of variation to range between 15-20% which ones again compares favourably with the results of this study, being between 20-24%. Bilodeau contributed differences between the two genders, to the variability in skinfold layer thickness and the fibre type characteristics, although student t-test used by his group, classified the 1 mm differences in skinfold layer for the BB muscle between the two genders as non-significant.

6.12 Correlation analysis

The Spearman correlation coefficient (being the non-parametric alternative of Pearson correlation coefficient) was used to examine all possible pairs among the 14 parameters. Parameter pairs presenting a good or excellent coefficient for the normal group and the corresponding parameter pairs for the two patient groups are listed in Table 5.111. The reasoning of performing correlation analysis is to investigate whether a more easily calculated parameter reflects the characteristics of a more time consuming and complicated parameter. More easily calculated parameters are those of the time domain t/s and zc/s , which were found to have a good correlation with the maximum and total power parameters, (for normal subjects), but not with the mean, median, or maximum frequencies. Results are somehow different for the two patient groups. The two time domain parameters present an excellent correlation between themselves and with P_{total} , but not with P_{max} for the myopathy patients. On the contrary an excellent correlation exists for all previous mentioned parameter pairs for neuropathy patients. In contrast to Inbar et al (1986), who found an excellent correlation among the zero crossings and the median frequency, concluding that an estimation of the zero crossings can be used to estimate the median frequency, which is quite often, required. However, interesting enough, the Inbar group did not detect any consistent changes in median frequency or zero crossings with varying tensions, which is of course in opposition to the results of this study,

where the zero crossings were found to increase significantly with force level, whereas the median frequency was found to decrease significantly with force level. Furthermore an excellent correlation exists between Pmax and Ptotal for normal subjects and neuropathy patients. Once again the Pmax parameter for the myopathy patients is not correlated well with Ptotal either. Finally if one examines all remaining parameter pairs of Table 5.111, it could be concluded that results are quite similar except that when Bfy for neuropathy patients is examined. Hence Pmax for myopathy and Bfy for neuropathy patients are not correlated at all with any other parameters. Figure 5.60 shows correlation analysis plots between t/s and zc/s, Pmedian and Pmean, Pmax and Ptotal and finally for Bfxslope and Bfyslope for the three group of subjects, NOR, MYO and NEURO. Differences in the coefficient of correlation are hence clear.

6.13 KNN classification

Tables 5.112 and 5.113 tabulate the KNN classifier performance results for two class models (NORMAL/ABNORMAL), (MYO/NEURO) and for three class models (NOR/MYO/NEURO) respectively. Various models were investigated depending on the number of subjects, number of features and values for k. Models with the same number of NORMAL and ABNORMAL subjects were also investigated to avoid bias due to the higher number of NORMAL subjects. These tables tabulate percentage of correct classifications, %CC, percentage of false positives, %FP, percentage of false negatives, %FN, sensitivity, SE, specificity, SP, recall RE and precision, PR.

The upper part of Table 5.112, presents classification results between NORMAL and ABNORMAL subjects. The ABNORMAL group includes both MYO and NEURO patients. When all features are used (14 parameters at five force levels), and for the same number of subjects (18 NORMAL and 18 ABNORMAL), the highest value of % of correct classification score, %CC is 94.4, when the k-value is equal to 1 (model 1). The corresponding values for the % of false positives, %FP, % of false negatives, %FN, sensitivity, SE, specificity, SP, recall, RE and precision PR are 5.6%, 5.6%, 94.4, 94.4, 94.4, and 94.4 respectively. These values suggest that: (i) there is a 5.6% possibility that the system using this particular model, may classify a normal subject as abnormal, (ii) there is a 5.6% possibility that the system may diagnose an

abnormal subject as normal, (iii) there is high possibility that the system will detect any event if this is present, 94.4, (iv) if an event is absent the system will diagnose this, with an accuracy of 94.4, (v) the system presents 94.4 recall, (correctly positive diagnosis made by the system divided by the number of positive diagnosis made by the physician and (vi) the precision of the system also reaches 94.4. Very good results were produced by the system, also with k being equal to 3. The values of %CC, %FP, %FN, SE, SP, RE, PR, obtained with this model (model 2), were 91.7%, 0.0%, 16.7%, 83.3%, 100.0, 83.3, 100.0, respectively. Models with five parameters that presented significant differences were also investigated. These parameters were: turns and zero crossings per second, median frequency, total power and maximum bispectrum peak amplitude. Therefore using these five parameters for the five force levels investigated, 25 input feature vectors were used. The best KNN models for 18 NORMAL and 18 ABNORMAL subjects, with 25 input features vector, was derived for k being equal to 5, (model 7), where the %CC, %FP, %FN, SE, SP, RE, and PR were, 69.4%, 22.2%, 38.9%, 61.1, 77.8, 61.1 and 73.3 respectively.

When 91 NORMALS, 20 ABNORMAL and all 70 features were used, the highest %CC score obtained was 86.5% (model 9), with the remaining features being equal to 3.3%, 60%, 40.0, 96.7, 44.4, and 72.7 in the same order as mentioned above. The best KNN model for the same number of subjects but with the 25 features was model 13, providing a %CC score equal to 82.9%. The remaining values obtained were, 7.7%, 60.0%, 40, 92.3, 44.4, and 53.3. As mentioned though earlier, with these models there is a bias due to the higher number of normal subjects.

Following the classification of a subject as ABNORMAL by the two class models of NORMAL/ABNORMAL, then the MYO/NEURO models can be used to classify a subject into one of these disease categories. The lower part of Table 5.112 tabulates the KNN classifier performance results for this classification. Both groups present nearly equal number of patients (11 myopathy and 9 neuropathy). With all 70 features used the highest %CC score is 65.0%, model 20. The respective values for %FP, %FN, SE, SP, RE and PR are, 45.4%, 22.2%, 77.8, 54.5, 35.0 and 58.3 respectively. When the 25 features were used, the highest %CC score obtained was 70%, model 24. The remaining values for %FP, %FN, SE, SP, RE, and PR were 36.4%, 22.2%, 77.8, 63.4, 35.0 and 63.6 respectively.

Table 5.113 presents classification between three groups (NOR/MYO/NEURO). For the same number of subjects (9 for each group), and with 70 features, the highest %CC score obtained was 59.3%, model 26. The rest of the measures calculated were, 0%, 46.2%, 53.8, 100.0, 38.9 and 100.0 for the %FP, %FN, SE, SP, RE and PR respectively. These Figs. did not improve when the selected 25 features were used. The highest %CC score was 51.9%, model 30, with the remaining measures being equal to 44.4%, 25%, 75.0, 55.6, 50.0 and 69.2 in the same order as mentioned above.

When the number of NORMAL subjects equals the number of ABNORMAL (18 NOR, 9 MYO and 9 NEURO subjects), the %CC score increases slightly. With 70 features the highest %CC score obtained was 66.7%, model 34. The %FP, %FN, SE, SP, RE and PR values were 5.9%, 38.5%, 61.5, 94.1, 44.4 and 88.0 respectively. With the 25 features, the %CC remained relatively low, highest value obtained 61.1%, model 38. Remaining measures were 25.0%, 28.6%, 71.4, 75.0, 55.6 and 71.4.

However, when 91 NOR/ 11 MYO/ 9 NEURO subjects are used, the %CC score increases. For 70 features the highest %CC score obtained was 82.9%, model 41. The rest of the measures were, 3.3%, 75.0%, 25.0, 96.7, 22.2 and 57.1. With 25 features, the highest %CC score was 77.5%, model 45. Remaining measures were 7.7%, 85.7%, 14.3, 92.3, 11.1 and 22.2.

It should be emphasized that patients selected by the Neurologist and referred for SEMG in this study were randomly selected and did not present a homogeneous group having the same MRC score. Moreover many myopathic diseases at some stages present characteristics of neuropathy disorders and vice versa (personal communication with Dr. Th. Kyriakides from the Cyprus Institute of Neurology and Genetics). Taking into consideration the above, it is clear that high scores for the percentage of correct classifications, sensitivity, specificity, recall, and precision and low scores for percentages of false positive and negative are quite difficult to be achieved by any system for SEMG analysis. It is thus believed that a non-invasive system presenting a correct classifications score, sensitivity, specificity, recall and precision equal to 94.4 and only 5.6% for both false positive and negative can be

used successfully to discriminate between NORMAL and ABNORMAL subjects. Furthermore, a correct classifications score equal to 70%, obtained between MYO and NEURO subjects, despite the drawbacks present due to the method of patient selection and the many different diseases present, can be widely accepted in the medical community.

Abel et al (1995), found a percentage of correct classifications of 75% when 12 normal subjects were compared with 18 myopathy and 15 neuropathy patients examined with needle EMG. Turns analysis and small segments analysis were used. However authors concluded that the classification methods used, did not offer better results than the Interference Pattern analysis and could not by any means match the diagnostic success of an experienced clinician.

Abou-Chadi et al (2001) used three versions of ANN to facilitate automatic classification of SEMG. With unsupervised techniques, the correct classification score reached 80%, when five normal subjects and five myopathy subjects were selected from a pool of 14 normal subjects and 14 patients. Recordings were performed for 5 seconds at 50% MVC. It is noted that for a two-class classification this study has reached a 94.4% of correct classifications score. Abou-Chadi et al (2001), have reached the conclusion that when SEMG is properly processed, it may provide the physician with a diagnostic assisting tool.

6.14 SOFM mapping

Twelve SOFM plots were investigated as shown in Chapter 5. These plots are discussed below. First of all by experimenting it was found that a grid size of 5x5 was adequate for models representing 36 subjects 18 NORMAL/18 ABNORMAL, 20 subjects 11 MYO/9 NEURO, 27 subjects 9 NOR/9 MYO/9 NEURO, and 36 subjects 18 NOR/9 MYO/9 NEURO. A grid size of 10x10 was chosen for models representing 111 subjects 91 NORMAL/20 ABNORMAL, and 91 NOR/11 MYO/9 NEURO.

Figures 5.61 and 5.62 illustrate mapping for 18 NORMAL and 18 ABNORMAL subjects for 70 and 25 features respectively. From Fig. 5.61 it may be seen that a clear separation between the two groups exists with the vast majority of the

NORMAL subjects distributed on the right part of the grid and the ABNORMAL subjects on the left part of the grid. A visual discrimination when 25 features are used is not that clear, as can be seen from Fig. 5.62. When however a larger number of normal subjects are used, Figs. 5.63 and 5.64, for 70 and 25 features respectively, the ABNORMAL subjects are more clearly distinguished. In Fig. 5.63, most of the ABNORMAL subjects are covering the top and left side and the NORMAL subjects the centre of the grid. In Fig. 5.64 most of the ABNORMAL subjects are covering the lower right hand corner. SOFM plots, mapping the 11 myopathy and 9 neuropathy patients for 70 and 25 features are presented in Figs. 5.65 and 5.66 respectively. As can be seen there is no clear discrimination.

Figures 5.67 and 5.68 show the distribution of three class models for 9 NOR/9 MYO/9 NEURO for 70 and 25 features respectively. There is no clear visual discrimination among the three groups. The discrimination of the three groups is slightly better in the next two Figs, Figs 5.69 and 5.70, indicating the distribution between 18 NOR/9 MYO/9 NEURO patients, for 70 and 25 features respectively. However as can be seen the discrimination has been improved only slightly. Finally when 91 NOR/11 MYO/9 NEURO are used Figs. 5.71 and 5.72 discrimination is improved having in mind the bias due to the large number of normal subjects.

Abel et al (1995), using needle EMG and SOFM models, managed to correctly recognise one of the two diseases (myopathy and neuropathy), in about 60-70% of the cases. Christodoulou et al (1999) using SOFM as a classification model reached a percentage of correct classifications score of 87.5%, while comparing 12 normal subjects, 13 myopathy and 15 MND patients in needle EMG (motor unit action potential analysis). However this result was obtained with needle recording and not with surface as in this study. Furthermore it must be noted that the neuropathy group of the Christodoulou's study was rather homogeneous, with all suffering from MND.

6.15 Suggested system

Based on the results obtained in this study, a simple diagnostic system is proposed for recording, analysing and classifying SEMG signals. This system can easily be implemented based on the following procedure that can be used to study SEMG

variability with force level or classify a new recording (from a subject under investigation) as NOR, MYO or NEURO:

1. Acquire SEMG from the biceps brachii muscle for 5 seconds at 10%, 30%, 50%, 70% and 100% of MVC.
2. Extract from the recorded signals, the following parameters in the:
 - (i) Time Domain: t/s and zc/s
 - (ii) Frequency Domain: P_{fmed}, P_{fmean}, P_{fx}, P_{total}, and P_{max}
 - (iii) Bi-frequency Domain: sg, sl, B_{max}, B_{fx}, B_{fy}, B_{fxslope}, B_{fyslope}.
3. Examine the influence of FL on these parameters and compare values recorded with the mean values listed for each group, using the Mann-Whitney test. Identify significant differences. It is noted that the increase of force level affects certain parameters differently for each group.
4. Perform KNN cluster analysis for NORMAL/ABNORMAL classification using model 1 of Table 5.112, 70 features and k=1. If the subject is classified as NORMAL, there is no need to proceed. If, however, the subject is classified as ABNORMAL perform KNN cluster analysis for MYO/NEURO classification using model 24 of Table 5.112, 25 features and k=7.
5. Perform KNN cluster analysis for NOR/MYO/NEURO classification using model 34 of Table 5.113, 70 features and k=3.
6. Compare classification of step 4 and 5. If the classification agrees, i.e. the subject under investigation was classified as belonging to the same class by both models, then the result is given with high confidence level, otherwise with low.
7. Visualise the mapping of the subject under investigation on the SOFM map for:
 - (i) NORMAL/ABNORMAL (model 1, Table 5.112) and in the MYO/NEURO (model 24, Table 5.112) if the subject is mapped as ABNORMAL.
 - (ii) NOR/MYO/NEURO (model 34, Table 5.113)

The proposed system can easily be applied for the collection of more cases covering different neuromuscular disorders. In addition it can be applied for the collection of more cases for monitoring the progression of the degree of severity of a disorder of the response to treatment.

Chapter 7
Conclusions

Chapter 7

CONCLUSIONS

7.1 Conclusions

In this work, the usefulness of SEMG in the clinical laboratory was investigated. A diagnostic system was developed enabling the recording, analysis and classification of surface electromyography signals. SEMG signals were analysed in the time, frequency and bi-frequency domains at different levels of force. The system is characterized by its convenience, simplicity and fast response.

The system was evaluated in the clinical laboratory on 94 subjects (with no signs or any family history of a neuromuscular disorder) and on twenty patients suffering either from a myopathy (11 patients) or a neuropathy (9 patients). Fourteen parameters were examined for each of the five force levels investigated. The Wilcoxon signed-rank test ($p < 0.05$) was applied to examine the influence of force transition from one force level to another and the Mann-Whitney test was used to examine differences in values recorded between the three groups. Results found were very promising since it was shown that SEMG can be used accurately, quickly and easily to distinguish between the three groups of subjects, since not only the force increment affects differently most parameters examined, but also significant differences were found in the values of the three groups. Age and gender influence were examined on results obtained and no significant influence was found.

Repeatability and reliability measurements on an arbitrary small group of normal subjects gave very good results. Correlation analysis showed that certain parameter pairs presented an excellent or good correlation for the normal group, but this was not always true for the patient groups.

Cluster analysis performed on two classes (a. NORMAL/ABNORMAL and b. MYO/NEURO) and on three classes (NOR/MYO/NEURO), produced high values of correct classifications score, despite the fact that the patient's group was not that homogeneous (patient's disease severity was varying).

Self Organising Feature Maps give visually the mapping of two (a. NORMAL/ABNORMAL and b. MYO/NEURO) and three class models (NOR/MYO/NEURO), with the former group presenting a better discrimination.

Based on the findings of this study, it is concluded that the SEMG system investigated can be used successfully and effectively as an additional tool by the neurophysiologist for the assessment and monitoring of muscle function. It is proposed, that the system will be used “blindly” without sharing any prior information or knowledge about the possible classification of the subject by the referring neurophysiologist. In addition, this system can be further exploited into clinical practise by combining the proposed SEMG system with the clinical assessment, muscle biopsy and, or nerve biopsy data, biochemical findings, and genetic and molecular genetic findings, in a decision support system for the assessment and monitoring of neuromuscular disorders.

7.2 Future work

Suggestions for future work include the following:

- (i) Digital libraries. There is a need for:
 - a. More recordings from patients and if possible from patients suffering from the same type of disorder. The small number of patients examined as compared with the large group of normals, might have influenced results, hence more patient data are considered a necessity.
 - b. Development of a reference data bank with values from other muscles apart from the Biceps Brachii muscle. However to achieve this using the proposed system, the experimental set-up has to be slightly modified to facilitate recordings from other extremity muscles such as the Gastrocnemius and the Tibialis Anterior. A first set of computer generated and experimental signals is available by SENIAM, Hermens et al (1999).
- (ii) Quantitative analysis. There is a need for the documentation of standardised algorithms that will be applied on reference digital libraries for the analysis, interpretation, and further decision making of SEMG signals. Analysis algorithms in the time, frequency and bi-frequency domains used in this study could be adopted as standardised algorithms for analysis. Furthermore

additional algorithms in the time-frequency domain including wavelet analysis could be investigated, Englehart et al (1999). Also neural networks models could be investigated for the classification of SEMG signals, as has been carried out successfully for needle EMG, Christodoulou et al (1998).

- (iii) Other SEMG applications. The normal SEMG findings reported in this study, although recorded at a short duration (5 seconds) at different force levels, could easily be exploited in the rehabilitation laboratory for monitoring the elderly and the disabled, or in the sports trauma or injuries, or workers subject to stress.
- (iv) Telematics applications. The development of the above technologies will enable their integration to therapy planning systems, department and hospital information systems, archiving and communication systems and internet-based cooperative working environments for teleconsultation, telediagnosis, and telemonitoring (for example patient home monitoring), Pattichis et al (1999).

It is hoped that the proposed system as well as the above directions for future work will contribute towards the improvement of the diagnostic, assessment and monitoring procedures in the SEMG analysis for the offering of advanced healthcare services for the benefit of the patients.

Appendix 1

Experiment Description Given to Subjects

Appendix 1

EXPERIMENT DESCRIPTION GIVEN TO SUBJECTS

Surface EMG for the assessment of neuromuscular disorders

Objective

Early detection and diagnosis are generally accepted today as being essential tools in managing any of the forty or so known neuromuscular disorders.

Clinical examination and laboratory tests help towards managing and even preventing at some instances these neuromuscular disorders through prenatal diagnosis and genetic counselling. Information obtained may lead to the understanding of the nature and hopefully the treatment of these diseases. More specifically laboratory investigations include neurophysiological tests, nerve and muscle biopsies and biochemical analysis and more recently DNA analysis for the localization and identification of genes. Neurophysiological tests are usually carried out using needle electrodes. And apart from the fact that patients are subjected to considerable pain and discomfort, as well as the risk of infection, constant expert supervision is necessary, which renders the whole process quite lengthy. In paediatric examinations and tests in particular, there are even more difficulties in using needle electrodes, and long term monitoring is quite difficult.

In this work, the usefulness of surface electromyography in the clinical laboratory is investigated. A diagnostic system is developed enabling the recording, analysis and classification of surface electromyography signals. Towards this goal, recordings from normal subjects and subjects suffering from a neuromuscular disorder are collected at 10, 30, 50, 70 and 100% of their maximum voluntary contraction.

The system is characterized by its convenience, simplicity and fast response.

Recording procedure

- (i) Once the entire procedure is explained, some personal data will be taken including name, weight, height, gender, age, address, and telephone numbers.
- (ii) Skin preparation of the left biceps brachii muscle, then takes place with alcohol wash.
- (iii) A non-invasive electrode will be attached to the biceps brachii muscle at a specific location. Contact gel is applied on the electrode contacts to improve the conductivity between the skin and electrodes.
- (iv) Volunteers will be asked to lie down on a couch, facing the equipment. A strap will be placed at the wrist of the subject, who will be asked to pull weights at maximum voluntary contraction, (MVC), and to maintain that level for 5 seconds. At the same time the subject must observe the oscilloscope, monitoring the force level. This procedure is performed three times to calculate the average MVC, with a two-minute interval between each effort to avoid fatigue.
- (v) The same procedure is performed at force levels 70, 50, 30 and 10% of MVC, twice at each force level.

It should be stressed that the entire procedure is entirely painless, safe and lasts approximately 20 minutes.

May I take this opportunity to express my personal but also the sincere thanks of the Cyprus Institute of Neurology and Genetics for your time and efforts towards the success of this research.

Prodromos A Kaplanis
Scientific Collaborator
Cyprus Institute of Neurology and Genetics
Nicosia
May 2001

Appendix 2
Subject's Personal Data Form

Appendix 2

SUBJECT'S PERSONAL DATA FORM

SUBJECT'S DATA

Date:31/08/03

Name of subject: Prodromos Kaplanis		Age: 42	
Address: Nicosia		Length of BB: 12 cm	
Telephone: 22354336 / 99614496		Perimeter at centre: 40 cm	
Email: p.a.kaplanis@cytanet.com.cy			
Sex: M/F	Height: 1.70 m	Weight: 70 kg	Left / Right Handed

HISTORY

Has a Neuromuscular disease been clinically verified?	Yes / No
If yes, name the disease N/A	
Physician's name N/A –Volunteer	

EXAMINATION DATA

Recording protocol used			
Electrode configuration		Monopolar / Bipolar / Double differential	
Skin Temperature recorded in degrees: Celsius 33degrees Celsius			
MVC recorded on oscilloscope: 6 volts	% of MVC	File Name	Sensitivity used in μ V per division
Rank the cooperation of the subject from 1 to 5. 1 Being the worst and 5 the best. 1 2 3 4 5 Additional Notes SAMPLE	10	pk10	20
	10	pk102	20
	30	pk30	20
	30	pk302	20
	50	pk50	20
	50	pk502	20
	70	pk70	50
	70	pk702	50
	100	pk100	100
	100	pk1002	100

Appendix 3

Technical Specifications of Data Acquisition Hardware

Appendix 3

TECHNICAL SPECIFICATIONS OF DATA ACQUISITION HARDWARE

A.2.1 Nicolet Viking IV electromyography

A.2.1.1 Computer characteristics

Processor:	An Intel processor 486, with a 33 MHz clock, including a math processor and a separate graphics accelerator board
Memory:	12 Megabytes
Hard disk:	170 Megabytes

A.2.1.2 Amplifiers (2 channels)

Fully electrically isolated amplifiers to IEC 601-1 and BSS 5724 Part 1 Type BF classification.

Input impedance:	$Z_{in} > 1000 \text{ M}\Omega$.
A/D:	12 bit
CMRR:	110 db
Sensitivity:	A sensitivity of 1 $\mu\text{V}/\text{div}$ to 10 mV/div in 13 steps.
Max scale output:	2 V pp
Low filter settings	Selectable 6 or 12 db/octave: 0.2, 0.5, 2, 5, 10, 20, 30, 100, 150, 300, 500,
in Hz (-3 db):	1K, 2K, 5K.
High filter settings	Fixed 12 db/octave, 30, 100, 200, 250, 300, 500, 1K, 1.5K,
in Hz (-3db):	2K, 3K, 5K,
in Hz (-3db):	10K, 20K.
Noise:	$< 0.7 \mu\text{V}$ RMS from 2 Hz – 10 KHz
Notch filter:	50 Hz, 60 Hz, on/off

A.2.1.3 Safety Standards

The system fully conforms with the following standards:

- UL 544 standards(certified by ETL Testing Laboratories INC)

- IEC 601-1 and EN60601-1/1991 international standards (certified by Rheinisch-Westfälischer Technischer Überwachungs-Verein e.V)
- CSA (conforms to C22.2 No. 125-M1984; certified by Warnock Hersey)

A.2.2 Data acquisition Card

The National Instrument board used is coded, MIO-16E-4, and is a high performance and reliable board with broad data acquisition capabilities and with channel-independent gains and ranges. It also offers 10 programmable function inputs.

Analog Input: 16 single-ended, 8 differential channels

Resolution: 12-bit resolution

Scan rate: 250 kS/s multichannel scan rate
500 kS/s single-channel sampling rate

Digital I/O: 8 TTL lines

Counter/Timers: 2 up/down, 24-bit resolution
20 MHz maximum source frequency

Triggering: Analogue and digital

Operating Environment

Ambient temp. 0° to 55° C

Relative humidity: 10% to 90%, non-condensing

Storage Environment:

Ambient temp.: -20° to 70° C

Relative humidity: 5% to 95%, non-condensing

For a selectable voltage range of 1 V (-0.5 to +0.5 V) and a selectable gain of 100, the theoretical resolution of one bit this data acquisition board may offer is

$$\frac{1V}{100 \times 2^{12}} = 2.4 \mu V$$

A.2.2.1 Shielded I/O connector block

The SCB-68, from National Instruments has two general-purpose breadboards suitable for most electronic components. A +5 VDC power supply fused at 800 mA from the DAQ board is required.

Output: 10 mV/°C
Accuracy: ±1° C from 0° to 110° C
Power Req. :+5 VDC (from DAQ board), 1 mA with no signal
conditioning installed,800 mA max (fused)

Operating Environment

Ambient temp. 0° to 55° C
Relative humidity: 10% to 90%, non-condensing

Storage Environment:

Ambient temp.: -20° to 70° C
Relative humidity: 5% to 95%, non-condensing

A.2.3 Electrodes used

This study utilizes a four bar EMG active probe designed by Dispositivi Elettronici Medicali, Italy.

The technical characteristics of the buffer amplifier are:

Gain 0 db
Phase margin 50°
Input Impedance: $Z_{in} > 1000 \text{ M}\Omega$
Output impedance: TL074 as voltage follower
Supply voltage: ± 5V, ± 10V S
Apply current: < 10mA.

General Characteristics:

Weight: 5gr
Size: 17 x 39 mm
Bar material: Silver

Appendix 4
Publications

List of Publications

1. **Kaplanis P A, Pattichis C S, Hadjileontiadis L, Panas S, (2000).** Bispectral Analysis of Surface EMG. 10th Mediterranean Electrotechnical Conference, Melecon, (2):770-773.
2. **Kaplanis P A, Pattichis C S, Hadjileontiadis L, Panas, (2001).** Analysis of Surface EMG using second and third- order statistics/spectra – based parameters. IFMBE Proceedings of the 9th Mediterranean Conference on Medical and Biological Engineering and Computing, Pula, Croatia (1):348:351.
3. **Kaplanis P A, Pattichis C S, Roberts V C, (2002).** Analysis of SEMG in normal subjects. 1st Mediterranean Congress of Neurology, Limassol, Cyprus.
4. **Kaplanis P A, Pattichis C S, Roberts V C, (2002).** Influence of Isometric Voluntary Contractions on time and frequency domain parameters of surface EMG. Proceedings of the 2nd joint conference of EMBS/BMES, Houston TX, USA, 2408-2409.
5. **Roberts V C, Kaplanis P A, Pattichis C S, Kyriakides T, (2003).** Surface electromyography (SEMG) analysis in normal subjects and subjects suffering with neuromuscular disorders. Proceedings of the World Congress on Medical Physics and Biomedical Engineering, Sydney, Australia.
6. **Kaplanis P A, Pattichis C S, Christodoulou C I, Hadjileontiadis L, Roberts V C, Kyriakides T, (2004).** A Surface Electromyography Classification System. Proceedings of the 10th Mediterranean Conference on Medical and Biological Engineering and Computing and Health Telematics, Ischia, Italy.
7. **Kaplanis P A, Pattichis C S, Hadjileontiadis L, Roberts V C, (2004).** Surface EMG Analysis on Normal Subjects Based on Isometric Voluntary Contraction. Submitted for publication in the IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering.

BISPECTRAL ANALYSIS OF SURFACE EMG

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Abstract: The objective of this ongoing study is to investigate whether or not Bispectral analysis (BS), a particular form of higher order spectra (HOS), may be utilized for analyzing the surface electromyographic signal (SEMG). The bicoherence index was used for characterizing the Gaussianity of the signal. Results indicate that SEMG signal distribution is highly non-Gaussian at low and high levels of force whereas the distribution has its maximum Gaussianity at the mid level of maximum voluntary contraction (MVC), i.e. at 50%. A measure of the linearity of the signal, based on deciding whether or not the estimated bicoherence is constant, follows the reverse pattern with the measure of Gaussianity. The power spectrum's (PS) median frequency, decreases from 105 to 93 Hz with increase of force, whereas the number of turns and the number of zero crosses increase with force. Further work is currently in progress in order to evaluate the usefulness of HOS in normal subjects and subjects suffering from neuromuscular disorders.

Index terms: Surface electromyography, Bispectral analysis, Power spectrum analysis.

I Introduction

Analysis of physiological signals using Power Spectrum (PS) techniques has been a well-accepted method for the last few decades. Due to the limitations though to: (i) detect and characterize existing non linearities in the SEMG signal, (ii) estimate the phase, and (iii) extract information due to deviations from normality [1], Higher Order Statistics (HOS), have been introduced in the 1960's and applied in the 1970's. Early attempts to use these in physiological signals have been reported and applied in electroencephalogram (EEG), with promising results. [2]. No attempts have been made, however, to utilize these in electromyography signals and, in particular, surface electromyography signals. (SEMG)

This study exploits the use of HOS in SEMG signal analysis in order to extract new parameters that could enhance the diagnostic character of SEMG.

II Materials and Methods

Data Capture. SEMG was recorded from the biceps brachii muscle of seventeen normal subjects (13 male and 4 female), aged between 25 and 55 years, using a four-bar EMG active probe, with an interelectrode distance of 10 mm and a bar width of 1 mm.

amplitude in mvolts

time in msec

Figure 1: SEMG recorded for a subject at 50% MVC.

A bar configuration has been preferred, from the well-accepted circular configuration, since a bar type electrode intersects with more fibers than a circular type. By intersecting more fibers a greater amplitude will be recorded [3]. From the four bars of the electrode, the second was used as allocation index. In particular it was placed at a distance equal to 1/3 of the biceps length. This ensures that all four electrodes lay between the innervation zone of the motor unit and the tendon. The differential recordings were recorded simultaneously one from each pair of the electrode bars. Recordings were performed for 5 seconds at 10%, 30%, 50%, 70% and 100% of the maximum voluntary contraction (MVC). The sampling frequency was 1000

Hz and the signals were band pass filtered between 20 Hz and 500 Hz with. Furthermore, the skin temperature was noted, since it has been verified that the mean frequency or the mean power frequency of the EMG signal decreases with a reduction in muscle temperature [4]. A typical section of the recorder SEMG signal for a subject at 50% MVC is depicted in Fig. 1.

Time domain analysis. The number of turns was defined as the number of slope reversals separated from the previous and the following turn by an amplitude difference greater than 50 μ V. The number of zero crossings per second was defined as the number of sign reversals exceeding a threshold of 50 μ V.

Power spectral analysis. The following measures were estimated from the power spectrum curve: median frequency, f_p , frequency at max power, f_{pmax} , max power, P_{max} , and total power, P_{total} . The signal was segmented at 512 points with 25% overlap.

Bispectral analysis. For a zero-mean, stationary process $\{X(k)\}$, the third-order cumulant (TOC) is defined as the expected value of the triple product

$$R(m, n) = E\{X(k)X(k + m)X(k + n)\}, \quad (1)$$

and the bispectrum is defined as the Fourier transform of the TOC sequence [5]:

$$B(\omega_1, \omega_2) = \sum_{m=-\infty}^{m=\infty} \sum_{n=-\infty}^{n=\infty} R(m, n) e^{-j(\omega_1 m + \omega_2 n)}. \quad (2)$$

In addition, the sum of magnitudes of the estimated bispectrum is computed by

$$D = \sum_{(\omega_1, \omega_2)} |B(\omega_1, \omega_2)|. \quad (3)$$

To quantify the non-Gaussianity of a random process, the normalized bispectrum, or bicoherence is estimated as

$$B_n(\omega_1, \omega_2) = \frac{B(\omega_1, \omega_2)}{\sqrt{P(\omega_1)P(\omega_2)P(\omega_1 + \omega_2)}}, \quad (4)$$

where $P(\cdot)$ is the power spectrum. The test of Gaussianity is based on the mean bicoherence power defined as

$$S_g = \sum |B_n(\omega_1, \omega_2)|, \quad (5)$$

with the summation performed over the non-redundant region.

The Gaussianity test (actually zero-skewness test) basically involves deciding whether or not the estimated bicoherence is zero. The linearity test involves deciding whether or not the estimated bicoherence is constant in the bifrequency domain, employing a measure of the difference (dR) between a theoretical and an estimated inter-quartile range R .

The BS analysis was performed with Hispec toolkit by MATLAB 5.3 (Mathworks Inc). The signal was segmented into overlapped records, for reducing the variance of the estimated BS, using a window of 512 points in length with a 25% overlap. The analysis for the Gaussianity test was accepted if the probability of false alarm, was less than 5%. The linearity analysis was accepted if the difference between the estimated statistic R was not more than a factor of two difference than the inter-quartile range of $X^2_2(\lambda)$ (the X^2 distributed random variable, with 2 degrees of freedom and non-centrality parameter, λ).

Seventeen percent of the recordings failed the Gaussianity criteria and fourteen percent failed the Linearity criteria as mentioned above. Analysis was performed using the Hispec toolkit by MATLAB.

III Results and Discussion

Figure 2 illustrates the PS and BS plots corresponding to the SEMG signal depicted in Fig. 1. Moreover, Table 1 tabulates the average parameters of all seventeen subjects from both pair of electrodes. Furthermore, in Fig. 3, the average degree of Gaussianity of all seventeen subjects is plotted against the various force levels used for both pairs of electrodes.

From the time domain analysis parameters, it is observed that the number of zero crossings and turns per second increases with force levels (FL). It should also be noted that there is no major difference between recordings of the two pairs.

From the frequency domain analysis parameters it is noted that the power spectrum median frequency decreases from 105/107 (1st electrode pair/2nd electrode pair), to 93/97 Hz with increase of FL, which again is in accordance with previous findings [6]-[8].

The total Power and max Power however increase with FL. These two parameters gave different results, which were more evident at higher levels of force. Similar findings were also reported by Li et al [9]. Li studied the differences in total power recorded by the biceps brachii muscle at different force levels (20, 40 and 60% MVC), at distances 5 to 60 mm, between the end plate zone and the midpoint of the recording bipolar electrodes. Li et al reported that in the distal and proximal direction from the end plate zone, there is a great difference of the recorded power at 60%, less at 40%, and nearly no difference at 20% of MVC.

From the bifrequency domain analysis parameters it was found that the test for Gaussianity results are not similar among the two pairs of electrodes. The first pair (see Fig. 3) indicates that the signal becomes less Gaussian for the 10 to 30% transition, has a more Gaussian distribution at 50% and from there on becomes less and less Gaussian. The other pair though, presents a different profile. The Gaussianity increases from 10 to 50%, and with further increase of MVC the signal becomes less Gaussian. Similar findings were recorded for needle EMG [10]. However a measure of the signals linearity, based on deciding whether or not the estimated bicoherence is constant, follows the reverse pattern with that of Gaussianity.

Table 1: Average parameters analyzed for all 17 subjects for both pairs of electrodes. For each force level, the values of the 1st and 2nd recording electrode pairs are given, separated by backslash (/). (1st pair/2nd pair).

Time domain			Frequency domain				Bispectrum domain	
% of MVC	Zero Crossings/ Second	Turns/ Second	Median frequency $f_{p_{median}}$ (Hz)	Frequency at max Power (Hz)	Total power Pt ($nV^2 Hz$)	Max Power Pmax ($nV^2 Hz$)	Gaussianity Test S_g	Linearity test dR
10	4/2	12/8	105/107	75/80	2/2	33/46	230/251	1.54/1.51
30	24/16	36/32	95/103	78/75	14/7	359/194	249/239	1.68/1.38
50	48/36	76/68	98/103	76/74	21/18	649/215	239/193	1.31/1.0
70	76/70	108/104	96/99	81/82	80/48	1860/1130	305/242	1.76/1.22
100	112/110	146/146	93/97	68/75	127/68	6740/4000	344/303	2.35/1.84

normalized units

frequency Hz

Figure 2: Power spectrum curve (top) and bispectrum curve (bottom) of the SEMG signal shown in Fig. 1.

Force level (% of MVC)

Figure 3. Change of Gaussianity, S_g with force level, for 1st (solid line) and 2nd (dashed line) recording pair.

Force level (% of MVC)

Figure 4. Change of Linearity, dR with force level, for 1st (solid line) and 2nd (dashed line) pair.

The average values for the linearity test are shown in Fig. 4. From this figure it is clear that the two pairs follow the same pattern, which is the reverse pattern of the first pair of the Gaussianity test as shown in Fig. 3. In this case, the signal seems to be less linear at 50% of MVC and more linear at 100% of MVC.

V Conclusions

The aim of this study was to investigate the usefulness of bispectral analysis in SEMG. Besides Bispectral analysis, time domain parameters and frequency domain parameters were examined. As expected, number of zero crossings and turns per second increased with FL.

From the frequency domain analysis, it was evident that the median frequency decreases with FL. Total Power and max power increase with FL, but they are also position dependent, as this was verified with the two electrode pairs used for recording. This was even more evident at higher levels of force.

Bispectrum analysis is also position dependent, since the first pair indicated that the signal become less Gaussian for the transition at low and high levels of force and has its maximum Gaussianity value at 50% of MVC. The other pair of electrodes which was positioned 20 mm away (mid point of two pairs), showed an increase of Gaussianity up to 50% of MVC and a decrease from there on. A measure of the Linearity showed an exact reverse pattern with that of Gaussianity.

More work is currently in progress to firstly to increase the data bank, with more recordings, for normals, as well as to develop a data bank with recording from subjects suffering with neuromuscular disorders.

VI Acknowledgements

This work was made possible through the kind support of the Cyprus Institute of Neurology and Genetics.

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ANALYSIS OF SURFACE EMG USING SECOND AND THIRD-ORDER STATISTICS/SPECTRA – BASED PARAMETERS

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Abstract: The objective of this ongoing study is to investigate if surface electromyography signals (SEMG), could be characterized using bispectrum and third-order statistics/spectra (HOS) – based parameters. In particular, the bicoherence index was used for measuring the degree of Gaussianity of the signal. The linearity of the signal, based on deciding whether or not the estimated bicoherence is constant, together with the amplitude of the bispectrum, its coordinates and its variance from the peak were estimated. Power spectrum and time domain parameters were also estimated. Experimental results from the analysis of real SEMG data recorded from thirty-three adult normal subjects (13 female and 20 male) aged between 20 and 50 years old, proved an influence of contraction on the aforementioned parameters ($p < 0.05$). Further work is currently in progress in order to evaluate the usefulness of HOS in subjects suffering from neuromuscular disorders.

Index terms: Surface electromyography, Bispectral analysis, Power spectrum analysis.

Introduction

Analysis of physiological signals using Power Spectrum (PS) techniques has been a well-accepted method for the last few decades. Due to the limitations though to: (i) detect and characterize existing non linearities of the signal, (ii) estimate the phase, and (iii) extract information due to deviations from normality [1], Higher Order Statistics (HOS), have been introduced in the 1960's and applied in the 1970's. Early attempts to use these in physiological signals have been reported and applied in electroencephalogram (EEG), with promising results. [2]. Since now, no attempts have been made however, to utilize HOS in electromyography signals and, in particular, in surface electromyography signals (SEMG)

This study analyses the influence of transition from 10% to 100% of the maximum voluntary contraction (MVC), of thirty-three analyzed recorded SEMG on seven

parameters of the bifrequency domain of bispectrum, four of the frequency domain of PS and two of the time domain.

Materials and Methods

Data Capture. SEMG were recorded from the biceps brachii (BB) muscle of forty-six normal subjects (28 male and 18 female), aged between 5 and 60 years old.

The subjects were divided in age groups per decade. i.e., 3 subjects ≤ 10 yrs, 11 yrs ≤ 7 subjects ≤ 20 yrs, 21 yrs ≤ 19 subjects ≤ 30 yrs, 31 yrs ≤ 8 subjects ≤ 40 yrs, 41 yrs ≤ 6 subjects ≤ 50 yrs, and 51 yrs ≤ 3 subjects ≤ 60 yrs. Recording was done using a four-bar EMG active probe with an interelectrode distance of 10 mm and a bar width of 1 mm. The electrode block was placed on the BB (see Fig. 1), in such a way so that the second electrode was at a distance equal with 1/3 of the BB length towards the shoulder, although exact positioning was quite difficult for female subjects and children.

Figure 1: Positioning of the electrode block on the BB. The 2nd electrode was placed at a distance equal

to 1/3 x towards the shoulder.

A bar configuration has been preferred from the well-accepted circular configuration, since the former intersects with more fibers than the latter. By intersecting more fibers a greater amplitude will be recorded [3]. From the four bars of the electrode, the second was used as allocation index. Its predefined placement ensures that all four electrodes lay between the innervation zone of the motor unit and the tendon. The differential recordings were recorded simultaneously one from each pair of the electrode bars. Only the highest value though of the pair was used for this analysis. Both pairs will be needed in the future if muscle fiber conduction velocity (MFCV) is to be estimated. Recordings were performed for 5 seconds at 10%, 30%, 50%, 70% and 100% of the maximum voluntary contraction (MVC). An antialiasing band pass filter [20÷500Hz] was initially applied on the recorded signals, which were then sampled with a sampling frequency of 1000Hz at a 12-digitization resolution. Furthermore, the skin temperature was noted, since it has been verified that the mean frequency or the mean power frequency of the EMG signal decreases with a reduction in muscle temperature [4].

Time domain analysis. Two parameters were estimated from the analysis of SEMGs in the time domain. In particular, the number of turns was defined as the number of slope reversals separated from the previous and the following turn by an amplitude difference greater than 50 μ V. The number of zero crossings per second was defined as the number of sign reversals exceeding a threshold of 50 μ V.

Power spectral analysis. The following measures were estimated from the power spectrum curve of the analyzed SEMGs: median frequency f_p , frequency at max power f_{max} , max power P_{max} , and total power P_{total} . The signal was segmented at 512 points with 25% overlap.

Bispectral analysis. For a zero-mean, stationary process $\{X(k)\}$, the third-order cumulant (TOC) is defined as the expected value of the triple product

$$R(m, n) = E\{X(k)X(k+m)X(k+n)\}, \quad (1)$$

and the bispectrum is defined as the Fourier transform of the TOC sequence [5]:

$$B(\omega_1, \omega_2) = \sum_{m=-\infty}^{m=\infty} \sum_{n=-\infty}^{n=\infty} R(m, n) e^{-j(\omega_1 m + \omega_2 n)}. \quad (2)$$

In addition, the sum of magnitudes of the estimated bispectrum is computed by

$$D = \sum_{(\omega_1, \omega_2)} |B(\omega_1, \omega_2)|. \quad (3)$$

To quantify the non-Gaussianity of a random process, the normalized bispectrum, or bicoherence is estimated as follows

$$B_n(\omega_1, \omega_2) = \frac{B(\omega_1, \omega_2)}{\sqrt{P(\omega_1)P(\omega_2)P(\omega_1 + \omega_2)}}, \quad (4)$$

where $P(\cdot)$ is the power spectrum. The test of Gaussianity is based on the mean bicoherence power defined as follows

$$S_g = \sum |B_n(\omega_1, \omega_2)|, \quad (5)$$

with the summation performed over the non-redundant region.

The Gaussianity test (actually zero-skewness test) basically involves deciding whether or not the estimated bicoherence is zero. The linearity test involves deciding whether or not the estimated bicoherence is constant in the bifrequency domain, employing a measure of the difference (dR) between a theoretical and an estimated inter-quartile range R .

The Bispectral analysis was performed with Hispec toolkit of MATLAB 5.3 (Mathworks Inc). The signal was segmented into overlapped records, for reducing the variance of the estimated BS, using a window of 512 points in length with a 25% overlap. The analysis for the Gaussianity test was accepted if the probability of false alarm, was less than 5%. The linearity analysis was accepted if the difference between the estimated statistic R was not more than a factor of two difference than the inter-quartile range of $X^2_2(\lambda)$ (the X^2 distributed random variable, with 2 degrees of freedom and non-centrality parameter, λ).

Results and Discussion

The results presented in this paper correspond to those derived from adults only (20 to 50 years old), thus from 33 subjects. Figure 2, illustrates the PS, a plot of the singular values and a plot of the BS of a female subject aged 21 yrs, recorded at 100% of MVC. From the power spectrum plot, the median frequency, the frequency at maximum power, the maximum power and the total power were estimated. From the bispectrum plots, the amplitude of the peak is estimated, B_{max} , its coordinates and its variation from the peak in both directions x and y were also estimated.

Figure 2: Plots of PS, Singular values and BS of a female subject aged 21yrs recorded at 100% of MVC. Frequency axis of the PS and BS plots should be multiplied times 1000 to give values in Hz

Results extracted from the SEMGs of the 33 normal subjects are shown in table 1. These have been used to investigate whether or not there is a significant difference in the change of the mean of the 13 parameters extracted.

Table 2 indicates the influence of transition from one level of voluntary contraction to another for all thirteen parameters investigated. Differences in the means of parameters were evaluated using the Wilcoxon matched pairs rank test. A two-tailed 5% significance level was utilized.

Results show a significant change in both parameters of the time domain, i.e. the number of turns per second and number of zero crossings for any contraction transition.

The analysis in the PS domain gave also straightforward results. The median frequency variation is significant for transitions from low to high and from mid to high force levels. Shankar et al. [6] have also shown a variation in median frequency with an increase in applied torque. The frequency however, where maximum Power occurs, stays fairly constant irrespective of the force level, as shown in Table 1. The maximum and total power, though, show a steadily increase, which has also been reported by Li [7] Analysis in the BS domain is though more complicated. The amplitude change of the peak in a BS plot, between 10% of the MVC and any other percentage is significant. Any other transition though gave non-significant indexes. The change in the position of Bmax in either direction for any of the 10 different transitions is non significant. The change in the spreading of the peak in the x direction seems to change significantly from low to high FL, from mid to high FL and also between the two mid FL (50 and 70%). The only significant FL given for the spreading of the maximum peak of the bispectrum in the y-direction was from 30 to 50 %. The test of the bicoherence index (test of Gaussianity) showed a significant difference between low and high FL and also between mid and high FL. Similar findings have been reported for needle EMG recordings [8]. Finally a test on deciding whether or not the bicoherence index was constant or not (test of linearity), showed a significant change between transitions 10 to 30%, 10 and 100% and 70 to 100%. It must be noted that 12.1 % of the recordings failed the Gaussianity criteria and 18.2% failed the Linearity criteria.

Table 1. Average parameters for 33 normal subjects aged between 21 and 50 years old

Parameters	Percentage of Force Levels				
	10	30	50	70	100
Turns/second (t/s)	7	19	34	51	72
Zero crossings (crossings)	3	11	23	34	56
Median frequency (fp)	102	99	100	98	96
Frequency at max power (fx)	72	73	78	73	72
Maximum power (Pmax)	3E-09	2E-08	6E-08	2E-07	6E-07
Total power (Ptotal)	9E-08	5E-07	1E-06	3E-06	1E-05
Amplitude of Bispectrum (Bmax)	442	969	513	957	11325
Test of Gaussianity (Gaussianity)	251	253	252	239	311
Test of Linearity (Linearity)	1.34	1.93	1.75	1.53	2.24
Bmax coordinate in x-direction (f1)	52	52	53	54	53
Bmax coordinate in y-direction (f2)	34	39	39	37	37
Spreading of Bmax in x-direction (f1var)	60	58	59	54	52
Spreading of Bmax in y-direction (f2var)	14	14	15	15	15

Table 2. Evaluation of the transition from a lower to a higher percentage of the force level as a significant (S) ($p < 0.05$) or not significant (NS) ($p \geq 0.05$) factor for the 13 parameters investigated using the Wilcoxon paired two-tailed test.

Parameter	10/30	10/50	10/70	10/100	30/50	30/70	30/100	50/70	50/100	70/100
t/s	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
Crossings	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
fp	NS	NS	NS	S	NS	NS	NS	NS	S	NS
fx	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
Pmax	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
Ptotal	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
Bmax	S	S	S	S	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
Gaussianity	NS	NS	NS	S	NS	NS	NS	NS	S	S
Linearity	S	NS	NS	S	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	S
f1	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
f2	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
f1var	NS	NS	NS	S	NS	NS	S	S	S	NS
f2var	NS	NS	NS	NS	S	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS

Conclusions

The aim of this study was to investigate the influence of force level on 13 different parameters extracted from surface electromyography signals recorded from the BB muscle of 33 normal subjects. Emphasis was given on Higher Order Statistics since they may overcome limitations present in Power Spectral analysis.

Results showed that the influences of force transition from a low to a high level are quite obvious and clear in all time domain and frequency domain parameters. The also applies to most Bispectrum parameters.

In the near future these findings will be compared with those taken from signals recorded from patients suffering with neuromuscular diseases, aiming to replace, even partly, needle EMG examinations, necessary for the assessment of neuromuscular diseases.

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ANALYSIS OF SEMG IN NORMAL SUBJECTS

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Background Surface EMG (SEMG) has not yet been accepted as a diagnostic tool in the effort to assess a neuromuscular disorder due to its lack of sensitivity and its weak and distorted signal.

Objective The objective of this ongoing study is to compare data recorded from normal subjects and patients.

Methods. Ninety-one normal volunteers aged between 5 and 69 years old, participated in this study. SEMG was recorded from the left biceps brachii muscle, during voluntary contraction, equal to 10, 30, 50, 70, and 100% of maximum voluntary contraction. From the recorded signal twelve different parameters were extracted and their behaviors with force increment was examined.

Results Turns per second and number of zero crossings were found to increase steadily with force. The frequency where the Power Spectrum's maximum peak occurred was independent with force. On the contrary the frequency, which divided the Power Spectrum into two equal parts, was found to decrease with force increment. The signal's Gaussianity increased up to 70% and then was reduced again. The linearity followed the reverse pattern. The location of the Bispectrum peak was independent with force increment and also the rate of the peak dying off. Age and gender were found to have no effect on results.

Conclusions During this simple, painless and easy to perform test, influences of force transitions from a low to a higher were examined. In all parameters the effect is obvious. What remains to be done is to compare these results with those obtained from patients. If results are different then SEMG has a most promising future.

INFLUENCE OF ISOMETRIC VOLUNTARY CONTRACTION ON TIME AND FREQUENCY DOMAIN PARAMETERS OF SURFACE EMG

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Abstract- The main objective of this paper was to investigate the effect of increase of isometric voluntary contraction (IVC) on surface EMG recorded from the Biceps Brachii (BB) muscle. Five different force levels (FL) were used: 10, 30, 50, 70 and 100% of maximum voluntary contraction (MVC), with each recording lasting 5 seconds. The following sets of parameters were extracted: (i) in the time domain (turns (ts) and zero crossings per second (zc)), and (ii) in the frequency domain (median frequency (fp), frequency at maximum power (fx), maximum power (Px), and total power (Pt)). A total of 91 normal subjects aged between 5 and 69 years old were analyzed. The Wilcoxon paired two-tailed test ($p < 0.05$), was used to classify changes in parameters examined as significant (S) or non-significant (NS) during transition from a force level to another. Results showed that: ts, zc, Px, and Pt increase with force whereas fp decreases with force. Moreover, these parameters showed significant difference between the different force levels examined.

Keywords - Surface EMG, isometric voluntary contraction

I. INTRODUCTION

Many researchers attempted analysis of surface SEMG. The most frequently examined parameters were mean power frequency (MPF), and to a lesser degree Power Spectrum (PS) shape and total power (Pt). However because results were often conflicting [1]-[5] and group samples examined were small in size, the advantages of SEMG have not been justified that well. The aim of this study is to investigate SEMG simple time and frequency domain parameters on a large group of normal subjects and investigate if they exhibit significant difference at different force levels.

II. METHODOLOGY

Ninety-one normal subjects aged between 5 and 69 years of age (54 male (m) and 37 female (f)) participated in this study. The subjects were divided in age groups as follows: 5-9 years, 12 subjects (7 m & 5 f), 10-19 years, 12 subjects (8 m & 4 f), 20-29 years, 20 subjects (10 m & 10 f), 30-39 years, 13 subjects (8 m & 5 f), 40-49 years, 12 subjects (7 m & 5 f), 50-59 years, 12 subjects (7 m & 5 f), and 60-69 years, 10 subjects (7 m & 3 f).

Recording set-up. Frequency settings were 20 Hz and 500 Hz for lower and upper cut off frequencies respectively and the sensitivity varied between 10 and 500 μ V/div, depending on the force level of each individual. The sampling frequency was 1000 Hz with 16 bits resolution and the duration of the signal recording was 5 seconds. Recording was carried out using a four-bar EMG active

probe with an interelectrode distance of 10 mm and a bar width of 1 mm. The electrode block was placed on the BB in such a way so that the second electrode was at a distance equal with 1/3 of the BB length towards the shoulder. Five different force levels (FL) were used: 10, 30, 50, 70 and 100% of maximum voluntary contraction (MVC).

Signal processing. Six parameters were analyzed: two from the time domain (turns (ts) and zero crossings per second (zc)), and four from the frequency domain (median frequency (fp), frequency at maximum power (fx), maximum power (Px), and total power (Pt)). Differences in the mean values of these six parameters were evaluated using the Wilcoxon matched pair rank test. A two-tailed significance level of 95% ($p \leq 0.05$) was used.

Time domain analysis. The number of ts was defined as the number of slope reversals separated from the previous and the following turn by an amplitude difference greater than 10 μ V. The number of zc was defined as the number of sign reversals exceeding a threshold of 10 μ V.

Power spectral analysis. This was computed by averaging segments of the signal of 512 points with 25% overlap. The fp divides the area under the PS area in two equal parts, whereas fx is the frequency at the highest PS peak. The Pt was calculated as the area under the curve and the maximum power Px was estimated as the highest value of the PS curve.

III. RESULTS

Table I summarizes the median, and in parenthesis the lower quartile (25%) and upper quartile (75%) range for all six parameters examined for each force level. The median and lower and upper quartiles are given due to the non-Gaussian distribution of the data investigated. Table II summarizes the results of statistical analysis of the Wilcoxon matched pair rank test between different force levels. In Table II, significant difference (S) is given if $p \leq 0.05$, whereas a non significant (NS) difference is given for $p > 0.05$.

As given in Table I results show that: ts, zc, Px, and Pt increase with force level, whereas fp decreases with force level. Moreover, these parameters showed significant difference between the different combinations of the force levels examined (see Table II). Feature fx showed significant difference only between 10 and 30% of MVC.

Figure 1 illustrates the median, lower and upper quartiles spread for each force level of the turns per second and the median frequency. It is clearly illustrated that there is an

increase of the number of turns per second with force level, whereas the reverse is true for the median frequency.

TABLE I MEDIAN, AND IN PARENTHESIS THE LOWER QUARTILE (25%) AND UPPER QUARTILE (75%) RANGE FOR ALL SIX PARAMETERS EXAMINED FOR EACH FORCE LEVEL

	10%	30%	50%	70%	100%
ts	34 (3-57)	75 (28-100)	92 (55-122)	105 (70-134)	121 (88-146)
zc	10 (0-44)	51 (7-81)	73 (36-102)	94 (49-108)	99 (78-116)
fp	104 (90-125)	101 (88-116)	99 (86-115)	95 (84-112)	93 (83-110)
fx	76 (64-96)	74 (63-83)	77 (67-93)	75 (65-91)	72 (64-88)
Px	0.24 (0.08-1.2)	0.92 (0.28-4)	2.8 (0.63-15)	5.03 (1.5-31.3)	18 (3.7-110)
Pt	9 (3-3.9)	31 (7.3-145)	85 (22-470)	190 (43-810)	560 (113-2460)

TABLE II RESULTS OF STATISTICAL ANALYSIS FOR EACH PARAMETER FOR THE WILCOXON MATCHED PAIR RANK TEST BETWEEN DIFFERENT FORCE LEVELS. SIGNIFICANT DIFFERENCE (S) IS GIVEN IF $p \leq 0.05$, WHEREAS A NONSIGNIFICANT (NS) DIFFERENCE IS GIVEN FOR $p > 0.05$

	ts	zc	fp	fx	Px	Pt
10-30%	S	S	S	S	S	S
10-50%	S	S	S	NS	S	S
10-70%	S	S	S	NS	S	S
10-100%	S	S	S	NS	S	S
30-50%	S	S	S	NS	S	S
30-70%	S	S	S	NS	S	S
30-100%	S	S	S	NS	S	S
50-70%	S	S	S	NS	S	S
50-100%	S	S	S	NS	S	S
70-100%	S	S	S	NS	S	S

Fig. 1 Median, lower and upper quartiles spread for each force level (shown in the x-axis as percentage of MVC) of the turns per second and the median frequency.

IV. DISCUSSION

The turns per second and the zero crossings were increased significantly with force for all subjects as well as the maximum and total power extracted from the power spectrum of the signals recorded. The median frequency showed a small but significant decrease in value with force, whereas the frequency at maximum power remained fairly constant with non significant difference between force levels except in the 10-30% transition.

Although the mean frequency was generally used by most of the studies, in this study the median frequency was selected for the following reasons: (i) it is more reliable

when examining signals affected with noise such as SEMG signals [4], (ii) since SEMG signals do not present the characteristics of a normal distribution, median frequency should be preferred [6], and (iii) mean frequency is more influenced from the low pass tissue filtering effect rather than the median frequency [6]. Similar findings to this study regarding the decrease of median frequency with force level were also reported in [7].

The change of the six parameters computed with age and gender was also investigated, however, non significant differences were identified.

The results of these study suggest that simple parameters, like the turns per second, the zero crossings per second, the median frequency, the power at maximum frequency and the total power differ significantly between the different transitions of 10, 30, 50, 70, and 100 of MVC. These parameters are currently evaluated on SEMG recorded from subjects suffering with neuromuscular disorders.

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Surface electromyography (SEMG) analysis in normal subjects and subjects suffering with neuromuscular disorders

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INTRODUCTION

In the last two decades, surface electromyography (SEMG) has been used very effectively for Functional Electrical Stimulation or for the control of artificial limbs. However, its use in clinical diagnosis has been extremely limited. The objective of this work is to investigate the usefulness of SEMG in differentiating between normal (NOR) subjects and subjects suffering with myopathy (MYO), and neuropathy (NEURO) at different muscular force levels (FL).

METHODS

SEMG was recorded from 94, 11, and nine NOR, MYO, and NEURO subjects respectively at five different muscular force levels (10, 30, 50, 70 and 100% of maximum voluntary contraction (MVC)). These SEMG recordings were carried out for 5 seconds for each level of contraction from the biceps brachii muscle. The following features were computed from the data captured: turns per second (ts), zero crossings (zc), power spectrum median frequency (f_{med}), and Bispectrum peak amplitude (B_{max}). The Wilcoxon signed-rank test at $\alpha=0.05$ was used to detect differences between the medians of the features at the various force transitions as well as between the normal and the abnormal groups.

RESULTS

Features ts , zc , and B_{max} are influenced significantly with FL for NOR, MYO, and NEURO, as well as they discriminate between NOR-MYO, NOR-NEURO, and MYO-NEURO. The feature f_{med} decreases significantly only for NOR, as well as discriminating between NOR-MYO, and MYO-NEURO. For the 10-100% MVC force transition, the median values for ts , zc , $\log(B_{max})$, and f_{med} for the NOR, MYO and NEURO groups were as shown below:

	NOR	MYO	NEURO
ts	6-28	23-47	17-45
zc	3-22	17-36	10-38
$\log(B_{max})$	2.02-2.53	2.20-2.70	1.86-1.98
f_{med}	109-96Hz	103-102Hz	120-117Hz

CONCLUSION

Our study has shown that ts , zc , and B_{max} are influenced significantly with FL for NOR, MYO, and NEURO, as well as discriminating between NOR, MYO, and NEURO.

A Surface Electromyography Classification System

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Abstract: The objective of this study was to investigate whether surface electromyography (SEMG) signals may be used to discriminate between normal (NOR), myopathy (MYO) and neuropathy (NEUR) subjects. Ninety-one normal subjects participated and 20 patients (11 MYO and 9 NEUR). Recorded signals were obtained for 5 seconds at 10, 30, 50 70 and 100% of Maximum Voluntary Contraction (MVC). Five parameters were obtained, two from the time domain (turns and zero crossings per second), two from the frequency domain (median frequency and total power per second) and one from the bi-frequency domain (bispectrum peak amplitude). The KNN classifier with the leave-one-out method was used for classification whereas the Self Organising Feature Maps (SOFM) was used for cluster analysis and visualization of the group separation. Results have shown that separation of normal subjects from neuromuscular diseased patients is possible with a success rate of the order of 83%, whereas separation of subjects from the two types of patients (myopathy and neuropathy) is again high and of the order of 77%.

Index terms: Surface electromyography, myopathy neuropathy, SOFM, KNN.

Introduction

To be able to identify whether or not a subject is suffering from a neuromuscular disorder or even more to identify the correct disorder type a needle electromyography (EMG) examination necessitating constant expert supervisor and all the drawbacks associated with an invasive examination. Analysis of signals recorded with surface electrodes from various research groups aiming to discriminate normal from abnormal subjects have produced poor results and have hence been generally neglected or approached with suspicion.

In this study, we present only selected results obtained from a large group of subjects (91 normal subjects and 20 patients), where fourteen parameters were examined [1].

In particular the influence of transition from a high to a low force level (100%, 70%, 50%, 30% and 10%) of

the maximum voluntary contraction (MVC) was examined. Five parameters from the three domains (time, frequency and bi-frequency) were used for the analysis and comparison of the EMG signals acquired from the controls and patients. In addition Self Organising Feature Maps (SOFM) and the Kohonen Neural network (KNN) leave one out method parameter classification technique were adopted to classify the subjects into the following classes; normal (NOR) subjects (non-diseased), myopathy (MYO), or neuropathy (NEUR) patients.

Materials and Methods

Data Capture. SEMG were recorded from the biceps brachii (BB) muscle of all subjects. Eighteen non-diseased subjects, from a total of 91 were selected with the method of age/gender, in order to be tested against the patients separately.

Recording was done using a four-bar EMG active probe with an interelectrode distance of 10 mm and a bar width of 1 mm. The electrode block was placed on the BB, in such a way so that the second electrode was at a distance equal with 1/3 of the BB length towards the shoulder

A bar configuration has been preferred from the well-accepted circular configuration, since the former intersects with more fibers than the latter. By intersecting more fibers greater amplitude will be recorded [2]. From the four bars of the electrode, the second was used as allocation index. Its predefined placement ensures that all four electrodes lay between the innervation zone of the motor unit and the tendon. The differential recordings were recorded simultaneously one from each pair of the electrode bars. Only the highest value though of the pair was used for this analysis. Recordings were performed for 5 seconds at 10%, 30%, 50%, 70% and 100% of the maximum voluntary contraction (MVC). An antialiasing band pass filter [20÷500Hz] was initially applied on the recorded signals, which were then sampled with a sampling frequency of 1 kHz at a 12-bit digitization resolution.

Time domain analysis. Two parameters were estimated from the analysis of SEMGs in the time domain. The number of turns per second was defined

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as the number of slope reversals separated from the previous and the following turn by an amplitude difference greater than 20 μV in one second. The number of zero crossings per second was defined as the number of sign reversals exceeding a threshold of 20 μV in a period of one second.

Power spectral analysis. The following measures were estimated from the power spectrum curve of the analyzed SEMGs: median frequency and total power per second P_{ts} . The signal was segmented at 512 points with 25% overlap.

Bispectral analysis. From the Bispectrum domain, the Bispectrum peak amplitude was calculated.

For a zero-mean, stationary process $\{X(k)\}$, the third-order cumulant (TOC) is defined as the expected value of the triple product

$$R(m, n) = E\{X(k)X(k+m)X(k+n)\}, \quad (1)$$

and the bispectrum is defined as the Fourier transform of the TOC sequence [3].

$$B(\omega_1, \omega_2) = \sum_{m=-\infty}^{m=\infty} \sum_{n=-\infty}^{n=\infty} R(m, n) e^{-j(\omega_1 m + \omega_2 n)} \quad (2)$$

The signal was segmented into overlapped records, for reducing the variance of the estimated BS, using a window of 512 points in length with a 25% overlap.

Classifications. The KNN classifier was used in this study for classification of subjects, between the three groups of subjects, as well as between two groups (normals and patients). In the KNN algorithm, in order to classify a new input pattern, its k nearest neighbours from the training set are identified. The new pattern is classified to the most frequent class among its neighbours based on a similarity measure that is usually the Euclidean distance as defined below [4].

$$Ed_{xy} = \|x - y\| = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - y_i)^2}$$

In this study, the KNN subject classification system was implemented for different values of $k=1,3,5$ and 7 , and for 25 features (5 force level x five parameters), and it was tested for the following:

1. 18 NOR, 9 MYO and 9 NEUR
2. 18 NOR and 18 patients as one group
3. 91 NOR, 11 MYO and 9 NEUR
4. 91 NOR and 20 patients as one group

In order to evaluate the performance of a cluster analysis system the following parameters need to be first defined: (i) True positive (TP), decision occurs when the positive diagnosis of the system coincides with a positive diagnosis according to the Neurophysiologist (ii) False positive (FP) decision occurs when the system made a positive diagnosis that is not in agreement with the Neurophysiologist (iii)

False negative, occurs when the system made a negative diagnosis that is not in agreement with the Neurophysiologist and (iv) True negative (TN) both the physician and the system indicate the absence of a positive diagnosis.

The following measures may then be defined [5]:

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Percentage of correct classifications (\%CC)} \\ \%CC &= 100 \times (TP + TN) / n \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

n is the number of subjects

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Percentage of false positives (\%FP)} \\ \%FP &= 100 \times FP / (TN + FP) \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Percentage of false negatives (\%FN)} \\ \%FN &= 100 \times FN / (TP + FN) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Sensitivity

$$SE = 100 \times TP / (TP + FN) \quad (7)$$

Sensitivity is the likelihood that an event will be detected given that it is present

Specificity

$$SP = 100 \times TN / (TN + FP) \quad (8)$$

Specificity is the likelihood that the absence of an event will be detected given that it is absent

Recall

$$RE = 100 \times TP / (N_{NEUR} + N_{MYO}) \quad (9)$$

where N_{NEUR} is the number of NEUR patients and N_{MYO} is the number of MYO patients

Recall is the number of positive diagnoses correctly made by the system, divided by the total number of positive diagnoses made by the physician.

Precision

$$PR = 100 \times TP / (TP + FP) \quad (10)$$

Results and Discussion

The average values for the five selected parameters at the corresponding force levels for the three groups of subjects, normals (NOR), myopathy patients (MYO) and neuropathy patients (NEUR) are listed in Table 1 for all 91 normal subjects (top) and for the selection of 18 subjects (below). The values listed in Table 1 have been used to produce Tables 2 and 3 and the plots in Figure 1. These selected parameters present significant differences, ($p < 0.05$, Wilcoxon signed rank test), between corresponding force levels and between one force level and another [1].

Table 2, presents the clustering results, including all measures listed earlier for different values of k value for two classes, (Normal and Abnormal). Table 3 is a

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similar table but for three classes (Normal, Myopathy and Neuropathy).

From Table 2, the highest percentage of correct classifications (%CC), between Normal and Abnormal (patients), is given for k=1 with 91 normal subjects compared with 20 patients (83%), which gives also the highest value in specificity (92). The success rate if compared with a similar one obtained (87.5%) [6], may seem low, however one needs to remember that this present, technique utilizes surface electromyography and voluntary stimulation alone. Furthermore the patients here were suffering from different type of diseases and were classified only as myopathy and neuropathy patients and irrespective of their disease

severity. From Table 3 the highest value of correct classification and specificity is given for the same combination i.e. when k=1, and 91 normal subjects are compared with 11 myopathy patients and 9 neuropathy patients. However this should be seen with caution since the unequal number of subjects per class creates a bias in favor of the larger classes. The more reliable results are when equal number of subjects per class with the best result being 69%.

Figure 1 plots the Self Organising Feature Maps (SOFM), showing the distribution of all 91 normal subjects and 18 patients and of a selection of 18 subjects and 18 patients.

Table 1. Average values for the five parameters for the three groups of subjects at 10, 30, 50, 70 and 100% MVC, with the standard deviation in parenthesis for all 91 normal subjects (top table) and for the selected 18 normal subjects (below).

	PERCENTAGE OF MAXIMUM VOLUNTARY CONTRACTION														
	10%			30%			50%			70%			100%		
	NOR	MYO	NEUR	NOR	MYO	NEUR	NOR	MYO	NEUR	NOR	MYO	NEUR	NOR	MYO	NEUR
t/s	6	23	17	12	29	25	17	35	33	22	38	37	28	47	46
zc/s	3	17	10	7	23	18	12	29	26	26	32	31	20	36	38
Pfmed (Hz)	109	103	102	104	103	118	102	102	121	100	97	117	96	102	117
Pt/s	0.5	1.2	0.7	1.1	1.5	1.1	1.5	1.8	1.4	1.8	1.9	1.6	2.2	2.4	1.9
V ²															
Bmax	2.0	2.2	1.9	2.2	2.3	2.0	2.3	2.4	1.8	2.4	2.7	1.8	2.5	2.7	2.0
V ³ sec															

	PERCENTAGE OF MAXIMUM VOLUNTARY CONTRACTION														
	10%			30%			50%			70%			100%		
	NOR	MYO	NEUR	NOR	MYO	NEUR	NOR	MYO	NEUR	NOR	MYO	NEUR	NOR	MYO	NEUR
t/s	6	23	17	11	29	25	18	35	33	25	38	37	32	47	46
zc/s	3	17	10	7	23	18	11	29	26	14	32	31	23	36	38
Pfmed (Hz)	124	103	102	121	103	118	115	102	121	113	97	117	107	102	117
Pt/s	0.5	1.2	0.7	1.0	1.5	1.1	1.4	1.8	1.4	1.7	1.9	1.6	2.1	2.4	1.9
V ²															
Bmax	1.8	2.2	1.9	1.7	2.3	2.0	1.9	2.4	1.8	2.0	2.7	1.8	2.2	2.7	2.0
V ³ sec															

Table 2. KNN Classifier performance results for two classes (Normal and Abnormal)

K	NORMAL	ABNORMAL	%CC	%FP	%FN	SE	SP	RE	PR
1	91	20	83	8	60	40	92	44	53
1	18	18	61	28	50	50	72	50	64
3	91	20	77	24	20	80	76	89	42
3	18	18	58	33	50	50	67	50	60
5	91	20	72	31	15	85	69	94	38
5	18	18	69	22	39	61	78	61	73
7	91	20	81	14	40	60	86	67	48
7	18	18	67	28	39	61	72	61	69

Table 3. KNN Classifier performance results for three classes (Normal [NOR], Myopathy [MYO] and Neuropathy [NEUR])

K	NOR	MYO	NEUR	%CC	%FP	%FN	SE	SP	RE	PR
1	91	11	9	77	8	86	14	92	11	22
1	18	9	9	61	28	50	50	72	50	64
3	91	11	9	68	34	36	64	76	39	24
3	18	9	9	61	25	29	71	75	56	71
5	91	11	9	65	31	25	75	69	50	24
5	18	9	9	47	35	54	46	65	33	50
7	91	11	9	60	37	17	83	62	56	24
7	18	9	9	56	25	33	67	75	44	67

Figure 1. Left plot presents the SOFM classification between 91 normal subjects (x) and 18 patients (o) and right plot distinguishes between selected 18 normal subjects (x) and 18 patients (o).

Conclusions

Results have shown that surface electromyography signals when applied into our system may be used with a high degree of accuracy to discriminate between normal subjects and neuromuscular diseased patients. Furthermore patients may be discriminated from normal subjects into groups (normal, myopathy or neuropathy) with a slightly less degree of correct classification. However it is believed that even better results may be obtained when more parameters are applied into the system. Still, even these results are quite promising and may be used without causing any discomfort to the patients, to help the neurophysiologist cross-reference their diagnosis as to if and what type of disease a patient is suffering from.

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Surface EMG Analysis on Normal Subjects Based on Isometric Voluntary Contraction

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Abstract

The objective of this study was to compute reference SEMG values for normal subjects of 13 parameters extracted in the time, frequency and bispectrum domain, from the Biceps Brachii (BB) muscle generated under isometric voluntary contraction (IVC). SEMG signals were recorded from 94 subjects for 5 seconds at 10, 30, 50, 70 and 100% of Maximum Voluntary Contraction (MVC). The Wilcoxon signed-rank test was applied to detect significant differences or not at $p < 0.05$ between force levels for each of the 13 parameters. The main findings of this study can be summarized as follows: (i) The time domain parameters turns per second and number of zero crossings per second increase significantly with force level. (ii) The power spectrum median frequency parameter decreases significantly with force level, whereas maximum power and total power increase significantly with force level. (iii) The bispectrum parameter, maximum amplitude, increases significantly with force level with the exception the transition from 30 to 50% MVC. Although the tests for Gaussianity and linearity show no significant difference with force level, the SEMG signal exhibits a more Gaussian distribution with increase of force up to 70% MVC. The SEMG linearity test, that is a measure of how constant the bicoherence index is in the bi-frequency domain, shows that the signal's bicoherence index is less constant (hence, the signal is less linear) at 70% of MVC compared to 10, 30, 50 and 100% MVC. (iv) The time domain parameters have good

correlation between them as well as, between each one of them and maximum and total power. The median frequency has a good (negative) correlation with the Bispectrum peak amplitude. (v) No significant differences exist between values based on gender or age. The findings of this study can further be used for the assessment of subjects suffering with neuromuscular disorders, or in the rehabilitation laboratory for monitoring the elderly or the disabled, or in the occupational medicine laboratory.

Index terms: SEMG, Time domain analysis, Power spectrum analysis, Bispectrum analysis.

Introduction

Surface Electromyography EMG (SEMG), provides a non-invasive way of studying muscular function. The SEMG signal is very complex, representing a summation of tissue-filtered signals generated by a number of concurrently active motor units. The generated motor unit action potentials (MUAPs) recorded on the skin surface vary in amplitude, duration and frequency content [1]. Although SEMG has been used effectively for Functional Electrical Stimulation (FES) or for the controlling of artificial limbs, its use in clinical diagnosis has been very limited or non-existent [2], [3]. Grossman and Wiener [4] have warned physiologists from as early as 1966, that SEMG should not be used as a diagnostic tool due to the phenomenon of crosstalk, signal attenuation and filtering. Regardless of this, a number of studies have shown that SEMG generated by either voluntary or

electrically elicited muscle activity, contain more significant information than it was originally believed [5]. However, only a few studies have been traced in the literature, tabulating normal values of one or maybe two parameters, recorded only though, from a limited number of subjects (see Table 1). The objective of this study was to compute reference SEMG values for normal subjects. Thirteen parameters were extracted in the time, frequency, and bispectrum domains, from SEMG signals recorded from the Biceps Brachii (BB) muscle during isometric voluntary contractions (IVC). The values recorded could then be used as reference values for the assessment of muscle function in the clinical or rehabilitation laboratory.

Table 1 summarizes in chronological order SEMG studies and findings carried out on the BB muscle on normal subjects. The studies shown examined the influence of increase (step or ramp) voluntary contraction, on time domain and/or frequency domain parameters. Step contractions, involve maintaining the force at a constant percentage of MVC for a few seconds, whereas ramp contractions involve a linear increase from 0 to 100% of MVC, without stopping at any percentage. The most frequently examined parameters were the mean power frequency (*MPF*) [5]-[12], and the median frequency (*Pf med*) [12] – [16], and to a lesser degree the frequency at max Power (*Pf x*) [6], [13], the number of zero crossings per second (*zc/s*) [17] the Power Spectrum (*PS*) shape [13], [18] and the total power (*Pt*) [10]. Hagberg *et al.* [7] showed that at levels higher than 25-30% of Maximum Voluntary Contraction (MVC), the *MPF* became independent of contraction level, whereas Moritani *et al.* [8] showed an increase of up to 80% of MVC. Another study [6] however, showed a continuous increase of *MPF*. On the contrary, Gerdle *et al.* [9] showed that the increase in *MPF* values exists only up to 60% of MVC. A totally different finding was that of Rainoldi *et al.* [11], who showed that *MPF* decreases for force levels (FL) between 30 and 70% of MVC. Farina *et al.* [12], investigating the

possibilities and limitations of the use of SEMG variables (including *MPF*), as indicators of Motor Unit recruitment strategies, showed that *MPF* did not follow a consistent pattern with ramp contractions. Contradictions exist in the findings regarding the *PS* distribution as well. Although Chaffin [18], found that there is a shift of the *PS* towards the lower frequency band (LSB), with force increment, Gander *et al.* [13], found the opposite. Median frequency, *Pf med*, illustrates the same contradicting findings [12]-[16] although one may refer to a pilot study [2], whose results are in full agreement with this study. It is clearly shown in Table 1 that many discrepancies exist between findings. These could be due to: (i) the limited and different number of subjects examined in most of the cases (4-31), excluding this study, (ii) the difference in recording time (1 to 45 seconds), since fatigue may influence results at longer recording times [19] and [20], (iii) the method of statistical analysis used, (iv) the force level exhibited, (v) the positioning of electrodes, and (vi) to the variations in the experimental conditions [14], and (vii) due to the orientation of the muscle fibers with respect to the recording surface electrodes, their length, and the thickness of the individual subcutaneous layers [12].

Besides the above-mentioned parameters, parameters from the bi-frequency domain were recently introduced, although not yet applied on EMG signals. One effort was made by Zazula [21], who concluded that even a robust approach, based on bicepstral system identification, failed with surface EMG. By applying bi-frequency techniques one does not have to rely on the assumption that the signal presents a Gaussian (normal) distribution [22]. It is well accepted today that real life physiological signals are highly non-Gaussian and by neglecting this and analyzing biosignals, with inappropriate methods, may lead to false results. For instance, the median frequency is considered more reliable than the mean power frequency and, hence, should be preferred, since: (i) the

median frequency estimate is less affected by the noise [5], (ii) the signal does not present the characteristics of a normal distribution, (iii) the median frequency is a zero-order parameter, where all frequency components are weighted equally, in contrast to first-order parameters such as the mean power frequency, where the higher frequency components are weighted more and (iv) in case of a considerable amount of skinfold layer (which was not calculated in this study), the mean frequency is influenced more due to the low pass filtering effect of the skin [15]. Still however the lack of normal median frequency Pf_{med} , values limits the usefulness of spectral analysis in general [14].

In this study, the following parameters were estimated: (i) in the time domain: turns per second, t/s and zero-crossings per second, zc/s ; (ii) in the frequency domain: median frequency, Pf_{med} , frequency at maximum power, Pf_x , maximum power, P_{max} and total power, P_{total} , and (iii) in the bi-frequency domain: gaussianity test, sg , linearity test, sl , Bispectrum peak amplitude, B_{max} , its peak location in the x and y directions, B_x and B_y , respectively, and the slope of the peak in the x and y directions B_{xslope} and B_{yslope} .

Material And Methods

A. Material

Ninety-four subjects (56 male (M) and 38 female (F)), aged between 5 and 69 years participated in this study. The subjects were divided into age groups (mean (SD)), as follows: < 9 years, 12 subjects, (7 M and 5 F) (8.3 (1.4)); 10 – 19 years, 12 subjects, (8 M and 4 F) (17.3 (2.4)); 20 – 29 years, 20 subjects, (10 M and 10 F) (23.75 (2.6)); 30 – 39 years, 15 subjects, (10 M and 5 F) (36.0 (2.6)); 40 – 49 years, 12 subjects (7 M and 5 F), (44.1 (1.9)); 50 - 59 years, 13 subjects (7 M and 6 F), (55.0 (2.4)), and 60 – 69 years 10 subjects, (7 M and 3 F) (65.1 (3.99)). None of the subjects had any previous history of neuromuscular disease. The study was approved by the Ethical Committee of the

Cyprus Institute of Neurology and Genetics (CING).

B. Recording set-up

Recording took place at a special screened EMG/EEG/EP laboratory, with constant temperature, at the Department of Clinical Neurophysiology at the CING. The Nicolet Viking IV, electromyography two-channel amplifier unit was used which was according to manufacturers' specifications, fully electrically isolated to IEC 601-1 and BSS 5724, Part 1 Type BF, and provided a 20 to 500 Hz bandwidth (12 dB/octave). The input impedance of the system Z_{in} , was stated to be $> 1000 \text{ M}\Omega$. The recording system was connected to a printer for hard copies and a specially designed calibrated force measurement system. The force measurement system looked quite similar to a vertical weight lifting device had a total of 40 kg weights and was placed at the foot end of the couch. Weights could be lifted via a long adjustable strap, placed on the subject's wrists. A force transducer calibrated at 2kg/V, was installed on the force measurement system, and was connected to an oscilloscope placed 1.5 m above ground for visual feedback, enabling the subject to maintain constant the requested percentage of MVC. A personal computer (PC-Pentium III/660 MHz) was also connected to the electromyography unit for storing the recorded raw signal, digitized by a 12-bit Analogue-to-Digital (A/D) converter (E Series Multifunction I/O – 250KS/S, from National Instruments). The sampling frequency of 1 kHz and the recording process (start/stop and the recording time of 5 seconds) were controlled through a program working under LABVIEW 6.0 (National Instruments, Inc.), installed on the PC.

The subject laid on his/her back having his dominant arm horizontal and abducted at 90° . The arm was placed along the side of the subject's body. The weight lifting device's strap was placed at the wrist of the subject. During the experiment, it was ensured that

the dominant arm was not lifted from the couch or moved away from the body. With this arrangement, unintentional movements from other parts of the body were eliminated or reduced [11].

Signals were detected using four parallel silver bars (10 mm apart, 10 mm long, 1 mm wide)

fixed on a plastic block made by Dispositivi Elettronici Medicali of Italy. Although circular electrodes are generally preferred, than bar electrodes, the correct diameter choice for circular electrodes is not straight forward, since this influences the low-pass filtering effect of the detected signal. A theoretical approach made by Helal et al 1992 [26], suggested that the choice of electrode diameter should be a compromise between the desired signal-to-noise ratio and the desired frequency bandwidth. On the other hand parallel bar type electrodes are gaining grounds, based mainly on De-Lucas experience [27] that a parallel configuration of an equivalent detection area as a circular configuration, intersects more fibers and hence provides a higher signal-to noise ratio. Furthermore, an electrode block containing fixed distance parallel bar electrodes, offers practical advantages as well, and hence was preferred in this study. The electrodes used in this set-up had a zero-gain, with a phase margin of 50° and input impedance $Z_{in} > 1000 \text{ M } \Omega$ as per manufactures specifications. Skin preparation of the BB muscle and the dominant arm took place with an alcohol wash. A special conductive paste (Elefix, Model Z-402CE by Nihon Kohden) was placed on the four electrodes. Special care was taken to avoid excessive paste, which could influence results by short-circuiting the electrodes.

The subject was asked to bend his/her arm and the actual length of the BB muscle was then measured. The electrode block was then placed and secured with a 50 mm Micropore adhesive tape, on the BB in such a way, so that the second electrode towards the dominant arm was always at a distance equal

to 1/3 of the BB length. This arrangement ensured that all four electrodes were between the motor point and the tendinous insertion and the electrode positioning was as consistent as possible for all subjects. This was carried out without the necessity of electrically stimulating the BB muscle to find the exact location of the motor point. These criteria were strictly followed to ensure consistent positioning for all recordings. The ground electrode was positioned distantly from the recording electrode to ensure a common reference to the amplifier's differential input [27]. The ground electrode was rather large (3 cm in diameter) ensuring a very good contact with the skin.

Before the actual recording took place, the subject was asked to experiment at various FLs to get accustomed with the process. Then she/he was asked to pull at MVC three times with an interval of two minutes in between. A mark of the average MVC was made on the oscilloscope with a red tape. It was stressed to the subjects that they had to keep the FL each time as constant as possible for the 5 seconds duration. The subject had two minutes to relax before the actual recording started. The subject was then asked to pull observing the oscilloscope's DC line, which had to reach the bottom part of the red tape. Once this was reached, the signal was recorded for 5 seconds, and afterwards the subject was asked to relax for a further two minutes. The same procedure was performed again, at the same FL. Then, the tape was placed at positions on the oscilloscope screen corresponding to 70, 50, 30, and 10% of MVC and the process was repeated. For the analysis the pair with the largest single differential output was used.

C. Time domain analysis

For each EMG epoch of 5 seconds, at each force level, the following parameters were measured in the time domain:

- 1) *Turns per second, t/s*: Number of slope reversals per second separated from the previous and the following turn by an amplitude difference greater than $20 \mu\text{V}$.

2) *Zero crossings per second, zc/s*: Defined as the number of sign reversals exceeding a threshold of 20 μV per second.

A similar approach was followed for needle EMG by Fuglsang et al [32] and Pattichis et al [33]. On the other hand Inbar et al [17], defined a zero as 0.1 per cent of the maximum voltage which drove the comparator, whereas Preece et al [31], defined the zero crossing frequency as excursions of the signal from baseline of greater than 1% of full scale deflection. Hof [28], defined the zero crossings frequency as half the number of zero crossings per second and without the use of a threshold made a comparison between theoretical and experimental values.

In this study the threshold of 20 μV was selected after experimenting with thresholds at different levels. Initially 50 μV was selected, but this caused many epochs to give zero or very small values for turns per second and zero crossings per second. This was also applicable for threshold values of 40 and 30 μV . On the other hand, 10 μV proved to be too small, since the preamplifier's noise is of the order of a few μV rms.

D. Power spectral analysis

For each 512 ms epoch, the average power spectrum PS curve was computed by taking the FFT of 512 points, with 25% overlaps segments. The 512 ms epoch satisfy the stationarity criteria [17]. The following parameters were computed from the power spectrum curve:

1) *Median frequency, Pf_{med}* : Frequency dividing the area under the PS curve in two equal parts.

$$\sum_{n=0}^{Pf_{p-1}} PS(n) = \sum_{Pf_p}^{N-1} PS(n) \quad (1)$$

2) *Frequency at maximum power, Pf_x* : Frequency corresponding to the peak of the PS curve.

3) *Total power, P_{total}* : Calculated as the total area under the PS curve, and

4) *Maximum power, P_{max}* : Highest value of the PS curve.

E. Bispectral analysis

For a real zero-mean, stationary process $\{X(k)\}$, the third-order cumulant (TOC) is defined [29] as the expected value of the triple product:

$$R(m, n) = E\{X(k)X(k+m)X(k+n)\}, \quad (2)$$

and the bispectrum is defined [29] as the Fourier transform of the TOC sequence:

$$B(\omega_1, \omega_2) = \sum_{m=-\infty}^{m=\infty} \sum_{n=-\infty}^{n=\infty} R(m, n) e^{-j(\omega_1 m + \omega_2 n)} \quad (3)$$

In addition, the sum of magnitudes of the estimated bispectrum is computed by:

$$D = \sum_{(\omega_1, \omega_2)} |B(\omega_1, \omega_2)| \quad (4)$$

To quantify the non-Gaussianity of a random process, the normalized bispectrum, or bicoherence is estimated as follows:

$$B_n(\omega_1, \omega_2) = \frac{B(\omega_1, \omega_2)}{\sqrt{P(\omega_1)P(\omega_2)P(\omega_1 + \omega_2)}}, \quad (5)$$

where $P(\cdot)$ is the estimated power spectrum. The test of Gaussianity is based on the mean bicoherence power, defined as follows:

$$S_g = \sum |B_n(\omega_1, \omega_2)|^2 \quad (6)$$

with the summation of P points performed over the non-redundant region [30].

For each epoch, the average bispectrum curve was computed using a window of 512 points in length with a 25% of overlap. The following tests and parameters were applied and computed, based on the bispectrum curve:

1) *Gaussianity test, sg* , (actually zero-skewness test): It basically involves deciding whether or not the expected value of the estimated bicoherence index is zero, i.e., $E\{B_n(\omega_1, \omega_2)\} = 0$. This is due to the fact that when $B(\omega_1, \omega_2) = 0$ the sg statistic in (6) is X^2 distributed, with $2P$ degrees of freedom [30]. Consequently, by examining whether the observed sg is consistent or not with a central chi-squared distribution, the assumption of Gaussianity or non-

Gaussianity could be adopted, respectively. A measure of this consistency is the probability-of-false alarm value, that is, the probability of being wrong in the adoption of the non-zero bispectrum assumption [30]. In our case, the non-Gaussianity assumption was accepted if the probability-of-false alarm was less than 5%.

- 2) *Linearity test, sl*: It involves deciding whether or not the estimated bicoherence is constant in the bi-frequency domain, employing a measure of the absolute difference (dR) between a theoretical inter-quartile range, R' , which corresponds to a $X^2_2(\lambda)$, i.e., a chi-squared distributed random variable with two degrees of freedom and a non-centrality parameter λ , and the estimated inter-quartile range, R , derived from the estimated squared bicoherence [29]. In our case, the non linearity hypothesis was adopted when $\frac{dR}{R'} > 2$.
- 3) *Bispectrum peak, Bmax*: Calculated as the peak of the bispectrum curve.
- 4) *Location of the Bmax in the x-direction, Bx*: It was calculated as the location of the peak of the bispectrum curve in the x-direction.
- 5) *Location of Bmax in the y-direction, By*: It was calculated as the location of the peak of the bispectrum curve in the y-direction.
- 6) *Rate of change of Bmax in the x-direction, Bxslope*, and
- 7) *Rate of change of Bmax in the y-direction direction, Byslope*.

The BS analysis was performed with the Hispec toolkit of MATLAB 5.3 (Mathworks Inc).

Results

A total of 94 subjects were analyzed for the five force levels. Figures 1(a) and 1(d), show a time domain plot, the corresponding power Figs 1(b) and 1(e) and bi-frequency plots Figs 1(c) and 1(f) of signals recorded at 10%

and 70% MVC from a male subject. Table 2, summarizes the mean and standard deviation values as well as the median and quartile values for all parameters analyzed at each force level. Table 3 tabulates the descriptive statistics for the median frequency. Table 4 presents the Wilcoxon signed rank test used to classify the transition between any two-force levels as significant (S), or non-significant (NS), based on a confidence level of 95% ($p < 0.05$). The Wilcoxon signed rank test has been preferred than the usually used t-test, which relies on the assumption that the data is taken from a normally distributed set. [9]. Figure 2 illustrates box plots for the six parameters influenced significantly with FL. Also, histogram distributions for t/s , $Pfmed$, and $Bmax$ are presented in Fig. 3, for the five corresponding FLs. Table 5 gives the Spearman correlation coefficient and was used to identify possible correlation results for selected parameter pairs. This coefficient has been preferred instead the corresponding parametric test of Pearson [34], used by other researchers [16], for the same reasons listed above.

A. Time Domain Analysis

As given in Table 2, the median values of t/s were, 3, 10, 17, 23, and 22, for FL at 10, 30, 50, 70 and 100% of MVC respectively. The number of turns per second increases significantly with force as given in Table 4 and illustrated in Fig. 2(a). The histogram distribution of t/s is given in Fig. 3(a). The number of zero crossings per second, zc/s , exhibited a similar pattern, i.e., the number of zc/s increases significantly with FL, as given in Table 5 and illustrated in Fig. 2(b). The median values of zc/s at the corresponding force level were 0, 4, 10, 17 and 83, as tabulated in Table 2. The turns per second, Fig. 3, show at 10% MVC, a significant ($p < 0.05$) non-normal distribution, a significant +ve skew (more observations in the left-tail than normal), and a significant +ve kurtosis (more observations are clustered around the mean value (3), than normal). At 30% MVC, again the distribution is significantly non-normally distributed, it

presents a significant +ve skew, but presents a non-significant ($p>0.05$) +ve kurtosis. The distribution is still significantly non-normally distributed, but presents a non-significant +ve skew and a significant -ve kurtosis (more observations are in the tails, with less clustered around the mean (10), than normal). At 70% MVC, the distribution remains significantly non-normally distributed, presents however a non-significant -ve skew (more observations in the right tail than normal), and a significant -ve kurtosis. Finally 100% MVC does not present a significant non-normal distribution ($p>0.05$), nor a significant -ve skew or a -ve kurtosis. Table 5 shows that there is a good correlation (0.65) between t/s and zc/s , whereas both t/s and zc/s exhibit also a good correlation with Maximum Power, P_{max} , and total power, P_{total} .

B. Frequency Domain Analysis

Median frequency. The median values of P_{fmed} were 104 Hz, 101 Hz, 99 Hz, 95 Hz, 93 Hz for the corresponding five force levels (see Tables 2 and 3). The median frequency decreases significantly with FL, as given in Table 4 and illustrated in Fig. 2(c). Median frequency is of particular interest for the reasons outlined in the introduction of this paper, with its descriptive statistics given in detail in Table 3. The corresponding box-plots and histogram distributions are given in Figs. 2(c) and 3, respectively. From Fig. 3(b), the distribution at 10% MVC is shown to present a significant non-normal distribution, with a significant +ve skew and a non-significant -ve kurtosis. The distribution at 30% MVC, still presents a significant non-normal distribution, but also a significant +ve skew and +ve kurtosis. At 50% of MVC however, P_{fmed} approximates a normal distribution ($p=0.23$). It presents also non-significant +ve skew and kurtosis. The distribution becomes significantly non-normally distributed, once again at 70% MVC, with a significant +ve skew and a non-significant +ve kurtosis. Finally at 100% MVC, the distribution as at 50% MVC, does not present a significant non-normal distribution

($p=0.081$), but significant +ve skew and kurtosis.

Frequency at maximum power. The median values for all 94 subjects for the frequency at maximum power for the five force levels investigated are, 76 Hz, 74 Hz, 77 Hz, 75 Hz, and 72 Hz respectively (see Table 2). As given in Table 4, this parameter is not affected with force level neither does it exhibit any correlation with other parameters.

Maximum and total power. The median values for the 94 subjects, for the logarithm of the maximum power for the five FLs are, -0.6 nV^2Hz^{-1} , -0.04 nV^2Hz^{-1} , 0.5 nV^2Hz^{-1} , 0.7 nV^2Hz^{-1} , and 1.3 nV^2Hz^{-1} as well as those for the total power are 0.4 nV^2Hz^{-1} , 1 nV^2Hz^{-1} , and 1.5 nV^2Hz^{-1} , 1.8 nV^2Hz^{-1} and 2.2 nV^2Hz^{-1} . Both of these parameters showed a significant increase with force level as given in Table 4 and illustrated in Figs. 2(d) and 2(e), respectively. An excellent correlation between the maximum power and total power and a good correlation between the power and time domain parameters were found.

C. Bispectrum Domain Analysis

Gaussianity and linearity tests. The median values for the test of Gaussianity, sg , indicate that the signal is non-Gaussian distributed, with higher values at 30% of MVC (see Table 2). Increase of force level does not cause significant change in sg (see Table 4). The linearity test median values indicate that the signal presents a higher linearity pattern at 30% of MVC (see Table 2). Increase of force level, does not cause a significant change in the linearity test except in the case of force transition from 70 to 100% MVC (see Table 4).

Bispectrum peak amplitude. The median values of the logarithm of the bispectrum peak amplitude were 1.9, 2.1, 2.1, 2.2, and 2.4 nV^3Hz^{-2} , see Table 2. The bispectrum amplitude increases significantly with force level, as given in Table 4 except in the case between 30-50% MVC. Figure 2(f) illustrates the effect of force level on this parameter. Figure 3(c) shows the significant non-normal distribution occurring at 10% MVC, as well as the significant +ve skew and +ve kurtosis.

Similar conclusions may be drawn for 30%, 50%, 70% and 100% of MVC.

Bispectrum peak amplitude in the x and y-directions. The position of the bispectrum peak in the x and y directions B_x and B_y respectively, remains fairly constant (non-significant difference), with median values in the region of 52-53 Hz and 47-49 Hz respectively for the five FLs. A good correlation was found between B_x and B_y (0.71), see Table 5.

Slope of the maximum amplitude of the Bispectrum in the x and y-directions. The median values of the slope of the bispectrum peak in the x - and y -axis B_x slope and B_y slope, were in the region of 49-57 $\text{nV}^3\text{Hz}^{-3}$ and 12-14 $\text{nV}^3\text{Hz}^{-3}$ respectively. An excellent correlation was found between the two parameters whereas a good correlation was found between the slope of the bispectrum peak in the x and y direction with the position of the bispectrum peak, see Table 5.

D. Other Findings

In this study no significant differences on all 13 parameters examined with age, using the Wilcoxon test ($p < 0.05$), were found. However an increase of Pf_{med} and MPF , when voluntary contraction level was increased from 20% to 80%, was found to be smaller [23] in elderly subjects than in younger subjects.

This study did not detect any significant differences with gender either. Gender division was performed for two gender groups, i.e., one for the age group from 20 to 29 years of age, where the gender is evenly distributed (10 male and 10 female subjects), and one for the entire group (56 male and 38 female subjects).

Repeatability measurements on eleven subjects were also performed, with two objectives: (i) to investigate whether similar results are recorded after a period of time had elapsed, and (ii) if analysis depends on whether recording begins from maximum to minimum % MVC or vice versa. No significant differences ($p > 0.05$) were found in either case.

Discussion

In the present study, SEMG reference values extracted in the time domain, frequency domain and bispectrum domain are investigated during isometric voluntary contraction. The mean and standard deviation, median values, the first and third quartile ranges of the parameters were calculated and their influence with force was examined. Transition from one FL to another was classified as significant or non-significant, using the Wilcoxon signed rank test ($p < 0.05$). Correlation between any two parameters was also examined. The findings of these parameters are discussed in this section, as well as compared to the findings of other studies.

A. Time Domain Analysis

Turns per second and zero crossings per second. Preece and co-workers [31] compared the usefulness of these two parameters for surface and needle recordings. They concluded that surface recordings might provide at least equal information for quantitative analysis for some muscles like the tibialis anterior, and even more reliable for other muscles such as the rectus femoris. Needle electrodes have also been used to examine the behaviour of zero crossings. Fuglsang and co-workers [32] examined the influence of this parameter with force increase via signals recorded from the Biceps Brachii muscle. They concluded that the number of zero crossings increases only up to mid force levels and then levels off. This remark is in opposition with the findings of this study, where the number of zero crossings per second was found to increase continuously and significantly at all force levels from 10 to 100% of MVC.

B. Frequency Domain Analysis

Median frequency. One of the earliest studies conducted on normal subjects regarding the influence of voluntary contraction on the shape of the PS [18], noted a shift of the spectrum towards the lower frequency region with force

increase. Although not stated by the author [18], this would result in a decrease in the median frequency, Pf_{med} , as shown in this study. Other studies have shown an increase in the median frequency (although insignificant), with force level [13] others have found Pf_{med} to be independent of FL [17] whereas others have simply stated that this parameter is somehow affected by IVC without specifying how [14]. On the other hand Farina et al [2002], does not support a relationship between spectral variables and force especially during ramp contractions. The range of normal values of Pf_{med} found by Krivickas [16] in attempting to evaluate clinically muscle fatigue was so broad that his group forecasted that Pf_{med} would preclude the clinical use of spectral analysis to evaluate muscle fatigue. In this study it is shown that Pf_{med} , decreases significantly with force level, which is in full agreement with the findings of a review paper [2] where it is stated “*the analysis of decline in median frequency with fatigue or increasing force is a measure which has no single correlate in standard needle EMG*”.

Frequency at maximum power. The effect of force level on the frequency at maximum power was examined by a limited number of studies. One study [6] has shown that the frequency at maximum power does not provide any statistically significant difference with respect to the level of force. Gander and Hudgins [13] have shown that with an increase in torque (Nm), the frequency at maximum power increased and decreased slightly throughout the recording process, without following a consistent pattern. This study has shown that frequency at maximum power remains fairly constant with force level, whereas the changes in the first and third quartile ranges are insignificant.

Maximum and Total power. To the best of our knowledge, no study has investigated the maximum power influence with FL. Even more, total power has not been fully investigated. Merletti and De Luca [5] stated that large muscles, such as the BB, present a non-linear relationship with force increase. This statement is in agreement with the findings of

this study where the maximum power was found to increase considerably with force in a non-linear way.

C. Bispectrum Domain Analysis

Gaussianity and linearity test. Our results are in agreement with Pattichis and co-workers [33], whose results were obtained with needle electrodes. With the exception of Pattichis and co-workers [33], no other groups examining this parameter were traced in the literature. Their study showed that the mean bicoherence values increased continuously with FL.

Unfortunately, no studies examining the behaviour of the Bispectrum peak, its coordinates and its slope in the x and y -directions were traced in the literature for comparison.

D. Other Findings

Parameter pairs presenting an excellent and good correlation are presented in Table 4. Inbar and co-workers [17] examined the correlation between zero crossings and median frequency, which were found to be excellently correlated, which is in opposition with the findings of this study. Age dependence examined showed no significant differences on all 13 parameters examined, using the Wilcoxon test ($p < 0.05$).

This study did not detect any significant differences with gender either. However Bilodeau *et al.* [35], found differences between the two genders for Pf_{med} but not for MPF . The group states that the difference in skinfold layer is the main contributor for differences between the two parameters, although no significant differences were noted for the BB muscle (1 mm difference, $p > 0.05$). Furthermore they had stated that increase in spectrum parameters were more obvious when using ramp contractions as opposed to step contractions, which is in opposition with the findings of Gerdle *et al.* [9]. The mean standard error of the mean, SE found by Bilodeau *et al.* [35], was 4.0, which

is nearly double than the average *SE* found in this study for the five force levels used here, being 2.3.

Conclusions

The aim of this study was to compute reference SEMG values of parameters extracted in the time, frequency, and bi-frequency domains, and to investigate the influence of force level on 13 different parameters from SEMG signals recorded from the BB muscle of 94 normal subjects. The findings of this study can be summarised as follows:

- (i) The time domain parameters turns per second and number of zero crossing increase significantly with force level,
- (ii) From the power spectrum, the median frequency parameter decreases significantly with force level, whereas max power and total power increase significantly with force level,
- (iii) The bispectrum parameter maximum amplitude increases significantly with force level with the exception the transition from 30 to 50% MVC. Although the test for Gaussianity and linearity show no significant difference with force level, the SEMG signal exhibits a more Gaussian distribution with increase of force up to 70% MVC. The SEMG linearity test shows that the signal is more constant at MVC and less constant at 70% of MVC,
- (iv) The time domain parameters were found to have a good correlation between them as well as, between each one of them and maximum and total power. Maximum and total power, exhibit an excellent correlation between them. The median frequency has a good correlation with the Bispectrum peak amplitude (-ve) and its slope in the x-direction. A good correlation was found between all possible pair combinations of the coordinates and slope of the Bispectrum peak. The Bispectrum peak amplitude presents also a good (-ve),

correlation with its coordinates in the x and y direction as well as with its slope in the x direction. Finally the slope of the Bispectrum peak in the x-direction presented an excellent correlation between the slope of the Bispectrum peak in the y-direction

- (v) No significant differences exist between values based on gender or age.

At present, these findings are compared with signals recorded from patients suffering with neuromuscular diseases like motor neuron disease (Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis etc) or Myopathy (Duchenne, Limb girdle etc). Preliminary findings suggest that certain differences exist between normal SEMG findings and corresponding findings analysed from patients. Also, our group will, also investigate the use of SEMG in the assessment of treatment followed. Most importantly, a more realistic scenario of the use of SEMG qualitative analysis findings in a clinical context would be to combine these findings with the clinical assessment, muscle biopsy and, or nerve biopsy data, biochemical findings, and genetic and molecular genetic findings, in a decision support system for the assessment and monitoring of neuromuscular disorders. This approach was followed by our group but with needle EMG quantitative analysis findings with very promising results [33]. Furthermore, the normal SEMG findings reported in this study, although they were recorded at a short duration (5 sec) at different force levels, could easily be exploited in the rehabilitation laboratory for monitoring the elderly and the disabled, in the patient home monitoring (telemonitoring), or in the sports and occupational medicine laboratories for the assessment of sports trauma or injuries, or workers subject to stress [37].

Last but not least, it is generally accepted that the wide spread of the use of SEMG is hindered by the lack of standardised algorithms, digital libraries, reference values, and training [37]. The EU funded SENIAM project [38] contributed significantly in the

first two directions, with this study contributing significantly in the third direction, towards, the creation of an extensive digital library with normal values for the Biceps Brachii muscle only. The need for creating reference values for the other muscles still exists. The rehabilitation doctors and therapists, or the sports and occupational medicine experts could use only the time domain parameters, t/s and zc/s , that are very easily to interpret and compute. To a lesser extent this is also applicable to the power spectrum total power and median frequency.

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Table 1. SEMG studies and findings in chronological order carried out on the BB muscle on normal subjects

GROUP	YEAR	REF	N (age)	PARAMETERS									COMMENTS
				<i>t/s</i>	<i>zc/s</i>	<i>Pfmed</i>	<i>Pfx</i>	<i>Pmax</i>	<i>Ptotal</i>	<i>PS</i>	<i>MPF</i>	<i>RP</i>	
Chaffin	1968	[18]	12 (NP)								√		PS→LSB [5 & 30% MVC, 15 sec/NP]
Hagberg <i>et al.</i>	1982	[7]	4 (21-24)									√	<i>MPF</i> ↓ FL > 25% MVC [5-80% MVC 3-5 sec/1 min]
Muro <i>et al.</i>	1982	[6]	5 (32.5±8.2)				√					√	<i>Pfx</i> ↓ FL; <i>MPF</i> ↑ FL [0.25 0.50 1.0 2.0 3 kg, 10 sec/30 min]
Gander <i>et al.</i>	1985	[13]	6 (20-40)			√	√				√	√	<i>Pfmed</i> ↑ FL; <i>Pfx</i> ↓ FL <i>PS</i> → HFB ↑ FL [1-10Nm randomly selected, 8.2 sec/2-several min]
Inbar <i>et al.</i>	1986	[17]	[9]		√	√							<i>zc/s</i> ↓ FL; <i>Pfmed</i> ↓ FL <i>zc/s</i> correlated with <i>Pfmed</i> & <i>MPF</i> [30 50 70 90% MVC, 6 sec/NP]
Moritani <i>et al.</i>	1987	[8]	12 (26.3±2.5)									√	<i>MPF</i> ↑ FL up to 80% of MVC [0-80% MVC, 5 sec/2 min]
Shankar <i>et al.</i>	1989	[14]	10 (25-28)			√			√				<i>Pfmed</i> affected by torque [4.9 Nm monitored at 8 joint positions, 10 sec/5-10 min]
Gerdle <i>et al.</i>	1990	[9]	9 (30-40)									√	<i>MPF</i> ↑ up to 60% MVC [20 40 60 80 100% MVC, 1-2 sec/several mins]
Li <i>et al.</i>	1996	[10]	12 (22-25)						√			√	<i>Ptotal</i> ↑ FL* <i>MPF</i> ↓ with distance from end plate zone* [20 40 60% MVC, brief contraction/NP]
Krivickas <i>et al.</i>	1998	[16]	31 (22-37)			√							<i>Pfmed</i> range broad, may limit the clinical use of spectral analysis [50% MVC, 45 sec/15 mins]
Rainoldi <i>et al.</i>	1999	[11]	10 (23-43)									√	<i>MPF</i> ↓ FL 30 to 70% MVC [10 30 50 70% MVC randomly selected, 30 sec/5mins]
Farina <i>et al.</i>	2002	[12]	10 (22-35)			√						√	No relationship between spectral parameters and force may be drawn
This study	2003		94 (5-69)	√	√	√	√	√	√				<i>t/s</i> , <i>zc/s</i> , <i>Pmax</i> , <i>Ptotal</i> , <i>Bmax</i> ↑ FL, <i>Pfmed</i> ↓ FL <i>Bx</i> , <i>By</i> , <i>Bxslope</i> , <i>Byslope</i> , <i>Pfx</i> , <i>sg</i> , <i>sl</i> , ↑ of FL [10 30 50 70 100% MVC, 5 sec/2mins]

Note: * Not statistically proven

Bmax (maximum peak of bispectrum)

Byslope (slope of Bmax in y-axis),

FL (force level)

[FL used, recording time /resting time]

LSB (lower frequency band)

HFB (higher frequency band)

MPF (mean power frequency),

MVC (maximum voluntary contraction)

N (number of subjects),

Bxslope (slope of Bmax in x-direction),

Pfmed (median frequency),*Pfx* (frequency at maximum power),

→ (shifts), ↑ (increase), ↓ (decrease), ↓↑

(independent)

Pmax (maximum power)*Ptotal* (total power)*PS* (Power Spectrum shape),*RP* (relative power),*By* (location of Bmax in y-axis),*sg* (Gaussianity test),*Bx* (location of Bmax in x-axis),*sl* (Linearity test),*t/s* (turns per second),*zc/s* (zero crossings per second)

Table 2. Mean and \pm Standard Deviation (mean \pm SD), together with median and first and third quartile range values median(P_{25%}-P_{75%}) of the parameters analysed. (log values are used for, *Pmax*, *Ptotal*, and *Bmax*)

%MVC	10	30	50	70	100
Time domain parameters					
<i>t/s</i>	6 \pm 7.5 3 (0-8)	12 \pm 10.5 10 (2-19)	17 \pm 12.4 17 (6-26)	22 \pm 13 23 (13-30)	28 \pm 12.8 22 (20-36)
<i>zc/s</i>	3-6 0 (0-2)	7-8.8 4 (0-10)	12-11.2 10 (1-21)	16-11.7 17 (6-25)	22-11.8 23 (16-30)
Frequency domain parameters					
<i>Pfmed</i> (Hz)	109 \pm 26.8 104 (90-125)	104 \pm 23 101 (88-116)	102 \pm 21.4 99 (86-115)	100 \pm 21.1 95 (84-112)	96 \pm 19.7 93 (83-110)
<i>Pfx</i> (Hz)	80 \pm 23 76 (64-96)	76 \pm 19 74 (63-83)	80 \pm 20 77 (67-93)	78 \pm 19.3 75 (65-91)	77 \pm 20 72 (64-88)
<i>Pmax</i> (nV ² Hz ⁻¹)	-0.5 \pm 0.84 -0.6 (-1.1-0.08)	0.06 \pm 0.91 -0.04 (-0.6-0.6)	0.5 \pm 0.98 0.5 (-0.2-1.17)	0.85 \pm 1.03 0.7 (0.16-1.5)	1.3 \pm 1.03 1.3 (0.57-2.04)
<i>Ptotal</i> (nV ² Hz ⁻¹)	0.5 \pm 0.8 0.4 (0-1.0)	1.1 \pm 0.9 1 (0.43-1.6)	1.5 \pm 0.9 1.5 (0.85-2.1)	1.8 \pm 0.92 1.8 (1.14-2.4)	2.2 \pm 0.94 2.2 (1.6-2.8)
Bispectrum parameters					
<i>Sg</i>	239 \pm 121 198 (166-292)	237 \pm 116 213 (169-253)	225 \pm 84 202 (171-250)	220 \pm 84 199 (173-247)	236 \pm 118 205 (158-255)
<i>Sl</i>	1.6 \pm 1.6 1.1 (0.7-1.6)	1.7 \pm 1.4 1.3(0.7-2.6)	1.6 \pm 1.5 1.2(0.6-2.0)	1.4 \pm 1.5 1.14(0.64-1.6)	2 \pm 4.2 1.2(0.8-2.1)
<i>Bmax</i> (nV ³ Hz ⁻²)	2 \pm 0.77 1.9 (1.6-2.3)	2.2 \pm 0.95 2.1 (1.6-2.50)	2.3 \pm 0.88 2.1 (1.70-2.58)	2.4 \pm 0.9 2.2 (1.8-2.8)	2.5 \pm 0.9 2.4 (2.0-2.9)
<i>Bx</i> (Hz)	54 \pm 26 52 (45-59)	57 \pm 30 52 (46-60)	53 \pm 11 53 (46-59)	55 \pm 13 53 (48-60)	55 \pm 13 53 (48-60)
<i>By</i> (Hz)	37 \pm 24 47 (22-57)	40 \pm 24 48 (21-57)	39 \pm 24 47 (24-57)	40 \pm 26 49 (22-58)	39 \pm 24 47 (22-57)
<i>Bxslope</i> (nV ³ Hz ⁻³)	60 \pm 25 57 (40-71)	58 \pm 24 56 (41-71)	56 \pm 23 54 (42-73)	54 \pm 22 53 (37-71)	51 \pm 20 49 (37-63)
<i>Byslope</i> (nV ³ Hz ⁻³)	13 \pm 5.4 12 (10-16)	14 \pm 5.4 14 (10-16)	13 \pm 4.7 13 (10-16)	14 \pm 5.3 13 (11-16)	14 \pm 5.3 13 (10-16)

Table 3. Descriptive statistics for the median frequency, *Pfmed*, for % MVC for 94 normal subjects

%MVC	10%	30%	50%	70%	100%
<i>Mean</i>	109	104	101.7	99.6	96.3
<i>95% CI</i>	103 to 115	99.3 to 108.9	97 to 106	95 to 104	92.16 to 100.4
<i>Variance</i>	722	532.9	456.8	445.8	388.57
<i>SD</i>	26.9	23	21.4	21.1	19.7
<i>SE</i>	2.8	2.42	2.24	2.21	2.07
<i>CV</i>	25%	22%	21%	21%	20%
<i>Median</i>	104	101	99	95	93
<i>96.5% CI</i>	95 to 113	95 to 105	93 to 105	91 to 103	89 to 98
<i>Range</i>	135	125	115	114	123
<i>IQR</i>	37.5	28.5	28.5	28	27
<i>2.5th Percentile</i>	65.9	66.9	59.9	64.3	58.9
<i>25th Percentile</i>	90	88	87	84.5	83.5
<i>50th Percentile</i>	104	101	99	95	93
<i>75th Percentile</i>	127.5	116	115	112.5	110.5
<i>97.5th Percentile</i>	165.8	159.2	152.9	145.1	132.1
<i>Near outliers (value)</i>	1 (187)	2 (164, 190)	1 (168)	1 (177)	1 (170)
<i>(coefficient, p)</i>					
<i>Shapiro-Wilk</i>	0.97, 0.034	0.95, 0.0026	0.982, 0.227	0.96, 0.006	0.975 to 0.081
<i>Skewness</i>	0.54, 0.0349	0.91, 0.001	0.468, 0.065	0.79, 0.003	0.54, 0.035
<i>Kurtosis</i>	-0.176, 0.835	1.29, 0.042	0.39, 0.36	0.90, 0.107	1.23, 0.05

CI (Confidence Interval),
CV (Coefficient of Variation),

SD (Standard Deviation),
IQR (Interquartile Range).

SE (Standard Error of the Mean),

Table 4. Transition classification from one force level to another, using the Wilcoxon signed rank test at ($p < 0.05$). S and NS indicate significant and non significant difference respectively

	Turns per second, t/s		Med freq, P_{med}				Gaussianity, sg							
	Zero crossings per second, zc/s		Frequency at max power, P_{fx}	Max power, P_{max}	Total power, P_{total}	Linearity, sl	Bmax ampl, B_{max}	Bispectrum peak in x-dir, B_x	Bispectrum peak in y-dir, B_y	Bispectrum slope in x-dir, B_{xslope}	Bispectrum slope in y dir, B_{yslope}			
10 to 30%	S	S	S	S	S	S	NS	NS	S	NS	NS	S	S	
10 to 50%	S	S	S	NS	S	S	NS	NS	S	NS	NS	S	S	
10 to 70%	S	S	S	NS	S	S	NS	NS	S	NS	NS	NS	NS	
10 to 100%	S	S	S	NS	S	S	NS	NS	S	NS	NS	S	S	
30 to 50%	S	S	S	NS	S	S	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	
30 to 70%	S	S	S	NS	S	S	NS	NS	S	NS	NS	S	NS	
30 to 100%	S	S	S	NS	S	S	NS	NS	S	NS	NS	NS	NS	
50 to 70%	S	S	S	NS	S	S	NS	NS	S	NS	NS	S	NS	
50-100%	S	S	S	NS	S	S	NS	NS	S	NS	NS	S	S	
70 to 100%	S	S	S	NS	S	S	NS	S	S	NS	NS	S	NS	

Table 5. Parameter pairs presenting an excellent and good correlation performed with Spearman correlation test with 95% confidence interval, CI.

<i>Parameter pair</i>	Correlation coefficient	95% CI	Classification
<i>t/s-zc/s</i>	0.65	0.59 to 0.70	Good
<i>t/s-Pmax</i>	0.67	0.62 to 0.72	Good
<i>t/s-Ptotal</i>	0.73	0.69 to 0.77	Good
<i>zc/s-Pmax</i>	0.69	0.64 to 0.71	Good
<i>zc/s-Ptotal</i>	0.66	0.61 to 0.71	Good
<i>Pmax-Ptotal</i>	0.87	0.85 to 0.89	Excellent
<i>Pfmed – Bmax</i>	-0.65	-0.7 to -0.6	Good
<i>Bx – Bmax</i>	-0.62	-0.68 to -0.56	Good
<i>By – Bmax</i>	-0.6	-0.66 to -0.54	Good
<i>Bxslope-Byslope</i>	0.84	0.81 to 0.87	Excellent
<i>Pfmed-Bxslope</i>	0.6	0.53 to 0.65	Good
<i>Bx-By</i>	0.71	0.66 to 0.75	Good
<i>Bx-Bxslope</i>	0.62	0.57 to 0.68	Good
<i>Bx-Byslope</i>	0.73	0.68 to 0.77	Good
<i>By-Bxslope</i>	0.69	0.64 to 0.73	Good
<i>By-Byslope</i>	0.64	0.58 to 0.69	Good
<i>Bxslope – Bmax</i>	-0.71	-0.75 to -0.66	Good

t/s: 27, zc/s: 16

t/s: 37, zc/s: 32

Pfmed: 110 Hz, Pfx: 105 Hz, logPx: 0.48nV²/Hz, logPtotal: 1.5n V²/Hz

Pfmed: 103 Hz, Pfx: 125 Hz, logPx: 1.41 nV²/Hz, logPtotal: 2.4 nV²/Hz

logBmax: 1.6 nV³/Hz², Bx: 63 Hz, By: 63 Hz Bxslope: 63 nV³/Hz³, Byslope 16 nV³/Hz³, sg: 203, sl: 1.9

logBmax: 2.1 nV³/Hz², Bx: 61 Hz, By: 61 Hz Bxslope: 56 nV³/Hz³, Byslope: 15 nV³/Hz³, sg: 185, sl: 0.6

Figure. 1. Time, power and bispectrum plots and features of a male subject aged 54 at 10 (1st column) and 70% (2nd column) of MVC.

Figure 2. *Boxplots* of parameters analysed that are influenced significantly with force level (see Table 4). The notched box shows the median, lower and upper quartiles and confidence interval around the median. The dotted line connects the nearest observations within 1.5 of the inter-quartile range (IQR) of the lower and upper quartiles. Crosses (+) and circles (o), indicate possible outliers—observations more than 1.5 x IQR and 3.0 x IQR from the quartiles respectively. Vertical lines show the requested non-parametric percentile range.

% MVC

Figure 3. Histogram distributions with force level for: (a) turns /second (b) median frequency, and (c) log bispectrum peak amplitude.

Appendix 5
Sample plots

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